

Volume: 1
Year: 2011
Symposium Edition: XXII

ISMEC GROUP SERIES
<http://mat520.unime.it/ismecacta/>
ISSN: 2239-2459

Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes

ISMEC 2011 XXII International Symposium on Metal Complexes

Giardini Naxos, Italy, June 13-16, 2011

Università degli Studi di Messina

Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes

ISMEC 2011 **XXII International Symposium on Metal Complexes** **Giardini Naxos, Italy, June 13-16, 2011**

Silvio Sammartano, Editor
University of Messina
President of the Scientific Committee of ISMEC 2011

Guido Crisponi, Editor
University of Cagliari
President of ISMEC Group

ISMEC GROUP SERIES
VOLUME: 1
YEAR: 2011
SYMPOSIUM EDITION: XXII

The

Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes (ISSN: 2239-2459)

are published annually online by the ISMEC Group

Editors:

Silvio Sammartano (*President of the Scientific Committee of ISMEC 2011*)

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università degli Studi di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
ssammartano@unime.it

Guido Crisponi (*President of ISMEC Group*)

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Cittadella Universitaria
09042 Monserrato – Cagliari, ITALY
crisponi@unica.it

Scientific Committee of ISMEC 2011:

Silvio Sammartano (Chairman)	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
Giuseppe Arena	<i>Università degli Studi di Catania</i>
Paloma Arranz Mascarós	<i>Universidad de Jaén</i>
Antonio Bianchi	<i>Università degli Studi di Firenze</i>
Guido Crisponi	<i>Università degli Studi di Cagliari</i>
Plinio Di Bernardo	<i>Università degli Studi di Padova</i>
Enrique García-España	<i>Universitat de València</i>
Antonio Gianguzza	<i>Università degli Studi di Palermo</i>
Juan Niclós Gutierrez	<i>Universidad de Granada</i>
Marian Olazabal	<i>Universidad del País Vasco</i>
Fernando Secco	<i>Università degli Studi di Pisa</i>
Manuel Valiente	<i>Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona</i>

Copyright:

Authors retain the copyrights of their acta, and their unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium are permitted, provided that the original work is properly cited. The use of general descriptive names, trade names, trademarks, and so forth in this publication, even if not specifically identified, does not imply that these names are not protected by the relevant laws and regulations. While the advice and information in this journal are believed to be true and accurate on the date of its going to press, neither the authors, the editors, nor the publisher can accept any legal responsibility for any errors or omissions that may be made. The publisher and the editors make no warranty, express or implied, with respect to the material contained herein.

Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes

ISMEC GROUP SERIES

VOLUME: 1

YEAR: 2011

SYMPOSIUM EDITION: XXII

<http://mat520.unime.it/ismecacta/>

ISSN: 2239-2459

Foreword

ISMEC 2011 is the 37th meeting in the series begun in 1974 as the annual congress of the Italian group of "Thermodynamics of complexes". In the late '80s, with the addition of Spanish participants, it became the Italian-Spanish Congress on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes (ISMEC), with annual meetings alternating between Italy and Spain. Last year, with the 21st edition of the congress at Bilbao, participation was widened again and the name was changed to "*International Symposium on Metal Complexes*". Over the years it has proved to be an effective and valuable meeting for scientists from all over the world and has facilitated the creation of many collaborative projects. The meeting is focused on different aspects of the study and application of the thermodynamics of complexes in the fields of Analytical, Biomedical, Environmental, Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, and aims to provide a valuable discussion forum on recent advances on the above mentioned areas, providing an unique opportunity for exchanging knowledge on leading edge developments in these and related fields. In particular, every year the following non-limitative scientific fields are covered:

Chemical Thermodynamics

Solution Equilibria

Complexes of biological, biochemical and environmental interest

Proteomics and Metabolomics

Metals in supramolecular chemistry

Metal complex interactions with DNA

Chemistry of cultural heritage

Speciation of biological fluids and natural waters

Metal nanoparticles

Computer methods for equilibrium analysis

Ligand interactions

During the 22nd edition of ISMEC, held from 13th to 16th June 2011 at Giardini Naxos (near Taormina, Italy) and organized by the ISMEC members of the University of Messina coordinated by Prof. Concetta De Stefano, we thought to provide a mechanism for publishing the acts of our symposia quickly and in a book form, creating this series. Its main purpose is to disclose rapidly the most recent advances of scientific research in the field of the thermodynamics of complexes, by publishing timely, comprehensive books developed from the ISMEC symposia. Every book of the series will be edited both by the President of the Scientific Committee of each ISMEC edition in collaboration with all other members, and by the President of ISMEC Group. Occasionally, other books of the series will be published, but always with the aim of providing readily accessible but accurate information both on the basic aspects and the new findings of chemical research in the same field.

Silvio Sammartano

and

Guido Crisponi

June 2011

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

<i>Silvio Sammartano (Chairman)</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
<i>Giuseppe Arena</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Catania</i>
<i>Paloma Arranz Mascarós</i>	<i>Universidad de Jaén</i>
<i>Antonio Bianchi</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Firenze</i>
<i>Guido Crisponi</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Cagliari</i>
<i>Plinio Di Bernardo</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Padova</i>
<i>Enrique García-España</i>	<i>Universitat de València</i>
<i>Antonio Gianguzza</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Palermo</i>
<i>Juan Niclós Gutierrez</i>	<i>Universidad de Granada</i>
<i>Marian Olazabal</i>	<i>Universidad del País Vasco</i>
<i>Fernando Secco</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Pisa</i>
<i>Manuel Valiente</i>	<i>Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona</i>

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

<i>Concetta De Stefano (President)</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
<i>Francesco Crea (Secretary)</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
<i>Sebastiano Campagna</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
<i>Alessandro De Robertis</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
<i>Claudia Foti</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
<i>Ottavia Giuffrè</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>
<i>Demetrio Milea</i>	<i>Università degli Studi di Messina</i>

Contacts:

Organizing Committee ISMEC 2011

email: ismec2011@mat520.unime.it

Phone +39 090 6765761/58/49

Fax +39 090 392827

Congress website: <http://mat520.unime.it/ismec2011>

Acta website: <http://mat520.unime.it/ismecacta>

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Monday 13th

h. 9.00 – 15.30 Registration of participants

h. 15.30 – 16.30 Opening Ceremony

Chairman: Antonio Gianguzza

h. 16.30 – 17.30 PL1 - Ocean Acidification on the Speciation of Metals
Frank J. Millero

h. 17.30 – 17.45 Coffee break

Chairman: Marian Olazabal

h. 17.45 – 18.05 OC1 - Chemically modified mesoporous silica for free iron sensing
Giovanni Emma, Maria Giovanna Guiso, Giancarla Alberti, Giacomo Dacarro, Angelo Taglietti, Raffaella Biesuz

h. 18.05 – 18.25 OC2 - Simultaneous Chromium and Copper sorption using grape stalks in packed columns
David Pujol, Florencio De La Torre, Jordi Poch, Núria Fiol, Isabel Villaescusa

h. 18.25 – 18.45 OC3 - SPION-Loaded Cellulose Sponge, a System for Arsenic Removal from Aqueous Solutions
D. Morillo Martín, G. Pérez González, M. Valiente Malmagro

h. 18.45 – 19.05 OC4 - Towards a more comprehensive modelling capability for aqueous solution thermodynamics
Darren Rowland, Peter May

h. 19.05 – 19.25 OC5 - The use of fundamental research to create superior product design
Simon Godfrey

h. 20.30 - Welcoming Cocktail

Tuesday 14th

Chairman: Giuseppe Arena

h. 09.00 – 10.00 **PL2-** Voltammetry as a potentiometric sensor. Significance of a Virtual Potential in the study of metal-ligand equilibria

Ignacy Cukrowski

Chairman: Enrique Garcia-España

h. 10.00 – 10.20 **OC6** - Experimental characterization and modelling of aqueous dispersions of ZnO nanoparticles

Calin David, Sara Cruz-Gonzalez, Sandrine Mongin, Encarnació Companys, Josep Monné, José Salvador, Carlos Rey-Castro, Jaume Puy, Josep Galceran

h. 10.20 – 10.40 **OC7** - Studies of Hyperbranched Polyethyleneimine as an Efficient Metal Ion Scavenger

Antonio Peñas Sanjuán, Manuel Melguizo, Paloma Arranz, Celeste García, Javier López Garzón, Manuel Pérez Mendoza

h. 10.40 – 11.00 **OC8** - Study on the interactions between proteins and inorganic pigments in paints

Ilaria Bonaduce, Emilia Bramanti, Celia Duce, Lisa Ghezzi, Alessio Spepi, Maria Rosaria Tinè

h. 11.00 – 11.15 *Coffee break*

Chairman: Manuel Valiente Malmagro

h. 11.15 – 11.45 **OC9** - Artificial Neural Networks in Chemical Kinetics

Filippo Amato, José Luis Gonzalez, Josef Havel

h. 11.45 – 12.05 **OC10** - Contribution of KAT Parameters for the Description of Solvent Effects on the CDTA and EGTA Complexes

Kavosh Majlesi, Saghar Rezaiejad

h. 12.05 – 12.25 **OC11** - Comparison of the Application of Debye-Huckel, Specific Ion Interaction and Parabolic models for the Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with D-(-)-Quinic Acid

Saghar Rezaiejad, Kavosh Majlesi

h. 12.25 – 12.45 **OC12** - The Inclusion of Activities in the Analysis of Equilibrium and Kinetic Studies. No More Inert Salts!

Nichola McCann, Peter King, Marcel Maeder

h. 12.45 – 13.05 **OC13** - Factor analysis program INDICES for prediction of the number of components in spectroscopic data

Milan Meloun

h. 13.05 – Lunch

Chairman: Juan Niclos-Gutierrez

h. 15.30 – 15.50 **OC14** - Assymetric tetranuclear mixed-ligand copper(II) complex with 4-aminopyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine ligand

Alicia Dominguez-Martin, Duane Choquesillo-Lazarte, Elena Bugella-Altamirano, Josefa María Gonzalez-Perez, Alfonso Castiñeiras, Juan Niclos-Gutierrez

h. 15.50 – 16.10 **OC15** - Copper(II) complexes of the oxime-and-amide ligands: The influence of peripheral hydroxyl group on coordination

Igor Vasyl Nikolayenko, Thomas John Theron

h. 16.10 – 16.30 **OC16** - The Hydroxyl Group: A Versatile Metal Ion-Binding Site

Helmut Sigel, Bert P. Operschall, Astrid Sigel

Chairman: Fernando Secco

h. 16.30 – 16.50 **OC17** - Study of the quenching of the excited state of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ by $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Pz}]^{3+}$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in the presence of α -cyclodextrins

Francisco Sanchez, Tania Lopes-Costa, Pilar Lopez-Cornejo, Francisco Montilla

h. 16.50 – 17.10 **OC18** - Comparison of kinetic and thermodynamic approaches for the determination of binding constants of excited species to different receptors

Eva Bernal, Francisco Sanchez, María Marchena

h. 17.10 – 17.30 **OC19** - Determination of reaction and reorganization free energies of electron transfer reactions under restricted geometry conditions

Manuel Lopez-Lopez, Francisco Sanchez, María Marchena

h. 17.30 – 17.45 *Coffee break*

Chairman: Maurizio Remelli

h. 17.45 – 18.15 **Pulidori Award** - Left-handed DNA: intercalation of the cyanine thiazole orange and structural changes. A kinetic and thermodynamic approach
Tarita Biver, Begoña García, José M. Leal, Fernando Secco and Elisa Turriani

h. 18.15- 19.45 **Poster Session**

Wednesday 15th

Chairman: Antonio Bianchi

h. 09.00 – 10.00 **PL3**- Designing Metalloenzymes: From Zinc Hydrolases to Copper Nitrite Reductase
Vincent Pecoraro, Melissa Zastrow, Matteo Tegoni, Anna F. A. Peacock, Fangting Yu, Jeanne Stuckey

Chairman: Paloma Arranz-Mascaros

h. 10.00 – 10.20 **OC20** - 15-Metallacrown-5 complexes: thermodynamic and kinetic selectivity for core metal ions
Matteo Tegoni, Choong Sun Lim, Maurizio Remelli, Francesco Dallavalle, Vincent L. Pecoraro

h. 10.20 – 10.40 **OC21** - Kinetics of formation of the 12-MC-4 metallacrown from (S)- α -Alanine hydroxamic acid and Copper(II) and its interaction with La(III)
Maria Rosa Beccia, Tarita Biver, Begoña García, José M. Leal, Maurizio Remelli, Fernando Secco, Matteo Tegoni, Marcella Venturini

h. 10.40 – 11.00 **OC22** - External and internal guest binding thermodynamics of a supramolecular host in water
Carmelo Sgarlata, Giuseppe Arena, Kenneth N. Raymond

h. 11.00 – 11.15 *Coffee break*

Chairman: Guido Crisponi

h. 11.15 – 11.45 **OC23** - DNA binding properties of ruthenium arene complex, genotoxicity and in vitro cytotoxicity
Natalia Busto, Begoña García, José M. Leal, Gustavo Espino Antonia Jimenez, Héctor Lozano, Tarita Biver, Célia Martins, Jorge F. Gaspar

- h. 11.45 – 12.05* **OC24** - Mn(II) Polyaza Scorpiand-like Complexes as Superoxide Dismutase Mimics
Enrique Garcia-España, Salvador Blasco, M. Paz Clares, Mario Inclan, Lucas Del Castillo, Begoña Verdejo, Conxa Soriano, Antonio Doménech, Julio Latorre
- h. 12.05 – 12.25* **OC25** - Molecular Movement of Two Novel Scorpiand-like Ligands and its Influence on DNA Intercalation
Enrique Garcia-España, Mario Inclan, M. Teresa Albelda, Juan Frias
- h. 12.25 – 12.45* **OC26** - Small molecules that are able to induce large conformation changes in polynucleotides: the DAPI/DNA system
Tarita Biver, Fernando Secco, Jacopo Spinelli, Marcella Venturini, María del Pilar Lopez Cornejo, Rafael Prado Gotor, Victoria Isabel Martin-Herrera, Natalia Busto Vazquez
- h. 12.45 – 13.05* **OC27** - CTAB Surfactant-Induced DNA Condensation-decondensation event at different binding ratio: A Multitechnique Study
Pilar Lopez-Cornejo, Consuelo Cerrillos, Elia Grueso
- h. 13.05 –* Lunch
- h. 15.30 – 19.30* Social program
- h. 21.00 –* Conference Dinner

Thursday 16th

- h. 09.00 – 10.00* **Round Table (Group meeting) and Presentation of Next Congress**
- Chairman:** Plinio Di Bernardo
- h. 10.00 – 10.20* **OC28** - Energetics of Heavy Metal-Thioether Interactions in Solution and Gas Phase
Elena Peralta, Andrea Melchior, Claudio Tavagnacco, Marilena Tolazzi, Manuel Valiente
- h. 10.20 – 10.40* **OC29** - Drug Discovery: towards the identification and characterization of new lead compounds as anticancer and antiprion agents

*Tiziana Pivetta, Francesco Isaia, Matteo Manca, Federica Pilla,
Alessandra Pani*

h. 10.40 – 11.00 **OC30** - A New Tripodal Hydroxypyrimidinone Sequestering Agent
*Anabela Capelo, Laurinda Arelas, Sérgio Marques, Lurdes Gano, Silvia
Chaves, M. Alexandra Esteves, M. Amélia Santos*

h. 11.00 – 11.20 **OC31** - The interaction of DNA with metal complexes: experimental and
computational studies
Giampaolo Barone, Angelo Spinello, Alessio Terenzi

h. 11.20 – 11.40 **OC32** - Manganese and Parkinson's Disease: new findings through a yeast
protein study
Massimiliano Peana, Maria Antonietta Zoroddu, Serenella Medici

h. 11.40 – 12.30 *Closing Ceremony*

LIST OF COMMUNICATIONS

PLENARY LECTURES

- PL1** Ocean Acidification on the Speciation of Metals
Frank J. Millero
- PL2** Voltammetry as a potentiometric sensor. Significance of a Virtual Potential in the study of metal-ligand equilibria
Ignacy Cukrowski
- PL3** Designing Metalloenzymes: From Zinc Hydrolases to Copper Nitrite Reductase
Vincent Pecoraro, Melissa Zastrow, Matteo Tegoni, Anna F. A. Peacock, Fangting Yu, Jeanne Stuckey

ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

- OC1** Chemically modified mesoporous silica for free iron sensing
Giovanni Emma, Maria Giovanna Guiso, Giancarla Alberti, Giacomo Dacarro, Angelo Taglietti, Raffaella Biesuz
- OC2** Simultaneous Chromium and Copper sorption using grape stalks in packed columns
David Pujol, Florencio De La Torre, Jordi Poch, Núria Fiol, Isabel Villaescusa
- OC3** SPION-Loaded Cellulose Sponge, a System for Arsenic Removal from Aqueous Solutions
D. Morillo Martín, G. Pérez González, M. Valiente Malmagro
- OC4** Towards a more comprehensive modelling capability for aqueous solution thermodynamics
Darren Rowland, Peter May
- OC5** The use of fundamental research to create superior product design
Simon Godfrey
- OC6** Experimental characterization and modelling of aqueous dispersions of ZnO nanoparticles
Calin David, Sara Cruz-Gonzalez, Sandrine Mongin, Encarnació Companys, Josep

Monné, José Salvador, Carlos Rey-Castro, Jaume Puy, Josep Galceran

- OC7** Studies of Hyperbranched Polyethyleneimine as an Efficient Metal Ion Scavenger
Antonio Peñas Sanjuán, Manuel Melguizo, Paloma Arranz, Celeste García, Javier López Garzón, Manuel Pérez Mendoza
- OC8** Study on the interactions between proteins and inorganic pigments in paints
Ilaria Bonaduce, Emilia Bramanti, Celia Duce, Lisa Ghezzi, Alessio Spepi, Maria Rosaria Tinè
- OC9** Artificial Neural Networks in Chemical Kinetics
Filippo Amato, José Luis Gonzalez, Josef Havel
- OC10** Contribution of KAT Parameters for the Description of Solvent Effects on the CDTA and EGTA Complexes
Kavosh Majlesi, Saghar Rezaiejad
- OC11** Comparison of the Application of Debye-Huckel, Specific Ion Interaction and Parabolic models for the Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with D-(-)-Quinic Acid
Saghar Rezaiejad, Kavosh Majlesi
- OC12** The Inclusion of Activities in the Analysis of Equilibrium and Kinetic Studies. No More Inert Salts!
Nichola McCann, Peter King, Marcel Maeder
- OC13** Factor analysis program INDICES for prediction of the number of components in spectroscopic data
Milan Meloun
- OC14** Assymmetric tetranuclear mixed-ligand copper(II) complex with 4-aminopyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine ligand
Alicia Dominguez-Martin, Duane Choquesillo-Lazarte, Elena Bugella-Altamirano, Josefa María Gonzalez-Perez, Alfonso Castiñeiras, Juan Niclos-Gutierrez
- OC15** Copper(II) complexes of the oxime-and-amide ligands: The influence of peripheral hydroxyl group on coordination
Igor Vasyly Nikolayenko, Thomas John Theron

- OC16** The Hydroxyl Group: A Versatile Metal Ion-Binding Site
Helmut Sigel, Bert P. Operschall, Astrid Sigel
- OC17** Study of the quenching of the excited state of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ by $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Pz}]^{3+}$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in the presence of α -cyclodextrins
Francisco Sanchez, Tania Lopes-Costa, Pilar Lopez-Cornejo, Francisco Montilla
- OC18** Comparison of kinetic and thermodynamic approaches for the determination of binding constants of excited species to different receptors
Eva Bernal, Francisco Sanchez, María Marchena
- OC19** Determination of reaction and reorganization free energies of electron transfer reactions under restricted geometry conditions
Manuel Lopez-Lopez, Francisco Sanchez, María Marchena
- OC20** 15-Metallacrown-5 complexes: thermodynamic and kinetic selectivity for core metal ions
Matteo Tegoni, Choong Sun Lim, Maurizio Remelli, Francesco Dallavalle, Vincent L. Pecoraro
- OC21** Kinetics of formation of the 12-MC-4 metallacrown from (S)- α -Alanine hydroxamic acid and Copper(II) and its interaction with La(III)
María Rosa Beccia, Tarita Biver, Begoña Garcia, José M. Leal, Maurizio Remelli, Fernando Secco, Matteo Tegoni, Marcella Venturini
- OC22** External and internal guest binding thermodynamics of a supramolecular host in water
Carmelo Sgarlata, Giuseppe Arena, Kenneth N. Raymond
- OC23** DNA binding properties of ruthenium arene complex, genotoxicity and in vitro cytotoxicity
Natalia Busto, Begoña Garcia, José M. Leal, Gustavo Espino Antonia Jimenez, Héctor Lozano, Tarita Biver, Célia Martins, Jorge F. Gaspar
- OC24** Mn(II) Polyaza Scorpian-like Complexes as Superoxide Dismutase Mimics
Enrique Garcia-España, Salvador Blasco, M. Paz Clares, Mario Inclan, Lucas Del Castillo, Begoña Verdejo, Conxa Soriano, Antonio Doménech, Julio Latorre

- OC25** Molecular Movement of Two Novel Scorpian-like Ligands and its Influence on DNA Intercalation
Enrique Garcia-España, Mario Inclan, M. Teresa Albelda, Juan Frias
- OC26** Small molecules that are able to induce large conformation changes in polynucleotides: the DAPI/DNA system
Tarita Biver, Fernando Secco, Jacopo Spinelli, Marcella Venturini, María del Pilar Lopez Cornejo, Rafael Prado Gotor, Victoria Isabel Martin-Herrera, Natalia Busto Vazquez
- OC27** CTAB Surfactant-Induced DNA Condensation-decondensation event at different binding ratio: A Multitechnique Study
Pilar Lopez-Cornejo, Consuelo Cerrillos, Elia Grueso
- OC28** Energetics of Heavy Metal-Thioether Interactions in Solution and Gas Phase
Elena Peralta, Andrea Melchior, Claudio Tavagnacco, Marilena Tolazzi, Manuel Valiente
- OC29** Drug Discovery: towards the identification and characterization of new lead compounds as anticancer and antiprion agents
Tiziana Pivetta, Francesco Isaia, Matteo Manca, Federica Pilla, Alessandra Pani
- OC30** A New Tripodal Hydroxypyrimidinone Sequestering Agent
Anabela Capelo, Laurinda Arelas, Sérgio Marques, Lurdes Gano, Silvia Chaves, M. Alexandra Esteves, M. Amélia Santos
- OC31** The interaction of DNA with metal complexes: experimental and computational studies
Giampaolo Barone, Angelo Spinello, Alessio Terenzi
- OC32** Manganese and Parkinson's Disease: new findings through a yeast protein study
Massimiliano Peana, Maria Antonietta Zoroddu, Serenella Medici

POSTERS

- P1** Novel Sol-Gel-Derived Material as chemosensor for Cu(II) and Ni(II): Dioxo-2,3,2 Functionalized Silica
Raffaella Biesuz, Angelo Taglietti, Yuri Diaz-Fernandez, Giancarla Alberti, Giovanni Emma, Maria Giovanna Guiso

- P2** Biosorption of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Cu^{2+} on rice husk, thermodynamic and kinetic studies
Maria Giovanna Guiso, Giancarla Alberti, Maria Pesavento, Raffaella Biesuz
- P3** Study of the Reactivity of Two Polyamine-Polyether/Nitrile Receptors towards Metal Ions
Javier Garcia-Martin, Paloma Arranz-Mascarós, M. Dolores Gutierrez-Valero, Rafael Lopez-Garzón, Francisco Javier López-Garzón, M^a Dolores López-De La Torre, Celeste García-Gallarín
- P4** Studies of Metal Ion Binding of a Pyrimidine/Desferrioxamine B Conjugate as Ion Receptor
Antonio Santiago-Medina, M^a Luz Godino-Salido, Manuel Melguizo-Guijarro, M^a Dolores López De La Torre, Manuel Pérez-Mendoza, María Domingo-García
- P5** Studies of Hyperbranched Polyethyleneimine as an Efficient Anion Scavenger
Antonio Peñas-Sanjuán, María D. Gutiérrez-Valero, Rafael López-Garzón, Antonio Santiago-Medina, M. Luz Godino-Salido, María Domingo-García
- P6** Anion Binding by a Tren-based Ligand Containing a Pyrimidine Functionality
Paloma Arranz, Carla Bazzicalupi, Antonio Bianchi, Claudia Giorgi, M. Luz Godino, M. Dolores Gutierrez, Rafael Lopez
- P7** Gold-Copper Extraction and Separation by Micellar Enhanced Ultrafiltration
Sabriye Aydinoglu, Tarita Biver, Fernando Secco, Marcella Venturini
- P8** Quantum-mechanical and spectral studies on the Thiazole Orange (TO) fluorophore: dimerisation and DNA intercalation
Alessandro Biancardi, Tarita Biver, Alberto Marini, Benedetta Mennucci, Fernando Secco
- P9** Studies on Platinum(II) and Palladium(II) binding to PADA in SDS micellar medium: a kinetic method for metal ions separation and recovery
Tarita Biver, Clara Paoletti, Fernando Secco, Marcella Venturini
- P10** Fluorescence study of the conformational transitions in Mg^{2+} dependent RNA-ligating 7S11 Deoxyribozyme
Elisa Turriani, Claudia Höbartner, Thomas M. Jovin

- P11** Characterization of the interaction between Poly(rA)·Poly(rU) and Thionine. A thermodynamic approach
Begoña García, José M. Leal, Natalia Busto, Héctor Lozano, Antonia Jimenez
- P12** Thermodynamic study of the interaction of 6-Anthracen-9-yl-[1,3,5] triazine-2,4-diamine with DNA
José M. Leal, Begoña García, Antonia Jimenez, Natalia Busto, Héctor Lozano, Gustavo Espino
- P13** A spectroscopic study of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with hydroxylated carboxylic ligands in aqueous solution
Silvia Berto, Pier Giuseppe Daniele, Enrico Prenesti, Enzo Laurenti
- P14** Analytical determination of total acidity in some Sardinian wines: evaluation of the contribute of different acids
Valeria Marina Nurchi, Guido Crisponi, Miriam Crespo-Alonso, Leonardo Toso, Delara Mansoori
- P15** A new hydroxypyrrone chelating agent for Fe^{III} and Al^{III}: a structural and equilibrium study
Miriam Crespo-Alonso, Guido Crisponi, Alicia Domínguez-Martín, Josefa M. González-Pérez, Juan Niclós-Gutiérrez, Leonardo Toso, Valeria M. Nurchi
- P16** A binuclear copper(II) compound derived from isocytosine and the trans-1,4-cyclohexanediaminotetraacetate(4-) chelating ligand
Hanan El Bakkali, Antonio Matilla-Hernandez, Alfonso Castiñeiras, Josefa María González-Pérez, Ricardo Navarrete-Casas, Juan Niclós-Gutiérrez
- P17** Evaluation of hydroxypyridinecarboxylic acids as new possible chelating agents for Iron(III) and Aluminium(III)
Annalisa Dean, Maria Grazia Ferlini, Denis Badocco, Paolo Pastore, Ignazio Castagliuolo, Alfonso Venzo, Robert A. Yokel, Valerio Di Marco
- P18** Complexation of thorium(IV) with sulfate at variable temperatures. A microcalorimetric study from 10 to 70 °C
Plinio Di Bernardo, Pier Luigi Zanonato, Francesco Endrizzi, Arturo Bismondo, Linfeng Rao

- P19** Experimental and theoretical study of the complexation of uranyl(VI) with acetate in dimethylsulfoxide
Plinio Di Bernardo, Pier Luigi Zanonato, Arturo Bismondo, Franco Benetollo, Linfeng Rao, Andrea Melchior, Marilena Tolazzi
- P20** Molecular dynamics simulation of cisplatin in water with an improved intermolecular interaction potential
Jose M. Martínez, Rafael R. Pappalardo, Enrique Sanchez-Marcos, Andrea Melchior
- P21** Thermodynamics Aspects and Analytical Applications of Hg(II)-TTCN Complexes
Elena Peralta, Marilena Tolazzi, Andrea Melchior, Manuel Valiente
- P22** Hazardous Heavy Metals Washing by Rainwater in Chronically Polluted Areas
Naiara Goienaga, Leire Kortazar, Raquel Glez-Turrion, Jose Antonio Carrero, Maitane Olivares, Alfredo Sarmiento, Luis Ángel Fernández, Juan Manuel Madariaga
- P23** Seawater H⁺ Affinity Spectrum: A Chemometric Exercise
Marian Olazabal Dueñas, Elisa Astigarraga Allende, Janire Saez Castaño, Luis Ángel Fernández Cuadrado
- P24** Influence of Soil Organic Matter in the Leaching Processes of Hazardous Heavy Metals
Naiara Goienaga, Leire Kortazar, Raquel Glez-Turrion, Olivia Gomez, Jose Antonio Carrero, Luis Ángel Fernández, Juan Manuel Madariaga
- P25** Raman Spectroscopy study of a salt weathering process in mortars of a Historical Palace House
Olivia Gomez-Laserna, Héctor Morillas, Nagore Prieto-Taboada, Iratxe Ibarondo, Irantzu Martinez-Arkarazo, Marian Olazabal, Juan Manuel Madariaga
- P26** Extraction method of soluble salts from bricks samples located in deteriorated building using focused ultrasound
Cristina Zarza, Nagore Prieto-Taboada, Silvia Fdez-Ortiz De Vallejuelo, Irantzu Martinez-Arkarazo, Alberto De Diego, Nestor Etxebarria, Marian Olazabal, Juan Manuel Madariaga
- P27** Buildings as repositories of hazardous compounds resulted from atmospheric pollution

Nagore Prieto-Taboada, Olivia Gomez-Laserna, Irantzu Martinez-Arkarazo, Marian Olazabal, Juan Manuel Madariaga

- P28** Cr(VI) removal from metal binary mixtures by using biosorbents
Marc Bartrolí, Jana Beyts, Núria Fiol, Florencio de la Torre, Jordi Poch, Isabel Villaescusa
- P29** Potentiometric and ESI MS investigation on Cd(II), Pb(II) and Zn(II) cations-L-cystine interaction in aqueous media
Emilia Furia, Fabio Mazzotti, Anna Napoli, Giovanni Sindona, Antonio Tagarelli
- P30** Speciation of Cadmium - D-penicilamine, mercaptosuccinic acid and glutathione systems in NaNO₃ ionic medium
Alba Giacalone, Antonio Gianguzza, Daniela Piazzese, Anna Napoli
- P31** Complexation of DNA with partially negatively charged gold nanoparticles in salt solution
Rafael Prado-Gotor, Elia Grueso
- P32** Gold nanoparticles-DNA Interactions: An atomic force microscopy and circular dichroism study
Rafael Prado-Gotor, Consuelo Cerrillos, Elia Grueso
- P33** Metal Interaction in Polytopic Receptors
Jorge González, Salvador Blasco, Mario Inclán, Javier Pitarch, Raquel Belda, Begoña Verdejo, Carmen E. Castillo, M. Angeles Mañez, José M. Llinares, Hermas R. Jiménez, Roberto Tejero, Manuel G. Basallote, Concepción Soriano, Enrique García-España
- P34** Complex-formation equilibria between Fe(III) and hydroxamic derivatives of bile acids
Sara Chiereghin, Dimitri Bacco, Marco Fogagnolo, Maurizio Remelli
- P35** Sequestration of Pd²⁺ by polyamino-polycarboxylic ligands
Antonio Gianguzza, Alberto Pettignano, Silvio Sammartano
- P36** Integrated Composite Kinetic Molecular Devices for Slow Anion Releasing
Giuseppe Alibrandi, Greta Bergamaschi, Riccardo Dollenz, Luigi Fabbrizzi, Maurizio Licchelli, Carmelo Lo Vecchio

- P37** Thermodynamic dissociation constants of some dronates using potentiometric titration data
Zuzana Ferencikova, Milan Meloun, Tomáš Pekarek
- P38** Recent progress in calculation methods to determine the dependence of stability constant values on ionic strength. Results for the nickel(II) / glycine system for $0.06 \leq I / \text{mol L}^{-1} \leq 5.3$
Rosalia Maria Cigala, Concetta De Stefano, Peter Gans, Demetrio Milea, Silvio Sammartano
- P39** Speciation of Sn^{2+} - hydroxocarboxylic ligand solutions: thermodynamic and spectroscopic study
Francesco Crea, Concetta De Stefano, Gabriele Lando, Demetrio Milea, Silvio Sammartano, Michelangelo Scopelliti
- P40** Even-Odd Alternation of some Thermodynamic Properties of α - ω -Alkanedicarboxylic Acids
Rosalia Maria Cigala, Francesco Crea, Stefano Materazzi
- P41** Study of the Thermodynamic Properties of DL-Tyrosine and DL-Tryptophan by Using Different Techniques. Determination of the Protonation Constants, Solubility and Activity Coefficients in $\text{NaCl}_{(\text{aq})}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}_{(\text{aq})}$ at Different Ionic Strengths and Temperatures
Clemente Bretti, Agatino Casale, Francesco Crea, Giuseppina Vianelli
- P42** Potentiometric and voltammetric study on the interaction of Sn^{2+} with phosphate and polycarboxylic ligands in aqueous solution
Daniela Cucinotta, Ottavia Giuffrè, Gabriele Lando, Giuseppe Manfredi
- P43** Binding ability of reduced glutathione towards $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Sn}^+$, at different temperatures and ionic strengths
Paola Cardiano, Alessandro De Robertis, Gabriella Falcone, Claudia Foti
- P44** Intramolecular Weak Interactions Determining the Thermodynamic Stereoselectivity of Copper(II) Complexes with Carnosine-trehalose Conjugates
Giuseppa Ida Grasso, Giuseppe Arena, Francesco Bellia, Giuseppe Maccarrone, Michele Parrinello, Adriana Pietropaolo, Graziella Vecchio, Enrico Rizzarelli

PLENARY LECTURES

Ocean Acidification on the Speciation of Metals

Frank J. MILLERO

Rosenstiel School of Marine and Atmospheric Science, University of Miami, Miami, FL 33149
millero@rsmas.miami.edu

The burning of fossil fuels has increased the pCO₂ in the atmosphere from 280 ppmv to 385 ppmv over the last 200 years. This increase is larger than has occurred over the past 800 ky. Equilibration of this CO₂ with surface waters will decrease the pH (called Ocean Acidification) from current values of 8.1 to values as low as 7.4 over the next 200 years. The decrease in the pH of ocean waters can affect chemical and biological processes that occur in the oceans. Many recent studies have shown that ocean acidification can affect the production and dissolution of CaCO₃(s) microorganisms in surface waters. Ocean acidification can also affect ionic equilibria such as acid-base and the formation of metal complexes. Many oxidation-reduction reactions of metals are also affected by changes in the pH.

In this paper, I will examine how ocean acidification of seawater can affect the state of metal ions. The decrease in pH can cause a decrease in the concentration of inorganic (OH⁻, CO₃²⁺ ions) and organic ligands that complex many metals in natural waters. This will change the speciation of many metals in seawater. Uncomplexed Cu²⁺ is toxic to bacteria and phytoplankton while uncomplexed Fe²⁺ is more available for the growth of phytoplankton. Since organic ligands in natural waters can form strong complexes with metals, more studies are needed to examine how pH affects the metal-organic ligands in natural waters.

Voltammetry as a potentiometric sensor. Significance of a Virtual Potential in the study of metal-ligand equilibria

Ignacy CUKROWSKI

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences, University of Pretoria, Pretoria 0002, South Africa
ignacy.cukrowski@up.ac.za

Non-equilibrium, dynamic and kinetically involved voltammetric data can be converted into equilibrium and thermodynamic type of data typical for a classical potentiometric sensor – see [1] and references therein. The virtual potential (VP)

$$E(C) + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{I(C)}{I(M)} \right) = E(\text{virt})$$

which combines the reversible reduction potential $E(C)$ of a metal containing species when complexes with a ligand L are formed and a normalised intensity of a voltammetric signal, $I(C)/(M)$, has been proved to be equivalent to a real Gaussian potential. VP was successfully applied in the study of a number of multicomponent and kinetically involved metal-ligand (M-L) systems and formation constants obtained using VPs did not differ statistically from those generated from real Gaussian potentials obtained on the same M-L systems from glass electrode potentiometry (GEP).

The relationships E vs. pH or E vs. pL, where E represents the experimentally observed half-wave or peak potential ($E_{1/2}$ or E_p) were used to predict the formation of metal complexes investigated by polarography for decades. It has been shown recently that only in a very rare case of a fully reversible electrochemical signal recorded on a fully labile M-L system these relationships hold. However, when VP is used instead of experimentally observed potential then one can correctly model the formation of any $M_pL_qH_r$ complex which might be a part of a labile, inert or kinetically mixed system even when polynuclear species are formed, or some or all metal complexes cannot be reduced (they are polarographically inactive).

A glass electrode (GE) is still regarded as the best potentiometric sensor with the widest linearity range. It has been shown, however, that a virtual potentiometric sensor generates unlimited linear response towards a free metal ion concentration outperforming all known ion selective electrodes, including GE. Also, one can use dedicated (to study M-L equilibria by GEP) potentiometric software to refine formation constants using either only VP or VP in combination with real potentiometric data. It means that it is possible to combine GEP, ISE and voltammetric data from several experiments performed on the same M-L system and refine simultaneously formation constants using a single software package.

Several M-L systems, including bisphosphonates used in the bone cancer therapies, will be discussed in details showing all the above unique properties of VP.

References:

- [1] Cukrowski, I.; Marques, H.M.; Mkwizu, T.S.; Magampa, P.P.; Serge C., *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2007**, *590*, 203-216.

Designing Metalloenzymes: From Zinc Hydrolases to Copper Nitrite Reductase

Vincent PECORARO, ^{a)} **Melissa ZASTROW,** ^{b)} **Matteo TEGONI,** ^{c)}
Anna F.A. PEACOCK, ^{d)} **Fangting YU,** ^{b)} **Jeanne STUCKEY** ^{e)}

^{a)} *Department of Chemistry, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor Michigan, USA*

^{b)} *Department of Chemistry, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor Michigan, USA*

^{c)} *Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Parma, Parma, Italy*

^{d)} *Department of Chemistry, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, Great Britain*

^{e)} *Department of Biological Chemistry and the Life Sciences Institute, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor Michigan, USA*

vlpec@umich.edu

De novo protein design provides an attractive approach for modeling the active sites of metalloproteins. Using this technique one may not only provide a synthetic construct which precisely mimics the first coordination sphere of a known metalloenzyme site, one may also develop a catalytic center that is embedded within a hydrophobic protein pocket and which has its coordination chemistry influenced by second coordination sphere ligands. In this presentation, we will discuss how to prepare a mixed Hg(II),Zn(II) protein that is capable of efficient, multiturnover hydrolysis of nitrophenylacetate in aqueous solution over the pH range 7.5 to 9.5. Furthermore, this new catalyst carries out CO₂ hydration better than any previously characterized biomimetic system. The Zn(II) catalytic center is structurally homologous with those found in carbonic anhydrases and matrix metalloproteinases [Figure 1]. We have now been able to prepare structural models for Type 2 copper environments such as found in nitrite reductase. We will show how Cu(I) binds to our peptides in a CuN₃O coordination geometry and is capable of complexing CO into the hydrophobic protein core. Most important, this designed copper protein is redox active and can convert NO₂⁻ into NO and H₂O, thus serving as a reactivity mimic for nitrite reductase activity.

Figure 1. Comparison of the x-ray structures of the Zn center in Hg^{II},Zn^{II}(CSL9CL23H)₃ [blue] and carbonic anhydrase [green].

ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

Chemically modified mesoporous silica for free iron sensing

Giovanni EMMA, Maria Giovanna GUIISO, Giancarla ALBERTI,
Giacomo Dacarro, Angelo Taglietti, Raffaella BIESUZ

Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Pavia, via Taramelli 12-27100 Pavia (ITALY)
rbiesuz@unipv.it

We are studying different solid sorbents with a strong selectivity towards hard metals, such as Fe(III), to be used in biological fluids for free metal sensing. We selected deferoxamine, DFO as a candidate ligand suitable to be anchored on a solid mainframe for the presence of a free amino group not involved in metal complexation. At the same time, DFO is a hydroxamate siderophore forming in solution with Fe(III) a 1:1 coloured complex (maximum $\lambda = 425$ nm) with the six oxygen atoms of the hydroxamates groups.

Recently we have considered mesoporous silica (MS) as solid matrix for the well known properties of this phase, widely employed for these purposes. Two types of MS, with different pore sizes, have been considered: MCM-41 and MSU-H. In addition to this, a novel synthesis for bounding DFO is proposed. The ligand is covalently bounded to the silane precursor before the anchorage to the solid phase (one-step synthesis), differently from the reported synthesis where the silica precursor and DFO were added step by step to silica [1].

Chemical-physics characterizations were performed to get information on the effectiveness of the functionalization process and to determine thermodynamics and kinetic parameters.

The TGA analysis confirmed the coverage of silica surface, while the presence on the solid of amidic group, characteristic of DFO, was verified through IR spectra.

Figure 1- Kinetic profiles for Fe(III) uptake from solution KNO_3 0.1M, $\text{pH}=2.5$ $c_{\text{Fe}}= 1.8 \cdot 10^{-5}\text{M}$ on different modified silica: blu (MSU-H), red (MCM-41), green (MCM-41 the one-step synthesis)

Figure 2 - Desorption Fe(III) profile at $\text{pH}=7$ as function of EDTA concentration. Solid phase: MSU-H (31 mg), previously saturated with the metal, water phase: KNO_3 0.1M and PIPES 10^{-2} M ($V= 55.5$ mL)

By contacting the sorbents with Fe(III) solutions, the complex formation is clearly seen by the typical dark-orange colour and the solid phase molecular spectroscopy proves the absorbance band of the complex almost overlapping that obtained in solution with the soluble ligand and the same metal. On the different materials SEM-EDS analysis were performed demonstrating that Fe(III) distributes on the surface of the solid phase, not entering into the pores.

Kinetic studies have been carried out considering the two types of modified mesoporous silica, and clearly show a faster iron(III) uptake for the MCM-41 prepared by the novel one-step synthesis. In this case, the metal sorption is quantitative within one hour, in comparison with the two hours needed by the other materials (fig.1).

For all the modified silica, sorption isotherms follow the Langmuir model and also in this case the novel synthesis with MCM-41 provides a major iron(III) uptake.

The quantification of the exchange properties is performed according to a well established procedure, previously adopted for synthetic resins [2]. In particular in this case a competitive method employing EDTA, at pH 7, was considered. An example of the sorption profile as function of EDTA concentration, is given in figure 2.

Knowing the partition coefficient we have demonstrated that it is possible to achieve information about the species distribution in a solution in contact with the solid phase [3].

In fluids where Fe(III) is free or weakly bounded, it is expected that the metal will be quantitatively sorbed, conversely, the metal will be only partially sorbed, if the metal ion in solution is bounded to strong ligands. For example, in biological fluids, the strong ligands could be proteins or other molecules, such as drugs used to treat acute iron poisoning in chelating therapy. From the degree of the competition, knowing the total metal concentration, the free metal can be evaluated.

References

- [1] Wanunu, M.; Livne, S.; Vaskevich, A.; Rubinstein, I. Assembly of coordination nanostructures via ligand derivatization of oxide surfaces. *Langmuir* **2006**, 22 (5), 2130-2135.
- [2] Biesuz, R.; Alberti, G.; Pesavento, M. Sorption of lead(II) on two chelating resins: From the exchange coefficient to the intrinsic complexation constant. *Journal of Solution Chemistry* **2008**, 37 (4), 527-541.
- [3] Alberti, G.; Pesavento, M.; Biesuz, R. A chelating resin as a probe for the copper(II) distribution in grape wines. *Reactive & Functional Polymers* **2007**, 67 (10), 1083-1093.

Simultaneous Chromium and Copper sorption using grape stalks in packed columns

David PUJOL,^{a)} **Florencio DE LA TORRE**,^{a)} **Jordi POCH**,^{b)} **Núria FIOL**,^{a)}
Isabel VILLAESCUSA^{a)}

^{a)} *Universitat de Girona, Department of Chemical Engineering, Escola Politècnica Superior, Campus de Montilivi, E-17071 Girona (Spain), +34 972418416,*

^{b)} *Universitat de Girona, Applied Mathematics Department, Campus de Montilivi, E-17071 Girona (Spain), +34 972 418413*
davidpujol@udg.edu

It is well known that hexavalent chromium is a highly toxic metal and dangerous for the environment. This metal is commonly used in textile, electroplating, tanning and metal finishing industries. Conventional methods for the removal of heavy metals from aqueous effluents are in some cases highly expensive. In order to decrease the cost of these treatments, sorption processes by using low cost sorbents are being studied.

In our laboratories, the efficiency of grape stalks as low cost sorbent for the removal of different metals ions such as chromium, copper or nickel in single solution have been demonstrated [1, 2]. Nevertheless, industrial wastewaters usually contain more than one metal. Therefore, the simultaneous removal of Cr(VI) and Cu(II), which are found frequently together in electroplating industry wastewaters has been investigated in batch mode. pH 3 was found to be the optimum for the simultaneous removal of chromium and copper, and the combined effect of both metals on the sorption of grape stalks was found to be synergistic for a large concentration range [3]. Nevertheless from a practical operation of full-scale treatment, continuous processes are preferred.

In this work the simultaneous sorption of Cr(VI) and Cu(II) using grape stalks packed columns was studied and the best operation conditions have been determined. The experiments were carried out in 30x300mm glass columns packed with grape stalks with a particle size 1-1.5mm. The influence of various parameters like flow rate, initial metal concentration and bed depth has been studied. In the outlet column solution, total Cr, Cr(VI) and Cu(II) concentration has been determined to obtain the breakthrough curves.

The obtained results have shown that a decrease in the flow rate provokes an increase of sorption capacity of grape stalks for both metals, and increases the volume that can be processed. The best results were obtained when the flow rate was 1.5 mL/min, thus subsequent experiments were performed using this flow rate. From the experimental data obtained at different conditions, the multi-component sorption in packed bed were modeled to determine the kinetic constants and to predict the breakthrough curves of each component.

References:

- [1] Fiol, N.; Villaescusa, I.; Martínez, M.; Miralles, N.; Poch, J.; Serarols, J., Biosorption of Cr(VI) using low cost sorbents. *Environmental Chemistry Letters* **2003**, 1, 135-139.
- [2] Villaescusa, I.; Fiol, N.; Martínez, M.; Miralles, N.; Poch, J.; Serarols, J., Removal of copper and nickel ions from aqueous solutions by grape stalks wastes. *Water Research* **2004**, 38, 992-1002.

- [3] Pujol, D.; Fiol, N.; Poch, J.; Villaescusa, I., Sorptive removal of Cr(VI) and Cu(II) from binary mixtures by grape stalks. *11th European Meeting on Environmental Chemistry (EMEC11) 2011*.

Acknowledgements: This work has been financially supported by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, Spain, Project CTM2008-06776-C02-01. A fellowship was attributed to David Pujol Oriola by Universitat de Girona (BR 10/09).

SPION-Loaded Cellulose Sponge, a System for Arsenic Removal from Aqueous Solutions

**Diego MORILLO MARTÍN, Gustavo PÉREZ GONZÁLEZ,
Manuel VALIENTE MALMAGRO**

*Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Departament de Química, Química Analítica, Centre
GTS 08193 Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain
manuel.valiente@uab.es*

Arsenic removal from contaminated waters is an important goal to accomplish environmental regulations. Decontamination process is made in several ways being adsorption process most efficient. In this concern, nanoparticles have been proposed as an appropriate material to increase the arsenic adsorption from contaminated waters. However, aggregation of nanoparticles has been detected as a main problem hindering the promising adsorption. To overcome this situation, a system to diminish aggregation based on the nanoparticles dispersion on an adequate supporting material is proposed. To this purpose, superparamagnetic nanoparticles have been fixed on a sponge of cellulose which helps to decrease the aggregation state and increase the adsorption of pollutants from aqueous effluents. This system has been applied to the adsorption of arsenate and arsenite, from aqueous solutions. The experimental studies report a lower aggregation of supported superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles over sponge than observed in the non supported nanoparticles. Dispersion of the superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles over sponge increases the adsorption capacity without modifying their properties. At this point, an increased adsorption capacity is observed for this sponge system than for superparamagnetic nanoparticles in suspension, maintaining their overall nanoproperties and demonstrating that sponge system is a suitable solution to overcome aggregation problem of adsorbent nanoparticles.

Acknowledgements: The present work has been developed under the financial support of the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, MICINN (Project CTQ2009-07432). Diego Morillo acknowledges MICINN for the FPI scholarship supporting his doctoral studies.

Towards a more comprehensive modelling capability for aqueous solution thermodynamics

Darren ROWLAND, Peter MAY

School of Chemical and Mathematical Sciences, Murdoch University, Australia

D.Rowland@murdoch.edu.au

The field of electrolyte solution thermodynamics has a long history. Despite decades of research however, no fundamental framework for describing the properties of electrolyte solutions has emerged. Numerous theoretical formulations have been developed which attempt to correlate the physicochemical properties of pure and mixed electrolytes in aqueous solution, but none of these are capable of accurately *predicting* the thermodynamics of multicomponent electrolyte mixed solutions, such as seawater.

The reasons for this lack of consensus are numerous. It is only in very dilute solutions that fundamental electrolyte solution theory is well established. In general, available thermodynamic models are based largely on empirical functions – with correspondingly poor predictive capability. Also, experimental information on mixed electrolyte systems is worryingly sparse and the consequences of error propagation from uncertainties in the raw experimental data and from poorly designed numerical analyses are widely underestimated.

We aim to address this problem by assembling as much relevant information on physicochemical properties as possible into a large, general database and to provide automatic computational methods to analyse the diverse data for thermodynamic consistency. Then, by focussing on the linear mixing rules of Zdanovskii and Young, robust and accurate predictions of the properties of mixed electrolyte solutions can be achieved.

A good model for the water activity of binary solutions is required by Zdanovskii's rule to predict the water activity of mixtures. Likewise, the use of Young's rule needs the density (or heat capacity) of binary solutions. Satisfactory fits to these properties of binary solutions can be obtained using the Pitzer equations. The empirical nature of the Pitzer model is much less problematic for binary solutions than for mixtures. This is because the combinatorial escalation in the number of required parameters is avoided.

This work describes an automatic optimisation procedure for fitting physicochemical data and the subsequent calculation of mixture properties using Zdanovskii's rule and Young's rule. We have found that many systems are very well described using this approach. However, difficulties have been encountered when representing certain properties, in particular trace activity coefficients. Possible ways of dealing with this problem are being investigated.

The use of fundamental research to create superior product design

Simon GODFREY

*Procter & Gamble Technical Centres Ltd, London Innovation Centre, Whitehall Lane,
Egham, Surrey, TW20 9NW, UK*
godfrey.s@pg.com

Hair colorants require chemistry to delight consumers, with consumers even needed to mix together two formulations to activate the product. While applied to the hair, melanin hairs natural pigmentation, is bleached by hydrogen peroxide, while new synthetic chromophores are formed within the hair. These combine to provide consumers with their new hair color. However, the chemical environment may lead to some undesired chemistry, due to the combination of hydrogen peroxide and redox metals. These can combine to form hydroxyl radicals via Fenton chemistry which can then lead to unwanted changes to the hair structure. Fundamental colorant chemistry understanding via speciation modelling shows the significant role colorant formulation bases provide in keeping key re-dox metals soluble, even at high pH. Understanding this chemistry not only explains the challenges observed during coloring, but also suggests solutions, the use of “protective” multi-dentate ligands to out compete colorant bases to bind key re-dox metals. Modelling can be used to understanding and solve this challenge leading to products with superior consumer performance. Examples are provided of how these insights have been translated into commercial products which provide superior hair health.

Experimental characterization and modelling of aqueous dispersions of ZnO nanoparticles

**Calin DAVID, Sara CRUZ-GONZALEZ, Sandrine MONGIN,
Encarnació COMPANYS, Josep MONNÉ, José SALVADOR,
Carlos REY-CASTRO, Jaume PUY, Josep GALCERAN**

Department of Chemistry, University of Lleida, Av. Rovira Roure 191, 25198 Lleida, Spain
carlos.rey@quimica.udl.es

The growing concern on the ecotoxicological issues related to engineered nanoparticles (NPs) requires the development and application of new analytical techniques and theoretical models in order to gain insight into their behaviour in aqueous environments. This behaviour depends on the specific physicochemical characteristics of the NPs at the pH, salinity and organic matter content of natural waters. In particular, ZnO NPs display several distinctive features under these conditions: a) a relatively high solubility; b) a strong tendency to aggregate; and c) a large surface area available for the adsorption of dissolved organic matter (DOM). The significant release of free Zn²⁺ ions may play a role in the toxic effects of ZnO nanoparticles [1]. In the literature, the measurement of soluble Zn(II) species has usually relied on the separation of the NPs by ultrafiltration or centrifugation, followed by elemental analysis of the liquid phase [2], which might be affected by artefacts due to very fine particles. The formation of aggregates influences both the kinetics of solubilization and the transport processes of the NPs (diffusion, settling, etc.). Finally, the association of NPs with DOM (e.g., humic acids) alters the surface charge, which, in turn, affects the stability of NPs in natural waters. At the same time, the complexing capacity of DOM may have an influence on the solubility of these NPs.

In this work, the new techniques AGNES (*Absence of Gradients and Nernstian Equilibrium Stripping*) [3,4] and DGT (*Diffusive Gradients in Thin Films*) [5] were used to obtain in-situ information on the equilibrium and dynamic Zn speciation in aqueous dispersions of ZnO NPs. AGNES provides an unambiguous measurement of the free Zn²⁺ concentration, whereas DGT yields an estimation of the labile fraction of dissolved metal. The advantages of DGT are its simplicity and applicability to a broad range of metal and inorganic ions, also in the field. The results obtained in this work show that both techniques can be very useful in the monitoring of soluble metal species in NP toxicity tests.

The equilibrium free Zn²⁺ concentrations measured by AGNES in buffered electrolyte solutions within a pH range of 7-9 show no significant dependence with the particle size and are consistent with values measured in solutions saturated with bulk ZnO at the same conditions. These data agree very well with standard speciation calculations using Visual MINTEQ and thermodynamic data reported in the literature [6]. At the same time, our preliminary results with DGT indicate that the amount of Zn measured as labile in the ZnO-NP dispersions is larger than the accumulation computed from the labile species given by MINTEQ. The possible contribution of very fine particles on the DGT results is addressed.

Additionally, the temporal resolution of AGNES allowed us to measure the variation of the free Zn^{2+} concentration with time following changes in the conditions of the aqueous dispersion (NP concentration, pH, etc.). The resulting kinetic data were compared with a reaction-diffusion model.

Finally, the aggregation and settling dynamics of the NPs, under the experimental conditions used in AGNES and DGT experiments, were studied through UV-absorption and Dynamic Light Scattering. The results show that the NPs tend to aggregate and settle down very quickly, although this behaviour is significantly affected by the presence of low concentrations of DOM. Relatively small aggregates and very stable dispersions were observed above 1.5 mg/L of humic acid. Electrophoretic mobility measurements suggest that organic matter readily adsorbs on ZnO leading to negatively charged particles, probably stabilized by electrostatic repulsion.

Acknowledgements: The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement n° 229244 (*ENNSATOX*). The authors also acknowledge further support of this research from the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (CTQ2009-07831 and CTQ2009-14612), and from the Comissionat d'Universitats i Recerca de la Generalitat de Catalunya (2009SGR00465). S. Cruz-Gonzalez and S. Mongin gratefully acknowledge their FPI fellowships from Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación of Spain and the European Social Fund.

References:

- [1] Franklin, N. M.; Rogers, N. J.; Apte, S. C.; Batley, G. E.; Gadd, G. E.; Casey, P. S., Comparative toxicity of nanoparticulate ZnO, bulk ZnO, and $ZnCl_2$ to a freshwater microalga (*Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata*): The importance of particle solubility. *Environmental Science & Technology* **2007**, 41, 8484-8490.
- [2] Bai, W.; Zhang, Z. Y.; Tian, W. J.; He, X.; Ma, Y. H.; Zhao, Y. L.; Chai, Z. F., Toxicity of zinc oxide nanoparticles to zebrafish embryo: a physicochemical study of toxicity mechanism. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research* **2010**, 12, 1645-1654.
- [3] Galceran, J.; Companys, E.; Puy, J.; Cecilia, J.; Garcés, J.L., AGNES: a new electroanalytical technique for measuring free metal ion concentration. *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **2004**, 566, 95-109.
- [4] Companys, E.; Puy, J.; Galceran, J., Humic acid complexation to Zn and Cd determined with the new electroanalytical technique AGNES. *Environ. Chem.* **2007**, 4, 347-354..
- [5] Mongin, S.; Uribe, R.; Puy, J.; Cecilia, J.; Galceran, J.; Zhang, H.; Davison, W., Key role of the resin layer thickness in the lability of complexes measured by DGT. Part I. Submitted to *Environmental Science & Technology* **2011**.
- [6] Zhang, Y.; Muhammed, M., Critical evaluation of thermodynamics of complex formation of metal ions in aqueous solutions VI. Hydrolysis and hydroxo-complexes of Zn^{2+} at 298.15 K. *Hydrometallurgy* **2001**, 60, 215-236.

Studies of Hyperbranched Polyethyleneimine as an Efficient Metal Ion Scavenger

Antonio PEÑAS SANJUÁN, ^{a)} **Manuel MELGUIZO,** ^{a)} **Paloma ARRANZ,** ^{a)} **Celeste GARCÍA,** ^{a)} **Javier LÓPEZ GARZÓN,** ^{b)} **Manuel PÉREZ MENDOZA** ^{b)}

^{a)} *Departamento de Química Inorgánica y Orgánica, Universidad de Jaén. Campus Las Lagunillas, 23071 Jaén (Spain).*

^{b)} *Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Universidad de Granada. Facultad de Ciencias, 18071 Granada (Spain).*

apenas@ujaen.es

The reactivity of a hyperbranched polyethyleneimine (PEI, $M_n = 600$) towards a series of divalent metal ions with environmental and technical interest ($M(II) = Mn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Pd(II)$) have been studied. From the point of view of their complexing abilities, the PEI macromolecules behave as arrangements of small complexing triamine units, L, that form complexes of stoichiometries of the types LM and L_2M [1]. The values of $\log K_{st}$ measured for them (Table 1) are slightly higher than those corresponding to analogous metal complexes with non-polymeric triamine ligands. Such an increase of the $\log K_{st}$ values is attributed to a polymer network contribution to the global stability [2].

Figure 1. Molecular structure of PEI

A hybrid material, AC-PEI, was obtained by grafting PEI onto the graphitic layers of an activated carbon (AC). The hybrid material showed very good adsorption capacity to the above mentioned ions from aqueous solutions. The values of the maximum adsorption capacity, X_m , measured for the set of studied metal ions suggest that the complexation models found for the different PEI-M systems operate in the adsorption process. This proves that functionalization of the AC with PEI provides selective complexing chemical functions to the carbon framework [3].

Table 1. Correlation between $\log K_{st}$ (289 K, 0.1 M KCl) and X_m of metal ions adsorbed under AC-PEI

Ion	pH of adsorption	Specie	Log K	X_m (mmol ion/g adsorbent)
Cd^{2+}	6.5	$[CdL]^{2+}$	8.90 (1)	0.305
Mn^{2+}	8.5	$[MnL]^{2+}$	4.84 (3)	0.285
Hg^{2+}	5.0	$[HgHL]^{3+}$	13.37 (4)	0.870
Pd^{2+}	5.0	$[PdL]^{2+}$	31.76 (5)	1.720

References:

- [1] Neil, J.; Wagener, J., *Talanta*, **1995**, 42, 219
- [2] Imam, M. R.; Peterca, M.; Edlind, U.; Balagurusamy, V. S.; Percec, V., *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.*, **2009**, 47, 4165.
- [3] García-Martín, J.; López-Garzón, R.; Godino-Salido, M. L.; Gutiérrez-Valero, M. D.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; Cuesta-Martos, R.; Carrasco-Marín, F., *Langmuir*, **2005**, 21, 6908

Study on the interactions between proteins and inorganic pigments in paints

Ilaria BONADUCE^{a)}, Emilia BRAMANTI^{b)}, Celia DUCE^{a)}, Lisa GHEZZI^{a)}, Alessio SPEPI^{a)}, Maria Rosaria TINE^{a)}

*^{a)} Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale, Università di Pisa, Via Risorgimento 35,
Pisa 56126, Italy,*

*^{b)} Istituto di Chimica dei Composti OrganoMetallici del CNR, via G. Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa,
Italy*

lisa@ns.dcci.unipi.it

Paints layers are generally made up of one or more pigments, which are a fine powder of inorganic coloured minerals, and a fluid binder, which enables the pigment to be dispersed, and to adhere to the support. This work aims at studying the interactions between proteinaceous binder and inorganic species in paint layers and how these evolve with time. In addition the degradation of proteinaceous materials was also investigated. Historically, binding media were natural products from plants or animals, including protein-based materials such as egg, casein or animal glue, vegetable gums, drying oils, and natural waxes. These could be used alone or in mixtures, determining the different painting techniques. Proteins have commonly been used as binders, in the “tempera” painting technique. The organic paints constituents, and thus proteins as well, undergo to physico-chemical modifications which are referred to as “ageing”, leading to the formation of new functional groups and intermolecular and intramolecular bonds. Moreover in every paint layer slow chemical reactions can take place between the organic and inorganic material present. In a tempera paint, inorganic pigments can interact with proteins through the formation of strong metal complexes [1]. This phenomenon is far from being completely understood, and this paper aims at filling this gap.

The study of the interactions between proteinaceous binder and inorganic species and of the degradation of proteinaceous materials, was performed using two pure single proteins (ovalbumin and casein) as model binders, and azurite ($\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$), calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), red ochre (Fe_2O_3), minium (Pb_3O_4) and cinnabar (HgS) as pigments. The research was carried out on a set of paint replicas on glass slides freshly prepared by us, which were analysed fresh and after artificial light ageing.

Multiple physical-chemical techniques were used to determine the nature, occurrence and modification of the interactions between proteins and inorganic compounds in the paint replicas, including Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC). These techniques have been widely used in the field of cultural heritage [2, 3] showing that these techniques are of primary importance for the comprehension of structural changes of binders during aging in the presence or not of other organic and inorganic materials. In particular thermoanalytical techniques and SEC allowed us to highlight the occurrence of interactions between proteins and pigments, and permitted to partially investigate into their nature, and evolution with ageing. FTIR proved to be extremely useful for understanding the

nature of these interactions, and for chemically characterise the modifications undergone by the proteinaceous binders as an effect of light ageing.

References:

- [1] De la Cruz-Canizares, A.; Domenech-Carbo, M.T.; Gimeno-Adelantado, J.V.; Mateo-Castro, R.; Bosch-Reig, F., Suppression of pigment interference in the gas chromatographic analysis of proteinaceous binding media in paintings with EDTA. *Journal of Chromatography A* **2004**,1025, 277-285
- [2] Bonaduce, I.; Carlyle, L.; Colombini, M.P.; Duce, C.; Ferrari, C.; Ribechini, E.; Selleri, P.; Tiné, M.R., A multi-analytical approach to studying binding media in oil paintings. Characterisation of differently pre-treated linseed oil by DE-MS, TG, and GC/MS. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry* **2011**, accepted for publication on 08-04-2011, Manuscript Number: JTAC-D-11-00263R1.
- [3] Colombini, M.P.; Modugno, F., Characterisation of proteinaceous binders in artistic paintings by chromatographic techniques. *Journal of Separation of Science* **2004**, 27(3), 147-160.

Artificial Neural Networks in Chemical Kinetics

Filippo AMATO, ^{a)} **José Luis GONZÁLEZ,** ^{b)} **Josef HAVEL** ^{a,c,d)}

^{a)} *Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kampus Bohunice, Kamenice 5/A14, Brno, Czech Republic.*

^{b)} *Department of Physical Chemistry, University of Salamanca, Salamanca, Spain.
jlgh93@usal.es*

^{c)} *Department of Physical Electronics, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kotlářská 2, 611 37 Brno, Czech Republic. havel@chemi.muni.cz*

^{d)} *R&D center for low-cost plasma and nanotechnology surface modifications, Masaryk University, Kotlářská 2, 611 37 Brno, Czech Republic
389626@mail.muni.cz*

Chemical research is nowadays more and more devoted toward the comprehension of chemical systems of high complexity, such as environmental or industrial ones. The usual experimental investigation of such systems requires a deep knowledge about their microscopic structure; especially in order to estimate parameters such as stability or kinetic rate constants. The information obtained from such studies is extremely useful especially in industrial applications to establish optimal operation conditions. Even with the aid of sophisticated computer programs, based, for example, on robust general regression algorithms [1], the study of complex chemical systems in terms of detailed mechanism and kinetics is still a hard work because to estimate values of parameters it is necessary to know and solve the system of ordinary differential equations (ODE) governing the system [2].

The main task of chemical kinetics is the estimation of rate constants, mechanisms and the factors affecting them. This information is useful to predict optimal reaction conditions for example to reach high yield. Moreover, such knowledge is useful for the development of more effective catalysts or new kinetic method of analysis.

Detailed description of the system, based on knowledge of reaction mechanism and physico-chemical constants, is usually called “hard” modeling. This approach might suffer of several difficulties, due to the intrinsic complexity of the system (*i.e.* if exact solution of ODE does not exist) and also to other phenomena like possible undistinguishability or unidentifiability of kinetic models [3].

A new possibility is offered by so called “soft” modeling, which is able to model hidden or very complex relationships between a set of “input” and a set of “output” data with a limited or even no knowledge about the microscopic behavior of the chemical system.

The aim of this work is to study potential of neural networks (ANN) “soft” modeling in kinetics.

The use of ANN will be studied for:

1. estimation of rate constants knowing the kinetic model;

2. estimation of analyte concentration determined by kinetic methods without any knowledge about the mechanism of the process;
3. application to some relevant industrial cases.

Several different cases were studied as, for example, consecutive or cyclic reaction paths. For each case, both the network architecture and experimental design were evaluated and optimized; moreover the quality of the model was checked with verification data sets.

The power of ANN in modeling complex systems was demonstrated and several different parameters can be estimated. In this context two different cases has been distinguished. In the first case the mechanism of the reactions is known and we can estimate parameters for other data under the condition that the mechanism is the same. However, it is also possible to model the system and estimate outputs without any knowledge about the microscopic behaviour of the system.

ANN represents simple, general and robust approach to model complex chemical kinetic systems and they are widely applicable even to problems where “hard” models are not available.

Figure 1: A general structure of ANN architecture with INPUTS, OUTPUTS and 2 hidden layers.

References:

- [1] M. M. Canedo and J. L. González-Hernández, A new computational application of the AGDC algorithm for kinetic resolution of multicomponent mixtures (static and dynamic). *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*; **2003**, 66, 63-78
- [2] Molga, E. J.; Van Woezik, B. A. A.; Westerterp, K. R., Neural networks for modelling of chemical reaction systems with complex kinetics: oxidation of 2-octanol with nitric acid. *Chemical Engineering and Processing* **2000**, 39 (4), 323-334.
- [3] Vajda, S.; Rabitz, H., Identifiability and Distinguishability of General Reaction Systems. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry* **1994**, 98 (20), 5265-5271.

Contribution of KAT Parameters for the Description of Solvent Effects on the CDTA and EGTA Complexes

Kavosh MAJLESI, Saghar REZAIENEJAD

*Department of Chemistry, Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran,
IRAN*

kavoshmajlesi@srbiau.ac.ir

Thermodynamic characteristics of solvation for all reagents involved in complexation are needed to understand the influence of mixed solvent composition on complex formation equilibrium. A multitude of empirical single and multiparameter solvent scales designed on the basis of solvent dependent phenomena are aimed at describing and quantifying the solvation interactions at molecular level. Single empirical parameters, multiparameter correlation equations have been developed, each of them measuring certain aspect of the overall solvation capability of a given solvent such as: solvent polarizability, dipolarity, hydrogen bonding donor acidity and acceptor basicity. Several multiparameter equations have been constructed to explain the solvent effect. Though a large amount of progress has been made in the calculation of solute-solvent interactions by the use of modern quantum mechanical methods, the empirical parameters continue to be of interest to experimental chemists. One single parameter can not be expected to be universally valid for all kinds of solvent-sensitive processes and thus a great variety of multiparameter treatments of solvent effects have been developed. One of the most successful quantitative treatments of solvent effects using a multiparameter equation is that of Kamlet-Abboud-Taft (KAT), known as the linear solvation energy relationship (LSER). Our laboratory has taken up the study of complexation of various aminopolycarboxylic acids with VO_2^+ and MoO_4^{2-} ions in order to study the influence of the solvents and ionic medium and to determine the contribution of KAT parameters in recent years [1-7]. Therefore in this work the intermolecular specific and non specific solute-solvent interactions were studied for trans-1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N, N, N', N'- tetraacetic acid (CDTA) and ethylene glycol-bis(2-aminoethylether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (EGTA) complexes of VO_2^+ ion by using the KAT equation. A UV spectrophotometric study of the complexation was carried out at a fixed ionic strength ($0.1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ of sodium perchlorate) and $t = 25^\circ\text{C}$ in different binary methanol-water mixtures. It was found that Lewis basicity parameter is the most important factor for the abovementioned complexes and the solvent can affect the stoichiometric composition of the complexes in some cases. The other KAT parameters (Lewis acidity and polarity) are in the second and third order.

References:

- [1] Majlesi, K.; Gholamhosseinzadeh, M.; Rezaiejad, S., Interaction of Molybdenum(VI) with Methyliminodiacetic Acid at Different Ionic Strengths by Using

- Parabolic, Extended Debye-Hückel and Specific Ion Interaction Models. *J. Solution. Chem* **2010**, 39 (5), 665-679.
- [2] Majlesi, K.; Rezaiejad, S., Solvatochromic Effect Studies on the Stability of Dioxovanadium(V) Complexes with Ethylene glycol-bis(2-aminoethylether)-N, N,N',N'- tetraacetic Acid in Different Water + Methanol Mixtures. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2010**, 55 (10), 4491-4498.
- [3] Majlesi, K.; Rezaiejad, S., Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with Methyliminodiacetic Acid in NaClO₄ Aqueous Solutions at Different Ionic Strengths by Using EDH, SIT and Parabolic Equations. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2010**, 55 (2), 882-888.
- [4] Majlesi, K.; Momeni, N., Complexation of Molybdenum(VI) with Ethylenediaminediacetic Acid in Different Water + Methanol Solutions. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2009**, 54 (9), 2479-2482.
- [5] Majlesi, K.; Rezaiejad, S., Application of the Parabolic Model, Specific Ion Interaction and Debye-Hückel Theories for the Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with Ethylenediamine-N, N'-diacetic Acid. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2009**, 54 (5), 1483-1492.
- [6] Majlesi, K.; Zare, K.; Rezaiejad, S., Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with Nitrilotriacetic Acid at Different Ionic Strengths by Using Specific Ion Interaction and Debye-Hückel Theories. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2008**, 53 (10), 2333-2340.

Comparison of the Application of Debye-Huckel, Specific Ion Interaction and Parabolic models for the Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with D-(-)-Quinic Acid

Saghar REZAIENEJAD, Kavosh MAJLESI

*Department of Chemistry, Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran,
IRAN*

[*sagharrezaiejad@gmail.com*](mailto:sagharrezaiejad@gmail.com)

Several reports have been published regarding the existence of vanadium in biological systems. Vanadium compounds may act as potential antimetastatic agents by inhibiting the induction of intracellular adhesive molecules and may also induce cytotoxic effects through DNA cleavage/fragmentation and plasma membrane lipoperoxidation. In this research the stability constants for the reaction of dioxovanadium(V) with D-(-)-quinic acid were determined at 25 ° C and different ionic strengths of sodium chloride. Speciation diagrams and dissociation constants were obtained on the basis of UV data and potentiometric titrations respectively. Acidic solutions of dioxovanadium(V) were titrated with basic solutions of quinic acid. The absorbance data in the UV range(245 to 280 nm) and pH = 1.00-3.00 were used for minimizing the error function on the basis of Gauss-Newton nonlinear least squares method in Microsoft Excel 2000 program. Parabolic, Specific Ion Interaction Theory (SIT) and Extended Debye-Hückel type (EDH) models successfully described the stability constants ionic strength dependence pattern. The SIT model is most useful in the ionic strength range up to 3.5-4.0 mol dm⁻³ and successful applications of the SIT model at 25°C in NaCl solutions up to the saturation of halite have also been demonstrated. The Specific Ion Interaction theory has been adopted as a standard procedure for the extrapolation and correction of equilibrium constants to infinite dilution in the OECD-NEA thermochemical databases. This research establishes the formation of only one species, VO₂L, for the complexation of VO₂⁺ ion with D-(-)-quinic acid and there is a good agreement between the SIT and parabolic models for stability and dissociation constants values at infinite dilution, but the results on the basis of the EDH model are different. The medium dependence is described by ion interaction coefficients in the SIT model. Δε values on the basis of SIT and parabolic models are more or less similar to each other and show that there is a combination of mild decrease and increase in stability constants variations with ionic strength. In this case, the dependence of stability constants on ionic strength is not very significant.

References:

- [1] Majlesi, K.; Rezaiejad, S. Application of the Parabolic Model, Specific Ion Interaction, and Debye-Hückel Theories for the Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with Ethylenediamine-N,N'-diacetic Acid. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2009**, 54, 1483-1492.

- [2] Majlesi, K. Complexation of Dioxovanadium (V) with Phenylalanine and Isoleucine at Different Ionic Strengths and Temperatures Using Debye-Hückel and Specific Ion Interaction Theories. *Rev. Inorg. Chem.* **2009**, 29, 1-19.
- [3] Majlesi, K.; Rezaiejad, S., Complexation of Dioxovanadium(V) with Methyliminodiacetic Acid in NaClO₄ Aqueous Solutions at Different Ionic Strengths by Using EDH, SIT and Parabolic Equations. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2010**, 55 (2), 882-888.
- [4] Majlesi, K.; Rezaiejad, S., Rouhzad, A., Ionic Strength Dependence of Dioxovanadium(V) Complexation with Ethylene Glycol-bis(2-aminoethylether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic Acid *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2011**, 56, 541-550.

The Inclusion of Activities in the Analysis of Equilibrium and Kinetic Studies. No More Inert Salts!

Nichola McCANN,^{a)} Peter KING,^{b)} Marcel MAEDER^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Chemistry, University of Newcastle, Australia*

^{b)} *Jplus Consulting, Perth, Australia*

Marcel.Maeder@newcastle.edu.au

In equilibrium studies it is common practice to maintain constant ionic strength by addition of an excess of inert salt to all solutions investigated. There are obvious disadvantages like additional cost but more importantly interference by ions that are not really completely inert. Additionally, if fundamental thermodynamic constants are to be reported the investigation of extensive ionic strength dependences have to be undertaken; i.e. constants are determined at a range of ionic strengths and extrapolation to zero ionic strength results in the desired value.

The law of mass action is based on activities. Constant ionic strength results in constant activity coefficients which allows the determination of ionic strength dependent equilibrium constants by numerical analysis, i.e. traditional data fitting software.

It is possible to estimate activity coefficients, based on a range of Debye- Hückel and other similar approximations, and we have incorporated these directly into the analysis algorithms. This results straightaway in thermodynamic constants at zero ionic strength since changes in ionic strength during the experiment are accommodated in the computations. No more inert salts and no more ionic strength dependences!

An example in kinetics ($\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{oxalate}^{2-} \rightarrow \text{Ni(ox)}$) is given below where the blue, dashed curve represents the traditional approach and the red, full line indicates that any single measurement results in the thermodynamic value. Several other applications will be presented.

Factor analysis program INDICES for prediction of the number of components in spectroscopic data

Milan MELOUN

*Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology,
University Pardubice, CZ-532 10 Pardubice, Czech Republic,
milan.meloun@upce.cz*

Determining the number of chemical components in a mixture is the first important step for further qualitative and quantitative analysis in all forms of spectral data treatment. Accuracy of 13 various statistical indices methods for estimation of the number of components that contribute to spectra was critically tested on simulated and on experimental data sets using algorithm INDICES in S-Plus software. All indices methods are classified into two categories, the precise methods based upon a knowledge of the instrumental error of the absorbance data, $s_{\text{inst}}(A)$, and the approximate methods requiring no such knowledge. Most indices always predict the correct number of components even a presence of the minor one when the signal-to-error ratio SE R is higher than 10 but in case of RESO and IND higher than 6. On base of SE R the detection limit of every index method is estimated. Two indices, RESO and IND, correctly predict a minor component in a mixture even its relative concentration is about 0.5 - 1% and solve an ill-defined problem with severe collinearity in spectra. Wernimont-Kankare procedure performs reliable determination of the instrumental standard deviation of spectrophotometer used. In case of real experimental data the RESO, IND and indices methods based on knowledge of instrumental error should be preferred. To investigate all statistical properties of absorbance data matrix which were designed to be quite similar to real experimental data and cover some typical situations of analytical practice, several data sets of absorption spectra were simulated for a three-components system in mixture: potassium bichromate, cobalt(II) sulphate and copper(II) sulphate, a mixture abbreviated {Cr-Co-Cu}. An absorbance matrix was created by multiplying absorptivity spectra of three components by their simulated concentration profiles to reach resulting absorbance. Each matrix data set contains digitized spectra consisted of digitized wavelengths. Random noise was added to the spectra by generating random numbers with a Gaussian distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation equal to the pre-selected noise level, $s_{\text{inst}}(A)$, to reach an optioned SE R value.

Acknowledgments: The financial support of the Grant Agency IGA MZ ČR (No NS9831-4/2008) and of the Czech Ministry of Education (Grant No MSM0021627502) is gratefully acknowledged.

References:

- [1] Meloun M., Čapek J., Mikšík P., Brereton R. G., Critical comparison of methods predicting the number of components in spectroscopic data *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2000**, Vol. 423, 51 - 68.

Fig. 1: (a) Spectra of relative absorbance for three components in a simulated three-components system in mixture, potassium bichromate - cobalt(II) sulphate - copper(II) sulphate, with $r = 3$, $n = 82$, $m = 41$ and $SER = 1570$, S-Plus, (b) 3D-relative absorption spectra forms the input of INDICES.

Fig. 2 The output of INDICES program: the indices (full circles) and logarithm of the indices (empty circles) of 13 methods as a function of the number of principal components k for a data of Fig. 1.

Assymmetric tetranuclear mixed-ligand copper(II) complex with 4-aminopyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine ligand

Alicia DOMÍNGUEZ-MARTÍN,^{a)} **Duane CHOQUESILLO-LAZARTE**,^{b)} **Elena BUGELLA-ALTAMIRANO**,^{a)} **Josefa María GONZÁLEZ-PÉREZ**,^{a)} **Alfonso CASTIÑEIRAS**,^{c)} **Juan NICLÓS-GUTIÉRREZ**^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Granada, Fac. Pharmacy, Campus Cartuja; Granada (18071), Spain.*

^{b)} *Edif. Inst Lopez Neyra, University of Granada, Laboratorio de Estudios Cristalográficos, IACT, Avda. del Conocimiento; Armilla, Granada (18100), Spain.*

^{c)} *Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Santiago, Fac. Pharmacy, Campus sur; Santiago de Compostela (15782), Spain.*

adominguez@ugr.es

4-aminopyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine (H4app) is an isomer of adenine (Hade) within the five-membered ring in the pyrazole configuration (see scheme 1). This fact mainly leads to alteration in the basicity order of the N-heterocyclic atoms that would affect to the molecular recognition of this purine ligand. In this sense, H4app has raised a great interest for its promising applications [1].

As a part of our research on mixed-ligand metal complexes with purine-like ligands and iminodiacetate chelators [2], we report the synthesis, the molecular and crystal structure and some physical properties (thermal stability, FT-IR and electronic spectra) of the novel compound $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{FBIDA})_4(\mu_2\text{-N}8,\text{N}9\text{-H}(\text{N}1)4\text{app})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. A figure of the complex molecule is depicted (H-atoms and non-coordinated water omitted for clarity).

The four Cu(II) coordination polyhedra are square-planar pyramidal, type 4+1. Metal surroundings of Cu1 to Cu3 are rather similar. They are chelated by the N-atom and two O-carboxylate atoms from N-(p-fluorobenzyl) iminodiacetate (FBIDA) chelating ligand plus one

N-atom of H4app ligand in the basal plane whereas one O-carboxylate atom is placed in the apical site, with Cu-O(carboxy) distances about 2.34-2.38 Å. Cu4 has a similar basal coordination set of donor atoms but its apical site is occupied by one aqua ligand, where Cu4-O(aqua) distance is 2.46 Å. According to these data, the distortion of the four closest donor atoms around the copper(II) is smaller for Cu1 to Cu3 (Addison parameter $\tau = 0.05$ (Cu2) or $\tau = 0.07$ (Cu1 and Cu3)) than for Cu4 ($\tau = 0.11$).

The most relevant features of the novel tetranuclear complex molecule are: (1) the FBIDA ligands play three different roles: the chelating ligand of Cu1 acts only as tridentate; the FBIDA ligands of Cu2 and Cu4 display such tridentate role but also acts as μ_2 -O(coord. carboxylate) ligand; the Cu3 atom is tridentately chelated by a FBIDA ligand that also plays the bridging μ_2 -O'-carboxylate role. The $\text{Cu}_2(\mu_2\text{-O}'\text{-FBIDA})\text{Cu}_3$ moiety exhibits a rough anti-syn conformation. (2) Both H4app ligands play the same μ_2 -N8,N9 bridging role. It should be remarked that the implication of N8 and N9 atoms represents the migration of the dissociable proton of H4app to N1 atom. (3) In the complex molecule Cu1 and Cu2 or Cu3 and Cu4 are linked by two unequal bridges. One is a monoatomic O-carboxylate bridge and the other is the N8,N9-H4app bridge. This kind of bridge represents the formation of non-planar five-membered di-copper rings (scheme 2).

The novel complex shows an acyclic non-linear topology in clear contrast to the centrosymmetric cyclic tetranuclear molecule of the compound $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{pheida})_2(\mu_2\text{-O}'\text{-pheida})_2(\mu_2\text{-N3,N7-H(N9)ade})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [3] (pheida = N-phenetyl-iminodiacetate(2-) ligand). The cyclic topology of this latter compound involves the bridging role of adenine ligands as well as the bridging role of only two pheida ligands. The stability of this cyclic tetranuclear molecule is tied to the reinforcements of Cu-N3 and Cu-N7 coordination bonds by intra-molecular interligand N9-H \cdots O(carboxy) and N6-H \cdots O(carboxy) H-bonding interactions. However, in the novel compound here reported, only the apical aqua ligand is involved in intra-molecular interligand H-bonding interactions with O(carboxylate) acceptors from two different FBIDA ligands (one of them bridging between Cu2 and Cu3 atoms) what seems to be related to the peculiar topology of here reported tetranuclear complex.

References:

- [1] Carraro, F.; Naldini, A.; Pucci, A.; Locatelli, G.A.; Maga, G.; Schenone, S.; Bruno, O.; Ranise, A.; Bondavalli, F.; Brullo, C.; et al, Pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines as potent Antiproliferative and Proapoptotic agents toward A431 and 8701-BC Cells in Culture via Inhibition of c-Src Phosphorylation, *J. Med. Chem.*, **2006**, 49(5), 1549-1561.
- [2] Patel, D.K.; Domínguez-Martín, A; Brandi-Blanco, M.P.; Nurchi, V.M.; Niclós-Gutiérrez, J., Metal ion binding modes of hypoxanthine and xanthine versus the versatile behaviour of adenine, *Coord. Chem. Reviews*, **2011**, submitted for publication.
- [3] Bugella-Altamirano, E.; Choquesillo-Lazarte, D.; González-Pérez, J.M.; Sánchez-Moreno, M.J.; Marín-Sánchez, R.; Martín-Ramos, J.D.; Covelo, B.; Carballo, R.; Castiñeiras, A.; Niclós-Gutiérrez, J., Three new modes of adenine- copper(II) coordination: interligand interactions controlling the selective N3-, N7- and bridging μ -N3,N7-metal-bonding of adenine to different N-substituted iminodiacetato-copper(II) chelates, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, **2002**, 339, 160-170.

Copper(II) complexes of the oxime-and-amide ligands: The influence of peripheral hydroxyl group on coordination

Igor Vasyli NIKOLAYENKO, Thomas John THERON

*University of KwaZulu-Natal, School of Chemistry (Pietermaritzburg), Private Bag X01,
Scottsville, 3209, Pietermaritzburg (South Africa), +27 0332605658
nikolaenko@ukzn.ac.za*

Coordination chemistry of oxime and amide donor groups is extensive and has profound biological relevance [1]. When encountered within the same ligand molecule, in particular, in close proximity to each other, they afford a variety of coordination modes towards transition metal ions [2-3]. In the past few years we have been involved with the synthesis, characterisation, and thermodynamic studies in solution of ligand (1), abbreviated as **hip₂pn**, and its complexes with divalent transition group metals. This ligand proved to possess useful metal binding centre and afforded two classes of stable complexes with Cu(II) ion.

Recently, we have prepared, isolated and characterised new ligand (2), abbreviated as **hip₂pn-OH**, different from (1) by a hydroxyl group in peripheral position (on the spacer bridging the chelating moieties). We expected that introduction of this group might influence: a) water solubility of metal complexes formed, and b) their thermodynamic stability due to the change in nucleophilicity of the amide nitrogen donors and different degree of sterical crowding in the bridge area. In current presentation we shall report and discuss the results of the thermodynamic (potentiometric, spectroscopic, and calorimetric), structural, magnetic, and computational study of copper(II) complexes with ligand (2) and compare them to findings for ligand (1). While ligand (1) is known to be diprotic in aqueous medium, and subsequently is denoted as LH₂, ligand (2) to our surprise turned out to deprotonate in three steps, and has to be labelled as LH₃. Supporting evidence and our interpretation of the fact will be presented and discussed. Our studies also established the formation of multiple copper(II) complexes in both systems. From the perspective of coordination environment around the metal ion they can be subdivided into two classes: class A, pseudo-macrocyclic complexes with N₂(ox)N₂(am) square planar coordination, and class B, somewhat mysterious complexes of the M : L = 2 : 1 ratio, likely to contain N(ox)O(am) chelate units. A-type complexes, orange-red in aqueous solutions, could be deprotonated to different degree, structures A1 to A3; also, some of them form dimeric species in solution (not shown).

B-type complexes, grey-green in aqueous medium, all display a characteristic absorption band in the electronic spectrum with the wavelength of maximum absorption close to 900 nm. Based on this unusual near IR *d-d* transition, we postulated the coordination environment with a direct contact of two Cu²⁺-centres. On the basis of the stoichiometric composition established in the refinement of potentiometric titration data as well as *ab initio* computer modelling, we suggest for these complexes provisional structure B1.

So far our attempts to isolate such compounds in solid state proved unsuccessful. However, ESR spectra of a series of aqueous solutions in the Cu-hip₂pn-OH system lend some credibility to the idea of direct Cu-Cu bonding; samples expected to contain sizeable amounts of such complexes have shown marked decrease in the number of unpaired Cu *d*-electrons (due to possible *d*_{z²} – *d*_{z²} coupling). Two different protonation states of B-type complexes have been detected for these ligands, di-cationic (shown above) and neutral. In the absence of direct structural evidence, we assume they differ by the number of deprotonated water molecules directly coordinated to copper ions. Factual evidence in support of all of the above statements will be presented. We shall also offer our interpretation of the complexes stability in relation to their molecular structures derived from the crystallographic studies and *ab initio* quantum mechanical modelling.

References:

- [1] Onindo, C.O.; Sliva, T.Yu.; Kowalik-Jankowska, T.; et al., Copper(II) co-ordination by oxime analogues of amino acids and peptides. *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.* **1995**, (23), 3911-3916.
- [2] Duda, A.M.; Karaczyn, A.; Kozlowski, H.; et al., Co-ordination of copper(II) and Nickel(II) ions by a novel open chain oxime ligand. *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.* **1997**, (20), 3853-3860.
- [3] Fritsky, I.O.; Kozlowski, H.; Prisyazhnaya, E.V.; et al., A short intramolecular hydrogen bond is a key factor in the self-assembly of a dimeric complex with a 22-membered macrocyclic cavity. *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.* **1998**, (10), 1535-1536.

The Hydroxyl Group: A Versatile Metal Ion-Binding Site

Helmut SIGEL, Bert P. OPERSCHALL, Astrid SIGEL

University of Basel, Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry, Spitalstrasse 51, CH-4056 Basel, Switzerland
Helmut.Sigel@unibas.ch

Hydroxyl groups occur in legion in many organic compounds but especially in those found in nature, like carbohydrates or nucleic acids and their derivatives. However, information about metal ion-hydroxyl group interactions is very scarce because such interactions are commonly weak and take place only if a primary binding site brings the hydroxyl group close to the metal ion. We have now reviewed the literature with regard to available stability constants of complexes formed by ligands containing next to a primary binding site a hydroxyl residue [1]. The following (monodentate) primary binding sites (PBS)

were considered: Phosph(on)ate, carboxylate, amino, imidazole, and pyridyl groups. In the given order the charge transfer from the primary coordinating atom to the metal ion decreases and this facilitates the hydroxyl-metal ion interaction. As far as possible, the alkaline earth ions, several 3d ions (Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+}), as well as Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , and Pb^{2+} ($= M^{2+}$) were used and the position of the intramolecular equilibrium (1) between the isomeric complexes, that is, between the open and closed or chelated forms, was determined.

Any hydroxyl-metal ion interaction must be connected with a stability enhancement, $\log \Delta$, compared to the stability of the complex formed by the primary binding site (PBS) alone [2]. This latter species is designated as $M(PBS-OH)_{op}$ and the chelated or closed one as $M(PBS-OH)_{cl}$. The formation degrees of the closed species can be calculated, e.g., for the complexes of hydroxyacetate ($HOAc^- = glycolate$) by constructing $\log K_{stab}$ versus pK_a straight-line plots [1] for simple carboxylate ligands (CA^-) (chloroacetate, formate, acetate, etc. [3]) (Figure; aq. sol.; 25°C; $I = 0.1$ M [1]). The M^{2+}/OH interaction leads to the stability enhancement $\log \Delta$ (= vertical distances in the Figure) [2, 4], and thus, to the proof that the

intramolecular equilibrium (1) exists. The dimension-less equilibrium constant K_I is linked to this enhancement by $K_I = [M(HOAc)_{cl}^+]/[M(HOAc)_{op}^+] = 10^{\log \Delta} - 1$ [4]. With known K_I

values the formation degrees (%) of the closed/chelated isomers can be calculated [4]. Some results are summarized in the Table [1]:

M ²⁺	log K _{M(HOAc)exp} ^M	log K _{M(HOAc)op} ^M	log Δ _{M/HOAc}	K _I	% M(HOAc) _{cl} ⁺
Ba ²⁺	0.66±0.06	0.24±0.11	0.42±0.13	1.63±0.76	62±11
Sr ²⁺	0.80±0.06	0.30±0.12	0.50±0.13	2.16±0.98	68±10
Ca ²⁺	1.11±0.06	0.33±0.05	0.78±0.08	5.03±1.08	83± 3
Mg ²⁺	0.92±0.06	0.38±0.03	0.54±0.07	2.47±0.54	71± 4
Mn ²⁺	1.23±0.10	0.63±0.12	0.60±0.16	2.98±1.43	75± 9
Cu ²⁺	2.40±0.06	0.61±0.05	0.79±0.08	5.17±1.11	84± 3
Zn ²⁺	1.98±0.04	0.94±0.04	1.04±0.06	9.96±1.43	91± 1

For the complexes of *o*-(hydroxymethyl)pyridine (HOMPy) with its neutral primary binding site even values of 92 and 99% are reached, e.g., for Mn(HOMPy)²⁺ and Zn(HOMPy)²⁺, respectively. A change from 5-membered chelates to potential 6-membered ones reduces the formation degree of the closed species very drastically, whereas a reduction of the solvent polarity (addition of 1,4-dioxane) favors it. An ether O atom is a poorer binding site than the hydroxyl group, as one might expect [1].

Of course, with ligands like 2,6-(dihydroxymethyl)pyridine the extent of the hydroxyl-metal ion interaction increases because now two sites are available for an interaction. A further point that warrants emphasis is that with N-hydroxyethylglycinate (HOGly⁻), which offers the bidentate glycinate-like unit as the primary binding site, the formation degree of the closed species involving the hydroxyl group increases drastically, leading in general to formation degrees of above 99.5% for the M(HOGly)_{cl}⁺ species [1]. The explanation for this observation is the "rigidity" that results upon binding of the glycinate-like unit to M²⁺; thereafter, the hydroxyl group is close to the metal ion and its movements in space are more restricted than it is the case with a monodentate primary binding site.

The relevance of the indicated results for biological systems, especially nucleic acids, is obvious. For example, Ca²⁺ has a higher affinity for hydroxyl groups than the other alkaline earth ions as follows from the Table. The stability enhancement, log Δ, for the Ca(HOAc)⁺ complex is by 0.24 (Mg²⁺) and 0.28 (Sr²⁺) log units more pronounced than that of its neighboring elements. In the case of the Mg(HOGly)_{cl}⁺ and Ca(HOGly)_{cl}⁺ species, the additional enhancement for the Ca²⁺ complex amounts to about 1.8 log unit! Here might be the reason for the atypical strong influence of Ca²⁺ on group II intron ribozyme catalysis and folding [5]. To conclude, the indicated results are of general interest for nucleic acid, macromolecular, and coordination chemistry, as well as catalysis.

Supported by the Department of Chemistry of the University of Basel.

- [1] Al-Sogair, F. M.; Operschall, B. P.; Sigel, A.; Sigel, H.; Schnabl, J.; Sigel, R. K. O., *Chem. Rev.* **2011**, *111*, in press.
- [2] Martin, R. B.; Sigel, H., *Comments Inorg. Chem.* **1988**, *6*, 285-314.
- [3] NIST Database 46, Version 8.0, data collected by Smith, R. M.; Martell, A. E., NIST, US Commerce Dept. Gaithersburg, MD, **2003**.
- [4] Sigel, H.; Kapinos, L. E., *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2000**, *200-202*, 563-594.
- [5] Steiner, M.; Rueda, D.; Sigel, R. K. O., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 9739-9742.

Study of the quenching of the excited state of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ by $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Pz}]^{3+}$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in the presence of α -cyclodextrins

**Francisco SANCHEZ, ^{b)} Tania LOPES-COSTA, ^{a)} Pilar LOPEZ-CORNEJO, ^{a)}
Francisco MONTILLA, ^{c)}**

^{a)} *Departamento de Química Física, Facultad de Química. Universidad de Sevilla.
C/ Profesor García González S/N, 41012, Sevilla (Spain)*

^{b)} *Departamento de Química Física, Facultad de Química. Universidad de Sevilla.
C/ Profesor García González S/N, 41012, Sevilla (Spain).*

^{c)} *Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Facultad de Química. Universidad de Sevilla.
C/ Profesor García González S/N, 41012, Sevilla (Spain).*

gcjrv@us.es

The quenching of the excited state of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ by $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Pz}]^{3+}$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ was studied in the presence of α -CD. The results imply that in the first of these reactions only one of the reactants, the ruthenium complex is bound to the α -CD. In the second case, both, the ruthenium complex as well as the quencher are bound to α -CD.

Formally, the pseudophase model explains the results obtained in the two reactions studied. A discussion on the meaning of the parameters obtained from the fit of the data to the (different) equations of this model will be presented.

Comparison of kinetic and thermodynamic approaches for the determination of binding constants of excited species to different receptors.

Eva BERNAL^{b)}, **Francisco SANCHEZ**,^{a)} **María MARCHENA**,^{a)}

^{a)} *Departamento de Química Física, Facultad de Química. Universidad de Sevilla.
C/ Profesor García González S/N, 41012, Sevilla (Spain)*

^{b)} *Departamento de Química Física, Facultad de Química. Universidad de Sevilla.
C/ Profesor García González S/N, 41012, Sevilla (Spain).*

evabernal@us.es

Generally speaking, the changes in reactivity caused by restricted geometry conditions (r.g.c.) have been explained by taking as a basis the Pseudophase Model of Menger and Portnoy [1] and related models [2]. These formulations assume an equilibrium distribution between free and bound reactants, characterized by an equilibrium constant K.

As matter of fact, the Pseudophase Model describes well the data in cases of rapid photochemical reactions, when the equilibrium condition does not hold [3-6]. This introduces the following question: *What is the meaning of parameters obtained by fitting the experimental data to the Pseudophase Model, in the case of photochemical reactions?* We developed a model that can explain the above mentioned facts and gives meaning to the parameters [7]. This model gives that the changes in the Stern-Volmer constants are not governed by K, but K_{app}, being K_{app}=K*(a_b/a_f). a_f and a_b are the quantum yields of the fluorophore free and bound to the receptor, respectively. This model is obeyed in the case of slow exchange limit, when λ_{exc} corresponds to the isosbestic point of the fluorophore and there is a homogeneous distribution of the quencher in the system, the following equations:

$$(K_{SV})_{obs} = \frac{(K_{SV})_f + (K_{SV})_b K_{app}[M]}{1 + K_{app}[M]} \quad (2)$$

$$K_{app} = K \frac{\Phi_b}{\Phi_f} \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi_i = \frac{k_i}{(k_r)_i + (k_{nr})_i + (k_q)_i [Q]} \quad (4)$$

In order to check this model we have studied the quenching of the excited state of 1-pyrene-carboxaldehyde by iodide (at fixed ionic strength) in the presence of DNA and β-cyclodextrin (β-CD), two receptors of different characteristics. The idea is to determine K following a classical procedure and compare it with the value obtained through equations 2-4 (K_{calc}). The results are in quantitative agreement with the model so:

	K /mol ⁻¹ dm ³	K_{app} / mol ⁻¹ dm ³	Φ_b/Φ_f	K_{calc} / mol ⁻¹ dm ³
DNA solutions	9400	1104	0.12	9200
β- CD solutions	1100	Range 2465-2909	Range 1.83-3.76	Average 1147

In conclusion, we have established a treatment that explains why, in the slow exchange limit of the excited state, the system behaves, apparently, according to the predictions of the two state model. The treatment establishes a quantitative relation (equation 3) between the true binding constant of the fluorophore to a given receptor and the apparent binding constant, obtained from kinetic (quenching) data. The treatment was applied to the quenching of 1-pyrene-carboxaldehyde by I⁻ in the presence of two different receptors. Quantitative agreement was found between the predictions of the treatment and the experimental data.

References:

- [1] Menger, F.M. ; Portnoy, C.E. , Chemistry of reactions proceeding inside molecular aggregates. *J. Am. Chem.Soc.* **1967**, 89 (18), 4698-4703.
- [2] Quina, F.H. ; Chaimovich, H. , Ion exchange in micellar solutions. 1. Conceptual framework for ion exchange in micellar solutions. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1979**, 83(14), 1844-1850.
- [3] Lopez-Cornejo, P. ; Sanchez, F. , Micellar Effects on the Kinetics of the Oxidation of the Excited State of the [Ru(bpy)3]2+ Complex by S2O82-. A Comparison of Different Approaches for the Interpretation of Micellar Effects on Kinetics. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2001**, 105 (43), 10523-10527.
- [4] López-Cornejo, P. ; Mozo, J.D. , Roldán, E. ; Domínguez, M. ; Sánchez, F. , Kinetic study of the reaction *Ru(bpy)3]2++S2O82- in solutions of Brij-35 at premicellar and micellar concentrations Dendrimers. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **2002**, 352 (1-2), 33-38.
- [5] Pelizzetti, E. ; Pramauro, E., Micellar effect on electron transfer. 1. Electron transfer of tris(2,2'-bipyridine)ruthenium in micellar solutions. *Inorg.Chem.* **1979**,18 (3), 882-883.
- [6] Lopes-Costa, T. ; Sanchez, F. ; Lopez-Cornejo, P. , Cooperative and Noncooperative Binding of *Ru(bpy)3]2+ to DNA and SB4.5G Dendrimers *J. Phys. Chem. B.* **2009**, 113(28), 9373-9378.
- [7] Marchena, M. ; Sanchez, F. , Kinetics of Photochemical Reactions Under Restricted Geometry Conditions. Progress in Reaction Kineticsand Mechanism. *Prog. React. Kinet. Mech.* **2010**, 35, 27-80.

Determination of reaction and reorganization free energies of electron transfer reactions under restricted geometry conditions.

Manuel LÓPEZ-LÓPEZ, ^{a)} **Francisco SÁNCHEZ,** ^{b)} **María MARCHENA** ^{b)}

^{a)} *Department of Chemical Engineering, Physical Chemistry and Organic Chemistry.
University of Huelva (Spain)*

^{b)} *Department of Physical Chemistry. University of Seville (Spain).
marijose@us.es*

Electron transfer reactions under restricted geometry conditions are of prime importance in Chemistry and Biochemistry. In fact, solar energy capture and storage is based, in natural and artificial systems, in this type of processes, because “any practical system for solar energy conversion and storage will involve heterogeneous reactions at some stage of the process”. The fabrication of sensors, the construction of molecular machines etc. are also related to electron transfer reaction under restricted geometry conditions.

In order to control the rate of this kind of reaction it is necessary to know how the restricted geometry conditions influences these reaction rates. In particular it is important to know the influence of the two parameters, the reaction, ΔG^0 , and reorganization free energies, λ , which determine the Franck-Condon factor of the rate constants:

$$k_{et} = Ae^{(\lambda + \Delta G^0)^2 / 4\lambda}$$

However, these free energies are not experimental parameters: they must be obtained from k_{et} which, in turn, must be extracted from the experimental rate constant.

In this communication we present different approaches used by us for obtaining λ and ΔG^0 , when the reactants participating in the electron transfer processes are bound to different receptors, that is, the reaction is produced under restricted geometry conditions.

15-Metallacrown-5 complexes: thermodynamic and kinetic selectivity for core metal ions

Matteo TEGONI,^{a)} **Choong Sun LIM,**^{b)} **Maurizio REMELLI,**^{c)} **Francesco DALLAVALLE,**^{a)} **Vincent L. PECORARO**^{b)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Generale ed Inorganica, Analitica, Fisica; Università di Parma, Parco Area delle Scienze 17A-43100 Parma (Italy)*

^{b)} *Department of Chemistry, University of Michigan, 930 N. University Ave, MI 48109-1055 Ann Arbor (USA)*

^{c)} *Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Ferrara, Via L. Borsari 46, 44100, Ferrara (Italy)*
matteo.tegoni@unipr.it

Metallacrowns (MC) are the inorganic analogs of crown ethers (Scheme 1) [1]. They can be obtained by self assembly of appropriate ligands (*e.g.* aminohydroxamates) and transition metal ions (*e.g.* Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺). 15-MC-5 complexes can be assembled using α -aminohydroxamates and both Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ as ring metals. Their formation is promoted by the presence of a suitable core metal ion (*e.g.* Ca²⁺ or Ln³⁺) which acts as a templating cation [2-4].

Scheme 1: Schematic representation of {Cu(II)[12-MC_{Cu(II)N}(β -Alaha)-4]}²⁺ (left, β -Alaha = β -alanine-hydroxamic acid) and {Ln(III)[15-MC_{Cu(II)N}(α -Alaha)-5]}³⁺ (right, α -Alaha = (*S*)- α -alaninehydroxamic acid).

In the past years, our research groups focussed on the study of the thermodynamics of self-assembly and core metal substitution of 15-MC-5 as a function of the nature of the core metal ion. The thermodynamic stability of {Ln(III)[15-MC_{Cu(II)N}(Ligand)-5]}³⁺ (Ligand = Pheha, Trpha) is similar for lanthanides in the series La-Gd. For the heavier lanthanides series (Gd-Yb), the MC stability steeply decreases as the result of unfavourable desolvation energies and lack of size correspondence between the core metal and the MC cavity (Figure 1). These data demonstrated that the metallacrown is stable even when the core Ln³⁺ is too large to properly fit into the cavity. Core metals larger than the cavity can act as an efficient templating cations, while core metals smaller than the cavity cannot stabilize efficiently the MC scaffold.

The kinetics of Ca²⁺-Ln³⁺ substitution for {Ca(II)[15-MC_{Cu(II)N}(Ligand)-5]}²⁺ (Ligand = Pheha, Trpha) are also dependent on the nature of the Ln³⁺ involved. For these processes, the larger is the lanthanide the faster is the core metal substitution reaction: while a decrease in the second-order kinetic constants is observed for the La³⁺-Gd³⁺ series, almost no differences are observed for the Gd³⁺-Er³⁺ series. Noteworthy, ESI-MS experiments ruled out a

deassembly mechanism for the core metal substitution, supporting a direct transmetallation step where the integrity of the MC scaffold is preserved.

Figure 1: Plot of $\log K$ values for Ca - Ln core metal substitution for $\{\text{Ca(II)}[15\text{-MC}_{\text{Cu(II)N}(\text{Trpha})\text{-5}}]^{2+}\}$ in methanol/water 99:1 as a function of the Ln^{3+} ionic radius.

Our studies demonstrated that while the formation of 15-MC-5 of Cu^{2+} needs a templating cation, the formation of 15-MC-5 of Ni^{2+} does not strictly require the presence of a suitable core metal. In fact, the vacant $[15\text{-MC}_{\text{Ni(II)N}(\alpha\text{-Alaha})\text{-5}]$ is assembled even when alkali metals are absent, and noteworthy this is the first example of a vacant, planar 15-MC-5 of aminohydroxamates reported in the literature. As regards the templating capability of Na^+ and K^+ , they do not act as efficient templating cations for copper(II) MCs. On the contrary, our potentiometric results demonstrated that the overall formation constant of the $[15\text{-MC}_{\text{Ni(II)N}(\alpha\text{-Alaha})\text{-5}]$ species increase of two orders of magnitude when in solution either K^+ or Na^+ are present. DFT calculations showed that Na^+ can fit into the $[15\text{-MC}_{\text{Ni(II)N}(\alpha\text{-Alaha})\text{-5}]$ cavity, while K^+ cannot because too large. Again, these results show the ability of large cations to act as suitable core metals, irrespective of the metal-cavity size correspondence, and demonstrate that the stability of MC can be tuned with an appropriate choice and combination of core and ring metals, and nature of the ligand.

References:

- [1] Mezei, G.; Zaleski, C. M.; Pecoraro, V. L., Structural and Functional Evolution of Metallacrowns. *Chem. Rev.* **2007**, 107, 4933-5003.
- [2] Tegoni, M.; Furlotti, M.; Tropiano, M.; Lim, C. S.; Pecoraro, V. L., Thermodynamics of Core Metal Replacement and Self-Assembly of Ca^{2+} 15-Metallacrown-5. *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, 49, 5190-5201.
- [3] Dallavalle, F.; Remelli, M.; Sansone, F.; Bacco, D.; Tegoni, M., Thermodynamics of Self-Assembly of Copper(II) 15-Metallacrown-5 of Eu(III) or Gd(III) with (*S*)- α -Alaninehydroxamic Acid in Aqueous Solution. *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, 49, 1761-1772.
- [4] Seda, S. H.; Janczak, J.; Lisowski, J., Synthesis and structural characterisation of nickel 15-metallacrown-5 complexes with lanthanide(III) and lead(II) ions: Influence of the central metal ion size on the spin state of peripheral nickel(II) ions. *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* **2006**, 9, 792-796.

Kinetics of formation of the 12-MC-4 metallacrown from (S)- α -Alanine hydroxamic acid and Copper(II) and its interaction with La(III)

Maria Rosa BECCIA,^{a)} **Tarita BIVER,**^{a)} **Begoña GARCIA,**^{b)} **José M. LEAL,**^{b)}
Maurizio REMELLI,^{c)} **Fernando SECCO,**^{a)} **Matteo TEGONI,**^{d)} **Marcella VENTURINI**^{a)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale, Università di Pisa, Via Risorgimento 35 - 56126 Pisa (Italy)*

^{b)} *Departamento de Química, Universidad de Burgos, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n - 09001 Burgos (Spain)*

^{c)} *Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Ferrara, Via Borsari 46 - 44100 Ferrara (Italy)*

^{d)} *Dipartimento di Chimica generale e inorganica, Chimica Analitica, Chimica Fisica, Università di Parma, Viale Usberti 14A - 43100 Parma (Italy)*

marosa@ns.dcci.unipi.it

Metallacrowns are a novel class of macrocyclic compounds, in which metal ions are an integral part of the macrocycle ring. [1,2] The α -aminohydroxamates, which are derivatives of hydroxamic acids with an additional amino group as a potential coordinating group, are suitable ligands for metallacrown formation. These molecules form a metallamacrocycle ring with a metal-nitrogen-oxygen backbone in the presence of Copper (II) ions. A metallacrown with a five-membered chelating ring (15-MC-5) was firstly proposed for these ligands, but in 2001 it was established that α -aminohydroxamates can form also Copper(II) 12-MC-4 complexes in solution, that contain a four-membered chelating ring and for which a non-planar and tensioned cup-like structure was suggested.[3,4]

Figure 1. Schematic structures of 12-metallacrown-4 (a) and 15-metallacrown-5 (b) for the Cu(II)/(S)- α -alaninehydroxamate. $M^{n+} = Ca^{2+}, Ln^{3+}, UO^{2+}$.

The equilibria and the kinetics of the Copper(II)/(S)- α -alaninehydroxamate 12-MC-4 (Figure 1 a) formation have been investigated by means of the stopped-flow technique, FAB-

MS and UV-Vis spectrophotometric titrations of the ligand with CuCl₂ solutions. A study of the trend of the kinetic parameters varying the pH, the ionic strength and the metal concentration has been performed, allowing an interpretation of the reaction mechanism. The reaction orders (r.o.) with respect to metal and ligand have been determined (Table 1) and their values, between 1 and 2, are in agreement with a complex reaction mechanism, that involves more than one step. The kinetic constants (k) for the metallacrown formation, measured at pH = 4.5 and T = 25°C, increase by a factor of about 50 on going from I=0.1 M to I=0.9 M (NaCl) (Table 1), revealing, according to the Debye-Hukel theory, that the rate determining step of the reaction involves ions with charges of the same sign.

Table 1. Reaction orders with respect to the metal (x) and the ligand (y) and kinetic constant (^aI=0.1 M (NaCl); ^bI=0.1 M (NaCl)) for the reaction of formation of the Copper(II)/(S)- α -alaninehydroxamate 12-MC-4.

x	y	10 ⁻⁴ k
1.4	1.3	3.9 ^a
		180 ^b

The kinetics of the of the replacement of the central copper atom by La(III) and the related conversion of Copper(II)/(S)- α -alaninehydroxamate 12-MC-4 (Figure 1 a) to 15-MC-5 (Figure 1 b) has also been studied. The obtained biphasic kinetic curves reveal the presence of two reaction steps, that can likely be ascribed to the interaction of the 12-MC-4 with La(III) (fast effect) and to the rearrangement of the building block with an expansion of the metallamacrocycle (slow effect). The influence of pH and ligand concentration on the reaction has been analysed as well.

References:

- [1] Lah M.S.; Pecoraro V.L., Isolation and Characterization of {Mn^{II} [Mn^{III} (salicylhydroximate)]₄ (acetate)₂ (DMF)₆} · 2DMF: An Inorganic Analogue of M²⁺(12-crown-4), *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1989**, 111, 7258-7259.
- [2] Lah M. S.; Kirk M. L.; Hatfield W.; Pecoraro V. L., The tetranuclear cluster Fe^{III} [Fe^{III} (salicylhydroximate) (MeOH) (acetate)]₃ is an analogue of M³⁺(9-crown-3), *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.* **1989**, 1606-1608.
- [3] Dallavalle F.; Tegoni M., Speciation and structure of copper(II) complexes with (S)-phenylalanine- and (S)-tryptophanhydroxamic acids in methanol/water solution: a combined potentiometric, spectrophotometric, CD and ESI-MS study, *Polyhedron*, **2001**, 20, 2697-2704.
- [4] Careri M.; Dallavalle F.; Tegoni M.; Zagnoni I., Pentacopper(II) 12-metallacrown-4 complexes with α - and β - aminohydroxamic acids in aqueous solution: a reinvestigation, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, **2003**, 93 (3-4), 174-180.

External and internal guest binding thermodynamics of a supramolecular host in water

Carmelo SGARLATA, ^{a)} **Giuseppe ARENA,** ^{a)} **Kenneth N. RAYMOND** ^{b)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università degli Studi di Catania, Catania, Italy*

^{b)} *Department of Chemistry, University of California, Berkeley, CA and Chemical Science Division, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Berkeley, CA*

sgarlata@unict.it

The supramolecular assembly $[\text{Ga}_4\text{L}_6]^{12-}$ (L = 1,5-bis(2,3-dihydroxybenzamido)naphthalene) has been reported to act as a chiral, nanoscale flask suitable to mediate the reactivity of encapsulated reactive guests and to carry out enzyme-like chemical transformations [1]. Moreover, the highly anionic exterior surface of the assembly imparts solubility in water and other polar solvents and affinity for the external ion-association of cationic molecules [2]. The driving forces for the external and internal guest binding are very different thus complicating the determination of the thermodynamic parameters. We have used a combination of NMR, UV-vis and isothermal titration calorimetry to definitively separate multiple guest binding to the interior and exterior of the supramolecular host and to determine the corresponding ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° values [3]. Data obtained by each independent technique measure different components of the host-guest equilibria and only when analyzed together and simultaneously a complete picture of the solution thermodynamics emerges. Striking differences between the internal and external binding of ammonium guests are found as a consequence of the high charge and hydrophilic outer space of the host contrasted by its hydrophobic inner space.

References:

- [1] Pluth, M. D.; Bergman, R. G.; Raymond, K. N., Proton-Mediated Chemistry and Catalysis in a Self-Assembled Supramolecular Host. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2009**, 42, 1650-1659.
- [2] Pluth, M. D.; Johnson, D. W.; Szigethy, G. S.; Davis, A. V.; Teat, S. J.; Oliver, A. G.; Bergman, R. G.; Raymond, K. N., Structural Consequences of Anionic Host–Cationic Guest Interactions in a Supramolecular Assembly. *Inorg. Chem.* **2009**, 48, 111–120.
- [3] Sgarlata, C.; Mugridge, J. S.; Pluth, M. D.; Tiedemann, B. E. F.; Zito, V.; Arena, G.; Raymond, K. N., External and Internal Guest Binding of a Highly Charged Supramolecular Host in Water: Deconvoluting the Very Different Thermodynamics. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, 132, 1005-1009.

DNA binding properties of ruthenium arene complex, genotoxicity and in vitro cytotoxicity

Natalia BUSTO, ^{a)} **Begoña GARCÍA,** ^{a)} **José M. LEAL,** ^{a)} **Gustavo ESPINO,** ^{a)} **Antonia JIMENEZ,** ^{a)} **Héctor LOZANO,** ^{a)} **Tarita BIVER,** ^{b)} **Célia MARTINS,** ^{c)} **Jorge F. GASPAR** ^{c)}

^{a)} *University of Burgos, Chemistry Department P. Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001Burgos*

^{b)} *University of Pisa, Dipartimento di Chimica e chimica Industriale , 35-56126 Pisa (Italy)*

^{c)} *New University of Lisbon, Genetics Department, Faculty of Medical Sciences,
1349-008 Lisbon (Portugal)*

nbusto@ubu.es

2, 4-Diamino-1,3,5-triazine derivatives have been shown to display antitumour and biological activity [1]. In this field, there is a growing interest on the synthesis of novel diamino-triazine derivatives [2] such as the 2-pydaT complex ligand used in this work. On the other hand, ruthenium complexes have attracted much attention recently due to their antitumour potential [3, 4]. In this context, arene Ru (II) complexes bearing a diamino-triazine derivative have been synthesized and characterized by Prof. Espino's group in Burgos University. One of them, depicted in figure 1, was used for DNA binding and genotoxicity studies.

Figure 1. $[\text{RuCl}(\text{p-cimeno})(\kappa^2\text{-N,N-2-pydaT})]\text{BF}_4$ referred to in the text as Ru -Cl.

To a first place, a stability study of the complex has been carried out. This compound undergoes hydrolyses both in water and in basic media to yield Ru-H₂O and Ru-OH, respectively. The two processes were detected by NMR and UV-Vis measurements. In the presence of NaCl and pH = 7.0, the Ru-Cl complex is the only species present.

To a second place, the interaction of Ru-Cl with CT-DNA was studied by a number of available techniques. The binding constants evaluated at different ionic strengths by spectrofluorometric titrations evince a notable electrostatic contribution. Spectrophotometric titrations and melting assays were also carried out. Ru-Cl showed no contribution to the thermal stabilization of the double helix. The conformational transitions of the interaction were studied by circular dichroism and viscosity experiments. The data gathered suggest that at least two different complexes are formed, depending on both the Ru-Cl and DNA concentrations ratio. The observation that the relative viscosity slightly decreased with increasing Ru-Cl amounts,

rules out intercalation as the mode of binding. These findings support the assumption that groove binding and external electrostatic binding take place as a function of the Ru-Cl / DNA ratio.

Additionally, the genotoxic activity of the Ru-Cl complex was tested in V79 cell line using the cytokinesis-block micronucleus assay, a widely applied technique for screening of chemicals. Surprisingly, the results achieved for all the doses tested suggest that Ru-Cl is by no means genotoxic under the conditions used. The in vitro cytotoxicity of the arene ruthenium complexes as well as the diamino-triazine ligands alone, characterized in V-79 cell line by the MTT cell proliferation assay with 24 hours exposure time, have discarded any cytotoxic activity.

In line with the features described of ruthenium arene and diamoni-triazine derivatives, it was thought reasonable to assume that these compounds could display cytotoxic and genotoxic activity. Also, Ru-Cl can interact with DNA outside the cell. The existence of another brown species, detected in basic media by NMR, can shed light into the absence of correlation of the DNA binding studies with the biological assays, in which it was observed that the cell media turned to brown. These findings suggest that the brown species is formed into the cell as a consequence of the Ru-Cl complex metabolization.

References:

- [1] Brzozowski, Z.; Saczewski, F.; Gdaniec, M., Synthesis, structural characterization and antitumor activity of novel 2,4-diamino-1,3,5-triazine derivatives. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* **2000**, 35, (12), 1053-1064.
- [2] Diaz-Ortiz, A.; Elguero, J.; Foces-Foces, C.; de la Hoz, A.; Moreno, A.; del Carmen Mateo, M.; Sanchez-Migallon, A.; Valiente, G., Green synthesis and self-association of 2,4-diamino-1,3,5-triazine derivatives. *New Journal of Chemistry* **2004**, 28, (8), 952-958.
- [3] Clarke, M. J., Ruthenium metallopharmaceuticals. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* **2003**, 236, (1-2), 209-233.
- [4] Han Ang, W.; Dyson, P. J., Classical and Non-Classical Ruthenium-Based Anticancer Drugs: Towards Targeted Chemotherapy. *European Journal of Inorganic Chemistry* **2006**, (20), 4003- 4018.

Mn(II) Polyaza Scorpiand-like Complexes as Superoxide Dismutase Mimics

Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA, ^{a)} Salvador BLASCO, ^{a)} M. Paz CLARES, ^{a)}
Mario INCLÁN, ^{a)} Lucas DEL CASTILLO, ^{b)} Begoña VERDEJO, ^{a)}
Conxa SORIANO, ^{b)} Antonio DOMÉNECH, ^{c)} Julio LATORRE ^{a)}

^{a)} *Departamento de Química Inorgánica, University of Valencia, Instituto de Ciencia Molecular, Paterna (Spain)*

^{b)} *Departamentos de Química Orgánica o Microbiología, University of Valencia, Facultad de Farmacia, Burjassot (Spain)*

^{c)} *Departamento de Química Analítica, University of Valencia, Facultad de Química, Burjassot (Spain)*

salvador.blasco@uv.es

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) names a family of enzymes found in living systems that play the role of speeding up dismutation of the superoxide anion (O_2^-) into hydrogen peroxide and dioxygen. Superoxide is formed as a by-product of the aerobic metabolism or in the respiratory burst as a part of the immunitary response.[1] The superoxide anion is harmful; it is involved in oxidative stress and oxidative stress-related diseases such as inflammation. Although superoxide anion dismutates spontaneously, aerobic organisms need to accelerate this process because the rate for the spontaneous dismutation is not fast enough to protect the tissues from the oxidative effects of the superoxide anion generated as by product for the aerobic metabolism.

Figure 1: MnSOD mechanism and crystal structure of a synthetic mimic for this enzyme

Synthesis of low weight, low toxic and high active SOD-like compounds is a topic of great interest for its potential use as therapeutic agents for the control of oxidative stress and control of inflammation disorders.[2] In this field, major efforts have been directed towards the mimicking of copper-based SODs following the pioneering work of Lippard and others. Less attention has been paid to other metals. Nonetheless interesting results have been obtained for manganese-based SODs. [3], indeed in the last decade many Mn-based SOD mimics have been claimed to catalyse the superoxide dismutation. Other metals such as iron or nickel among others are good candidates to catalyse the superoxide dismutation but so far there are few literature reports concerning this point.

In this communication we report the synthesis, properties and SOD-like activity for some complexes of so called scorpiand-like ligands containing Mn(II) as metallic core.[4] Their macrocyclic core is similar to the active center in native MnSOD. Their SOD-like activity has been tested by means of the McCord-Fridovich test.

References:

- [1] (a) I. Fridovich, *Science* **1978**, 201, 875-880. (b) C. Dahlgren, A. Karlson, *J. Immunol. Methods* **1999**, 232, 3-14.
- [2] (a) P. Riley, *Chem. Rev.*, **1999**, 99, 2573-2587. (b) Roland Krämer, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Eng.* **2000**, 39(24), 4469-4470.
- [3] (a) G. Kolks, C. R. Frihart, *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **1976**, 98, 5720-5721; (b) D. Salvemini, Z.-Q. Wang, *et al.*, *Science*, **1999**, 286, 304-306.
- [4] (a) M.P. Clares, S. Blasco, E. García-España, *et al.*; *Chem. Commun.*, **2011**, Advance Article (b) E. García-España, M. P. Clares, C. Soriano, S. Blasco, B. Verdejo and J. Gonzalez, Patent Application Number P20093071L.

Molecular Movement of Two Novel Scorpiand-like Ligands and its Influence on DNA Intercalation

Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA, ^{a)} Mario INCLÁN, ^{b)} M. Teresa ALBELDA, ^{a)} Juan FRÍAS ^{a)}

^{a)} University of Valencia. Supramolecular Chemistry Group, Instituto de Ciencia Molecular. Edificio de Institutos de Paterna. P.O. Box 22085. 46071 Valencia (Spain), +34963544733

^{b)} University of Valencia. Supramolecular Chemistry Group, Instituto de Ciencia Molecular. Edificio de Institutos de Paterna. P.O. Box 22085. 46071 Valencia (Spain), +34963544733.

mario.inclan@uv.es

Compounds capable of interacting with DNA are of great interest in medicinal chemistry because of the fact that they can exhibit a wide spectrum of antibacterial, antiprotozoal, antiviral, and antitumor activity [1]. Most of these ligands are based on conjugated π -electron systems which can intercalate between the base pairs of DNA [2]. In the present work, anthracene has been chosen as intercalating unit because its derivatives have received considerable attention as potential antitumor drugs [3].

Scorpiand-like ligands combine a rigid macrocycle with a flexible side chain containing extra donor atoms. This side chain can bend over the structure to coordinate a metal cation or to establish H bonds with the nitrogens from the macrocycle. In the present work we have studied this movement, driven by the pH or by the presence/absence of Cu^{2+} , and an attempt has been made to correlate this movement with the modulation of the DNA intercalation capability.

Figure 1. The two scorpiand-like ligands synthesised, and schematic DNA molecule.

With this purpose two aza scorpiand-like macrocycles have been prepared, L1 and L2 (**Figure 1**) by cyclization of tren amine with 2,6-bis(bromomethyl)pyridine. The side chain has been further functionalized with a fluorophoric anthracene group (L1), or elongated with

a propylamine chain and functionalized with an anthracene group (**L2**). Potentiometric titrations and solution studies on Cu^{2+} coordination were performed to determine the protonation and stability constants of the free ligands and the Cu^{2+} complexes. UV-Visible and fluorescence studies were also performed in order to study the motion of the side chain (**Figure 2**).

In order to study the interaction with *calif thymus* DNA, UV-Visible and fluorescence titrations were performed over the free ligands and the corresponding Cu^{2+} complexes; as well as helix melting studies, done in order to quantify the stabilization of the DNA double helix by the compounds. The circular dichroism technique gave us an insight on the conformational changes taking place on *ctDNA* upon interaction with our ligands/complexes. And the ethidium bromide displacement assays allowed us to quantify the intercalating ability of the different receptors.

All the data collected evidence substantial differences between the compound with the short side chain and the one with the elongated side chain upon interacting with *ctDNA*, which may be due to, among other factors, the conformational duality of these compounds.

Figure 2. Simulation of the pH-driven molecular movement of L1.

References:

- [1] J. Feigon, W. A. Denny, W. Leupin, D. R. Kearns. *J. Med Chem.* **1984**, 27, 450-465
- [2] A. Garas, E. Webb, V. Pillay, D. MacPhee, W. Denny, H. Zeller, R. Cotton. *Mutation Research.* **2009**, 678, 20-29
- [3] M. R. Duff, V. K. Mudhivarthi, C. V. Kumar. *The journal of physical chemistry B.* **2009**, 113(6), 1710-1721.

Small molecules that are able to induce large conformation changes in polynucleotides: the DAPI/DNA system

Tarita BIVER,^{a)} **Fernando SECCO,**^{a)} **Jacopo SPINELLI,**^{a)} **Marcella VENTURINI,**^{a)}
María del Pilar LÓPEZ CORNEJO,^{b)} **Rafael PRADO GOTOR,**^{b)} **Victoria Isabel**
MARTIN HERRERA,^{b)} **Natalia BUSTO VAZQUEZ**^{c)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale – Università di Pisa – Italy*

^{b)} *Departamento de Química Física – Universidad de Sevilla – Spain*

^{c)} *Departamento de Química Física – Universidad de Burgos – Spain*

tarita@dcci.unipi.it

Under certain conditions DNAs and RNAs can give rise to particular structures different from a typical double helix form; among them hairpins and loops, triple helices, and four-way junctions. These structures are frequently essential to let the polynucleotide exert a given function. Molecules that interfere with a structure selected among several can have fundamental (positive or negative) implications in the biochemistry of a certain process.

On this basis, our group is carrying out since some years an analysis of the ability of small molecules to stabilise, under given experimental conditions, peculiar DNAs and RNAs forms like multi-strand aggregates [1] or triple helices [2].

In this communication we will present a short overview of the results on the above topic with particular focus to the last system analysed: the DAPI/DNA system.

DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) is a fluorescent stain that is used extensively in fluorescence microscopy [3]. It was found to bind strongly to A-T rich regions in DNA, principally as a minor groove binder. On the other hand, indications on intercalation have also been found. Absorbance, fluorescence and viscosimetric titrations together with T-jump kinetic experiments have been done on the DAPI/DNA system to get new information on the very complex mode of binding of this fluorescent dye to polynucleotides. The results of these experiments will be discussed.

Figure 1: Examples of small molecules able to interfere with the presence of peculiar DNA or RNA forms: (A) proflavine; (B) coraline; (C) DAPI.

References:

- [1] Biver, T.; Ciatto, C.; Secco, F.; Venturini, M., Dye-induced aggregation of single stranded RNA: A mechanistic approach. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics* **2006**, 452, 93-101.
- [2] Biver, T.; Boggioni, A.; Garcia, B.; Leal, J. M.; Ruiz, R.; Secco, F.; Venturini, M., New aspects of the interaction of the antibiotic coralyne with RNA: coralyne induces triple helix formation in poly(A)poly(U). *Nucleic Acids Research* **2010**, 38, 1697-1710.
- [3] Kapuscinski, J., DAPI - a DNA-Specific Fluorescent-Probe. *Biotechnic & Histochemistry* **1995**, 70, 220-233.

CTAB Surfactant-Induced DNA Condensation-decondensation event at different binding ratio: A Multitechnique Study.

Pilar LÓPEZ-CORNEJO ^{a)}, **Consuelo CERRILLOS**, ^{b)} **Elia GRUESO** ^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Sevilla, C/Profesor García González, s/n, 41012, Sevilla, Spain.*

^{b)} *CITIUS (Center of Investigation, Technology and Innovation) University of Seville, Avda Reina Mercedes 4, 41012, Sevilla, Spain*
elia@us.es

The interaction between DNA and cationic surfactants below their critical micellar concentration (cmc) has received, since early times, a great interest from biomedical sciences [1], because of the need of better understanding of DNA behaviour in living cells. The transfection activity of DNA is highly dependent on the structure of DNA-vectors complexes [2]. Cationic surfactant induces coil to globular transitions of the polynucleotide. These conformational changes have been demonstrated by using different techniques, such as, fluorescence microscopy, UV spectroscopy, circular dichroism, capillarity electrophoresis and surface tension. However, few reports were found using atomic force microscopy (AFM). The elucidation of the optimal transfection efficiency for any given cell line appears to require a prior knowledge of the surfactant/DNA ratio and the physical shape and stability of the complexes. With this objective in mind, an exploration of the effects that the surfactant addition produce on the DNA structure at different [CTAB]/[DNA] binding ratio would be necessary. The CTAB/DNA interaction has been investigated by physicochemical techniques (fluorescence spectroscopy, zeta potential and hydrodynamic diameter of the CTAB/DNA complex measurements and thermal denaturation) together with structural techniques (AFM and circular dichroism). AFM has been used to obtain highly detailed topographical images obtaining structural information of the DNA/CTAB complex. Up to now, only a DNA compactation phenomena induced by long tail cationic surfactant has been reported by different authors [3, 5]. However, a decompactation process of DNA has also been observed from the AFM experiments at the highest CTAB/DNA molar ratio. These observations were consistent with others physicochemical and structural techniques. So, for example, we employed SYBR-Green I (SG) as a fluorescence intercalator to study the effect that CTAB produces on the DNA-SG complexes. The structural changes that the addition of the cationic surfactant exerts in DNA produce a change in the fluorescence emission of the probe (see Figure) reflecting its situation in the medium: released (if DNA is in a more compacted form) and entrapped (if DNA is in a more extended coil conformation). On the other hand, the formation of CTAB/DNA complexes enhances the DNA melting temperature by a few grades at the lowest CTAB/DNA molar ratios, while different melting profiles are obtained at the highest molar ratios. The zeta potential measurements show two inflexion points in the plot of the potential versus the CTAB/DNA molar ratio which can be related with different complex sizes and/or structures. The changes on positive and negative bands in the intrinsic circular

dichroism spectrum of DNA are also consistent with compaction and decompaction phenomena observed.

It is important to mention that, to the best of our knowledge, the decompaction process observed at the highest CTAB/DNA molar ratios has not previously been reported up to now. The findings described in this study show the importance that the surfactant-DNA binding ratio has in a profound study about structural changes of polymers induced by cationic surfactants.

References:

- [1] Dias, R. S.; Magno, L. M.; J. M. Valente, A.; Das, D.; Das, P. K.; Maiti, S.; Miguel, G. M; Lindman, B., Interactions between DNA and Cationic surfactants: Effect of DNA Conformation and Surfactant Headgroup. *J. Phys. Chem. B.* **2008**, 112, 14446-14452.
- [2] Koping-Hoggard, M.; Mel'nikova, Y. S.; Varum, K. M.; Lindman, B.; Artusom, P. *J. Gene. Med.* **2003**, 5, 130-141.
- [3] Marchetti, S.; Onori, G.; Cametti, C. Calorimetric and Dynamic Light-Scattering Investigation of Cationic Surfactant-DNA Complexes. *J. Phys. Chem. B.* **2006**, 110, 24761-24765.
- [4] Husale, S; Grange, W.; Karle, M.; Bürge, S.; Hegner, M. *Nucleic. Acids. Research.* **2008**, 36 (5) 1443-1449.
- [5] Bhattacharya, S.; Mandal, S. S. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta.* **1997**, 1323, 23-44.

Energetics of Heavy Metal-Thioether Interactions in Solution and Gas Phase

Elena PERALTA, ^{a)} **Andrea MELCHIOR**, ^{a)} **Claudio TAVAGNACCO**, ^{b)}
Marilena TOLAZZI, ^{a)} **Manuel VALIENTE** ^{c)}

^{a)}*Dipartimento di Chimica, Fisica e Ambiente dell'Università di Udine.*

^{b)}*Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche e Farmaceutiche dell'Università di Trieste.*

^{c)}*Departamento de Química Analítica de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.*

elena.peralta@uniud.it

Metal ion recognition is of fundamental importance to many areas of chemistry and biochemistry but the factors underlying the stability and selectivity of a given ligand/receptor are often not of straightforward interpretation. Recognition process may depend on a series of factors that include the nature of the donor atoms and their spatial arrangement, the backbone structure of the ligand and its rigidity, the eventual formation of chelate rings of variable size. In the case of macrocyclic or encapsulating receptors the ability to bind the metal ion in its preferential coordination geometry is to be taken into account to predict preferential recognition. Metal - sulphur bond is a fundamental interaction in biochemical systems and in selective separation applications for the heavy and precious metal extraction from liquid phase. For example, numerous macrocyclic structures containing sulphur donor atoms (thiols, thioethers, thioureas...) have been employed as selective extractants in a range of solvent extraction and bulk membrane transport studies[1-3].

Figure 1. Linear and macrocyclic thioethers

In this work, we present the first thermodynamic investigation concerning the complex formation by several linear and macrocyclic thioethers and the Zn(II), Cd(II), and Hg(II) ions in organic solvent. Our main aim is to test their potential as efficient complexing agents and selective extractants for environmentally important metal ions and rationalize the recognition process in a medium which has a relatively low dielectric constant and it is less structured than water. The stability constants are evaluated by potentiometry using Ag (I) as competitive ion. In the case of mercury, calorimetric titrations evidence that stability constants are extremely high, and preliminary experiments have shown that they cannot be determined by spectrophotometric titrations even in presence of a competing ion (Ag⁺) with high affinity for thioethers. For this reason, the stability constants of Hg(II) with the ligands have been determined by means of polarography [4] which has been demonstrated to be particularly suitable to study Hg(II) complexes of high stability in water and non aqueous solutions. Titration calorimetry has been used to determine the reaction enthalpy (ΔH°) and to calculate the entropic term ($T\Delta S^\circ$) allowing the definition of the picture of the complexation thermodynamics. Experimental and theoretical gas phase studies are often useful to interpret

at molecular level the thermodynamics of complex formation. Several works have been carried out in the last years to study the nature and energetics of metal binding by sulphur-containing ligands, for the importance in the biological and environmental systems, such as those of refs.[5-7]. In this framework, solution results are compared with gas-phase DFT study on the interaction of TTCN and Et₂S using the B3LYP functional (Fig. 2). Geometry optimizations were carried out in vacuum using a 6-31+G(d) basis set for all atoms except the metal ion, which was described by the quasi-relativistic Stuttgart-Dresden pseudopotential. Stationary points were characterized by vibrational mode analysis. The reliability of the results has been checked by comparing calculated structures to experimental counterparts. Metal solvation has been studied by considering the dissociation of acetonitrile molecules upon ligand coordination. We also checked the effect of introducing continuum solvent model to include the polarization due to the bulk solvent. Results clearly indicate how the observed ligand affinity is a balance of binding and solvent dissociation process.

Figure.2 Optimized structures of Hg(Et₂S)²⁺, Hg(TTCN)²⁺ and Hg(TTCN)₂²⁺ complexes in gas-phase.

- [1] Glenny M.W.; Lacombe M.; Love J.B.; Blake A.J.; Lindoy L.F.; Luckay R.C.; Gloe K.; Antonioli B., Wilson C.; Schröder M., Design and synthesis of heteroditopic aza-thioether macrocycles for metal extraction. *New J.Chem.* **2006**, 30, 1755.
- [2] *Macrocyclic Chemistry, Current Trends and Future Perspectives*, Gloe K.; Ed: Springer, New York, **2005**.
- [3] Feinerman-Melnikova M.; Lindoy L. F.; Liou S.Y.; McMurtrie J. C.; Green N. P.; Nezhadali A.; Rounaghi G.; Setzer W.N., Metal-in recognition-selective bulk membrane transport of silver(I) using thioether... *Aust.JChem.* **2004**, 57 (2), 161.
- [4] Vedernikov A. I.; Ushakov E. N.; Kuz'mina L. G.; Churakov A. V. ; Strelenko Y. A. ; Wörner M.; Braun A.M.; Howard J.A.K.; Alfimov M.W.; Gromov S.P., New dithiacrown–ether butadienyl dyes: synthesis, structure, and complex formation with heavy metal cations. *J.Phys.Org.Chem.* **2010**, 23, 195.
- [5] Belcastro M.; Marino T.; Russo N.; Sicilia E., Structure and Coordination Modes in the Interaction between Cd²⁺ and 3-Mercaptopropionic Acid, *J.Phys.Chem. A*, **2004**, 108, 8407-8410.
- [6] Niu Y.; Feng S.; Qu R.; Ding Y.; Wang D.; Wang Y., Theoretical Study on the Interaction of Sulfur- and Aminopyridine-Containing Chelating Resins With Hg(II) and Pb(II), *Int. J. Quantum.Chem.*, **2011**, 111, 991–1001.
- [7] Krupp E.M.; Milne B.F.; Mestrot A.; Mehari A.A.; Feldmann J., Investigation into mercury bound to biothiols: structural identification using ESI–ion-trap MS and introduction of a method for their HPLC separation with simultaneous detection by ICP-MS and ESI-MS, *Anal.Bioanal.Chem.*, **2008**, 390,1753–1764.

Drug Discovery: towards the identification and characterization of new lead compounds as anticancer and antiprion agents

Tiziana PIVETTA, ^{a)} **Francesco ISAIA**, ^{b)} **Matteo MANCA**, ^{c)}
Federica PILLA, ^{c)} **Alessandra PANI**, ^{c)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università degli Studi di Cagliari, ITALY*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica e Analitica, Università degli Studi di Cagliari, ITALY*

^{c)} *Scienze e Tecnologie Biomediche, Università degli Studi di Cagliari, ITALY*

tpivetta@unica.it

Copper(II) complexes with 1,10-phenantroline ligand (phen) are applied as antiproliferative agent in several tumor models [1]. Recently we synthesized a series of mixed copper(II) compounds with formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, where L represents five different substituted imidazolidine-2-thione ligands. The cytotoxicity and antiprion activity of these complexes was investigated in cultured cells of mouse neuroblastoma N2a cell lines persistently infected with the 22L strain of mouse-adapted scrapie [2]. We showed a higher cytotoxic activity of the mixed compounds with respect to the species $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH}_2)]^{2+}$, as well as a moderate effect against the generation of the scrapie-like prion protein [3]. On the basis of these promising results we started a rational design of new classes of Cu(II) complexes with the aim to identify novel lead compounds with antitumoral and/or antiprion activity. We prepared a new series of $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})(\text{L}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and studied their solution equilibria and their reaction with glutathione (GSH). In order to define the spectrum of antitumor activity and the role of the secondary L ligands, all mixed compounds were tested in several tumor-derived cell lines: haematological, carcinoma, neuroblastoma, and MDR (in particular cis-platin resistant) tumour-derived cell lines. Results will be presented and discussed. In Fig.1a is reported the spectrophotometric titration of $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})]^{2+}$ with 1-ethyl-2-imidazolidinethione, in Fig.1b is reported a kinetic experiment for the system $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH}_2)]^{2+}$ - GSH.

Fig.1. a) Titration of 0.50 mmoles of $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})]^{2+}$ with 1-ethyl-2-imidazolidinethione (25°C, 0.1M NaClO_4 , CH_3CN); **b)** Absorption vs time for the system $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ - GSH at 615 nm ($[\text{Cu}(\text{II})]=[\text{GSH}]=7.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M, pH 7 phosphate buffer)

References:

- [1] F. Carvallo-Chaigneau, C. Trejo-Solis, C. Gomez-Ruiz, E. Rodriguez-Aguilera, L. Macias-Rosales, E. Cortes-Barberena, C. Cedillo-Pelaez, I. Gracia-Mora, L. Ruiz-Azuara, V. Madrid-Marina, F. Constantino-Casas, *Biometals* 21 (2008) 17–28.
- [2] J.H. Viles, F. E. Cohen, S.B. Prusiner, D.B. Goodin, P.E. Wright, H J. Dyson, (1999) *Proc. Natl. Acad.Sci. U. S. A.* 96, 2042-2047
- [3] T. Pivetta, M. D. Cannas, F. Demartin, C. Castellano, S. Vascellari, G. Verani and F. Isaia, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2011, 105, 211-220.

A New Tripodal Hydroxypyrimidinone Sequestering Agent

Anabela CAPELO,^{a)} Laurinda AREIAS,^{a)} Sérgio MARQUES,^{b)} Lurdes GANO,^{c)} Sílvia CHAVES,^{b)} M. Alexandra ESTEVES,^{a)} M. Amélia SANTOS^{b)}

^{a)} LNEG, Unidade de Pilhas de Combustível e Hidrogénio, Estr. Paço do Lumiar, 1649-038
Lisboa, Portugal

^{b)} Centro de Química Estrutural, Instituto Superior técnico, Av. Rovisco Pais, 1049-001
Lisboa, Portugal

^{c)} Instituto Tecnológico e Nuclear, Estrada Nacional N° 10, 2686-953 Sacavém, Portugal
masantos@ist.utl.pt

Even though iron is an essential element for all living organisms, it is highly toxic when present in excess. In fact, iron levels must be strictly controlled, due to iron ability to redox cycle with consequent oxidative stress, organ failure and eventual death if no treatment is applied for excess iron removal from the body. Apart from haemoglobinopathic disorders (e.g. haemochromatosis, thalassemia), there are other diseases associated with misplaced iron in specific cells and tissues, such as cancer and neurodegenerative disorders - Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases or Friedreich's ataxia (a genetically inherited mitochondrial illness). In order to find adequate decorporating agents, several polydentate iron chelators have been developed by our group, based on 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinone units (3,4-HPs) [1], and also, more recently, on hydroxypyrimidinone chelating moieties [2]. In principle, the hexadentate iron chelators are the ideal ligands for scavenging trivalent cations, under biological concentration conditions, since 1:1 ($M^{3+}:L$) complexes are formed, thus being advantageous over bidentate chelators, not only relatively to the reduced requirement amount of administered chelating drug, but also in terms both of kinetic inertness and thermodynamics. Moreover, the coupling of hydroxypyrimidinone (HPM) groups to a anchoring scaffold to form a tripodal hexadentate chelator (I) seemed a promising strategy since, as compared to the homologous 3,4-HPs, these chelating units also demonstrated high chelating capacity for hard metal ions [2,3], but presenting better water solubility, higher acidity and lower toxicity due to the presence of an extra *N*-atom in the ring.

Herein, a hexadentate tris-hydroxypyrimidinone, derived from attaching three amino-alkyl-HPM units to nitrilopropionic acid (I), was studied in terms of iron and gallium chelating properties and also *in vivo* assayed for its capacity to remove *hard* metal ions from an animal model previously administered with gallium, through ⁶⁷Ga biodistribution. Further

analysis of solution and *in vivo* sequestering properties will be made in comparison with those of the analogous tris(3,4-HP) derivative (II) [4].

References:

- [1] Santos, M.A., Recent Developments on 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones with respect to their clinical applications. Mono and combined ligand approaches. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2008**, 252, 1213-1224.
- [2] Chaves, S.; Marques, S.; Areias, L.; Capelo, A.; Esteves, M.A.; Santos, M.A., A Tripodal Hydroxypyrimidinone-based Compound for Iron and Aluminium Decorporation. ISMEC 2010, Bilbao, Spain.
- [3] Esteves, M.A.; Cachudo, A.; Chaves, S.; Santos, M.A., New sílica-immobilized hydroxypyrimidinone as sorbent of hard metal ions from aqueous fluids. *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **2005**, 99, 1762-1768.
- [4] Chaves, S.; Marques, S.M.; Matos, A.M.F.; Nunes, A.; Gano, L.; Tuccinardi, T.; Martinelli, A.; Santos, M.A., New Tris(hydroxypyridinones) as Iron and Aluminium Sequestering Agents: Synthesis, Complexation and In Vivo Studies. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2010**, 16, 10535-10545.

The interaction of DNA with metal complexes: experimental and computational studies

Giampaolo BARONE, Angelo SPINELLO, Alessio TEREZI

*Dipartimento di Chimica “Stanislao Cannizzaro”, Università di Palermo,
Viale delle Scienze, Edificio 17, 90128 Palermo, Italy,
gbarone@unipa.it*

We have recently reported on the interaction of native calf thymus DNA with cationic first row transition metal complexes, in aqueous solutions at neutral pH, investigated by spectroscopic techniques such as circular dichroism, absorption and fluorescence in the UV-visible wavelength range [1,2]. Such techniques revealed the occurrence of essentially two kinds of molecule-DNA interaction, specifically intercalation [1] and groove binding [2]. The interaction type has been assigned by interpreting the experimental spectra on the basis of “finger print” criteria, by monitoring the shape, intensity and wavelength of the spectral bands recorded as a function of the molecule/DNA molar ratio.

Of course, such procedure cannot furnish atomic level details of the molecule-DNA interaction. For this reason we are recently making use of computational methods as supporting tool for the structural interpretation of the experimental spectra. For example, quantum chemical calculations have been employed to rationalise the electronic transitions of the absorption and emission spectra of a DNA-intercalating zinc(II) Schiff base complex [3]. Moreover, quantum chemical – molecular mechanical (QM/MM) hybrid methods have been applied to simulate the intercalative interaction of proflavine with DNA models [4].

Such computational approach has been at present extended by the use of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of the metal complex-DNA systems, by explicitly including counterions and the water solvent. The MD simulations are preliminary to the application of the QM/MM calculations and are performed i) to obtain a DNA conformation relaxed at the experimental conditions and ii) to explore a wider conformational space of the DNA-molecule system. In the present communication the first examples of the application of this combined experimental/computational approach to study the interaction of DNA with first row transition metal complexes will be shown.

References:

- [1] Terenzi, A.; Barone, G.; Silvestri, A.; Giuliani, A.M.; Ruggirello, A.; Turco Liveri, V., *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **2009**, 103, 1-9.
- [2] Terenzi, A.; Barone, G.; Palumbo Piccionello, A.; Giorgi, G.; Guarcello, A.; Portanova, P.; Calvaruso, G.; Buscemi, S.; Vivona, N.; Pace, A., *Dalton Trans.* **2010**, 39, 9140-9145.
- [3] Barone, G.; Ruggirello, A.; Silvestri, A.; Terenzi, A.; Turco Liveri, V., *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **2010**, 104, 765-773.
- [4] Ruiz, R.; García, B.; Ruisi, G.; Silvestri, A.; Barone, G., *J. Mol. Struct. (Theochem)* **2009**, 915, 86-92.

Manganese and Parkinson's Disease: new findings through a yeast protein study

Massimiliano PEANA, Maria Antonietta ZORODDU, Serenella MEDICI

a) University of Sassari, Chemistry Department, Via Vienna 2, 07100 Sassari
[*peana@uniss.it*](mailto:peana@uniss.it)

Parkinson Disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative pathology whose causes have not been yet fully clarified. For this reason it is also called an idiopathic (with no known or identifiable causes) syndrome, although some PD types can have a genetic or a post-traumatic origin, and different risk factors like exposure to some pesticides. Recently it emerged that also exposure to manganese (i.e. in welders or miners) can cause a PD-like syndrome (Parkinsonism), and a connection between genetic and environmental causes of Parkinson's disease has been discovered: a genetic interaction between two Parkinson's disease genes (alpha-synuclein and PARK9, alias ATP13A2) was found, and it was determined that the PARK9 protein can protect cells from manganese poisoning [1].

Shortly after, a study on a yeast gene, YPK9, which is 58% similar and 38% identical in its amino acid sequence to human PARK9, revealed that deletion of this gene confers sensitivity for growth for cadmium, manganese, nickel and selenium, suggesting that the YPK9 protein may play a role in the sequestration of divalent heavy metal ions [2]. In the same way, a mutation on PARK9 may expose humans to these cations, especially to manganese.

In this perspective, we have chosen short fragments of YPK9 protein that included interesting sequences for metal binding and studied their behaviour towards divalent cations such as manganese and calcium, using NMR mono- and bidimensional techniques and EPR spectroscopy. If metal binding were clearly assessed in the yeast analogue, we could get a hint of what may happen in humans. Here we would like to present our latest findings.

References:

- [1] Gitler, A.D.; Chesi, A.; Geddie, M.L.; Strathearn, K.E.; Hamamichi, S.; Hill, K.J.; Caldwell, K.A.; Caldwell, G.A.; Cooper, A.A.; Rochet, J.-C.; Lindquist, S., *Nat. Genet.* **2009**, Vol. 41, pp 308-315.
- [2] Schmidt, K.; Wolfe, D.M.; Stiller, B.; Pearce, D.A., *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Comm.* **2009**, Vol. 383, pp. 198-202.

POSTERS

Novel Sol–Gel-Derived Material as chemosensor for Cu(II) and Ni(II): Dioxo-2,3,2 Functionalized Silica

**Raffaella BIESUZ, Angelo TAGLIETTI, Yuri DIAZ-FERNANDEZ,
Giancarla ALBERTI, Giovanni EMMA, Maria Giovanna GUISO**

Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Pavia, via Taramelli 12-27100 Pavia (ITALY)
galberti@unipv.it

A novel organically modified silica material has been prepared by sol-gel processing. The material incorporates a classical ligand from coordination chemistry, dioxo-2,3,2, which was covalently bound to silica matrix by means of copolymerization of TEOS (tetraethoxysilane) and N¹,N³-bis(2-aminoethyl)-2-(3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl)malonamide, obtaining the optically transparent material Dioxo-2,3,2-FS.

The material has been characterized; in particular the acid-base properties of the Dioxo-2,3,2-FS and its binding capability toward Cu(II) and Ni(II) have been examined. The feasibility of the material as a chemical recognition phase for optical sensing of Cu(II) has also been studied.

To determine the protonation constants and the saturation capacity (mmol of active sites/g of dry material) of the Dioxo-2,3,2-FS, potentiometric acid-base titrations have been performed, at 25°C and at different ionic strength. From these experiments a capacity of 0.7 mmol/g has been obtained. The protonation constants of the active sites in the sol-gel phase were not significantly different from those reported for the Dioxo-2,3,2 in aqueous phase [1]; so that the following species distribution diagram for Dioxo 2,3,2-FS as function of pH have been obtained:

Figure 1: Species' distribution diagram for Dioxo 2,3,2-FS in function of solution pH

The study of the kinetic and thermodynamic properties of the retention of both Cu(II) and Ni(II) on the Dioxo-2,3,2-FS, have been performed by batch procedures.

Long contact time (around 18-24 hours) is needed to reach equilibrium between the sol-gel phase and the metal solution. It is important to highlight that moderate stirring conditions on a shaking plate have to be used since the fragility of the material under magnetic stirring.

The sorption profile of Cu(II) and Ni(II) on the Dioxo-2,3,2-FS have been interpreted by the formation of complexes in the solid phase with the same stoichiometry and with complexation constants in pretty good agreement with those reported in the literature for analogous Cu(II) and Ni(II) Dioxo complexes in solution [1,2].

To determine the selectivity of the Dioxo-2,3,2-FS, different tests have been performed considering solutions containing several divalent cations at different pH. The maximum retention of Cu(II) have been obtained at pH around 6; at this pH other metal ions, such as Cd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), are not sorbed at all. For Zn(II) and Pb(II) the percentage of metal sorbed at pH 6 is around 40%. This is an important result to a possible future employment of the material as a recognition phase for optical sensing of Cu(II).

Finally, fixed bed column experiments have been carried out considering multi-metal inlet solutions at pH 6. From the preliminary results, it was evident a good separation of Cu(II) from Cd(II), Co(II) and Ni(II), but for Pb(II) and Zn(II) other experiments have to be done to optimize the conditions.

References:

- [1] De Santis, G.; Fabbrizzi, L.; Manotti Lanfredi, A.M.; Pallavicini, P.; Perotti, A.; Ugozzoli, F. and Zema, M., {Cu₁₁[N,N'-bis(2-aminoethyl)-2-(2-(4-pyridyl)ethyl)malondiamido(2-)]}: A Convenient Building Block for the Construction of Supramolecular Coordination Compounds Containing Exchangeable Peripheral Cu^{II} Cations. *Inorg. Chem.* **1995**, 34(18), 4529-35.
- [2] Dacarro, G. Ricci, P., Taglietti A., Sacchi D., An Anthracene Based Photoswitchable Dioxo-Tetraaza Ligand Selective for Cu(II) and Capable of Photochemical pK_a Modulation *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2011**, 8, 1212-1218

Biosorption of Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Cu²⁺ on rice husk, thermodynamic and kinetic studies

Maria Giovanna GUISO, Giancarla ALBERTI, Maria PESAVENTO, Raffaella BIESUZ

Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Pavia, via Taramelli 12-27100 Pavia (ITALY)

maria.guiso@unipv.it

Removal of heavy metals using agricultural waste and industrial by-products has been massively explored in the last decades [1], since the low cost and large availability of these materials. It could be an alternative method to the use of commercial resins for metal sequestration; correspondingly, the employment of biosorbents in recovery or cleaning up procedures is encouraged for a reduced impact towards the environment.

Rice husk, the hard protecting covering of rice grains, is one of these materials [2] and was here studied for its absorbing properties towards some heavy metals, such as Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, and Cu²⁺. The investigation has been performed with different strategies mainly devoted to characterize the biosorbent. In particular the untreated rice husk was considered.

The relative poor resistance to mechanical stress makes not possible, with our equipment, to perform reliable acid-base titrations. The exchange capacity has been evaluated by different procedures found in literature [3] and it was found to be around 0.112(3) mmol g⁻¹ as determined by acid release.

The conditional capacity is determined by the loading curves towards the three metal ions here considered. Lead(II) is the metal ion which shows the highest affinity for the biosorbent at least for pH less than 6.

For each considered metal, kinetic studies [4] were carried out by batch experiments to determine the maximum time needed to achieved equilibrium. The kinetic of sorption follows a pseudo-second-order law, reaching the equilibrium conditions in about 6 hours for all the metals.

The exchange reactions were studied according to a well established procedure, previously employed for other biphasic systems [5].

The studies on metal uptake as a function of the pH also demonstrate that the mechanism is not limited to ion exchange and an equation is proposed to evaluate the affinity of sorption by means of the overall exchange coefficients (K_{MLn}). The value of K_{MLn} is not dependent on the composition of the solution, since the possible competitive reactions are accounted for by the reaction coefficient α_M [6]. The proton exchange coefficient is evaluated at the same time.

The competition for metal complexation by any ligand in solution is also accounted for. Apparently, the effect produced by the variation in the ionic strength can be explained only by the increasing α_M that increases with nitrate concentration.

An interesting outlook on the structure of the rice husk and nature of the metal sorption is achieved with the high definition of SEM images. As an example in Figure 1 some of these images are reported. The SEM images give an idea about the possible distribution of heavy metal ions when sorbed by the husk.

An attempt to employ the rice husk in a dynamic system is presented. The column experiment demonstrates the feasibility for an application for lead(II) recovery in a remediation contest.

Figure 1 Some SEM micrographs obtained by Evo-MA10-HR microscope: (a) global view, (b) detail of the outer surface and (c) detail of the inner surface.

References:

- [1] Febrianto, J.; Kosasih, A. N.; Sunarso, J.; Ju, Y.; Indraswati, N.; Ismadji, S., *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2009**, 162, 616–645.
- [2] Chuah, T.G.; Jumariah, A.; Azni, I.; Katayon, S.; Choong, S.Y.T.; *Desalination*. **2005**, 175, 305-316.
- [3] I. Villaescusa, N. Fiol, M. Mart´inez, N. Miralles, J. Poch, J. Serarols, *Water Res.* **2004**, 38, 992–1002.
- [4] P. Lodeiro, R. Herrero, M. E. Sastre de Vicente, *Environ. Chem.* **2006**, 3, 400–418.
- [5] G. Alberti, M. G. Guiso, R. Biesuz, *Talanta* **2009**, 79, 603–612.
- [6] A. Ringbom,; E. Still, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1972, 59, 143-156.

Study of the Reactivity of Two Polyamine-Polyether/Nitrile Receptors towards Metal Ions

Javier GARCÍA-MARTÍN, ^{a)} Paloma ARRANZ-MASCARÓS, ^{a)} M. Dolores GUTIERREZ-VALERO, ^{a)} Rafael LOPEZ-GARZÓN, ^{a)} Francisco Javier LÓPEZ-GARZÓN, ^{b)} M^a Dolores LÓPEZ-DE LA TORRE, ^{a)} Celeste GARCÍA-GALLARÍN ^{a)}

^{a)} Department of Inorganic and Organic Chemistry, University of Jaen, Campus Las Lagunillas, 23071, Jaén (Spain). ^{b)} Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Granada, 18071, Granada (Spain)

parranz@ujaen.es

Metal ions such as Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, and Mn²⁺ are spread in biological and inorganic systems playing different roles in industrial processes, agriculture, and medicine. In many cases their excessive use may determine toxicity of soils and waters, resulting in environmental damages. The use of solid supports as functionalized activated carbons (AC) can be a solution to remove metal ions from aqueous industrial effluents and wastewaters. The specific functionalization of the carbon surface becomes a main goal for the improvement of its metal-ion capture capacity; in this way, we have proposed a method consisting on the irreversible anchorage onto the carbon surface of purposely designed molecular receptors (L) [1, 2]. The irreversible character of these anchorage processes has been explained on the basis of the electronic properties of the interacting moieties [1, 3], i.e. the arene centers of the activated carbon and a pyrimidine residue present in the molecular receptor. In previous studies we have found that a hybrid carbon material (AC-L1) containing the TREN derivative function (see scheme 1) acts efficiently in the adsorption of both metal cations (Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺) [4, 5] and anions (CrO₄²⁻, SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, AsO₄³⁻ and HgCl₄²⁻) [1, 2], due to the dual character of polyamine receptors which are able, depending of their protonation state, to coordinate to metal ions or to form supramolecular assemblies with anions.

Scheme 1
P3

In continuation of our work on the preparation of specific ion receptors supported on activated carbons, herein we present the results of the interaction between two polyamine receptors, L2 and L3 (see above, scheme 1), against Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Mn^{2+} ions, by potentiometric (using KCl as electrolyte) and conductimetric measurements. This work methodology is necessary as a preliminary study to know the behavior in aqueous solution of the coordinating functions in the molecular receptor. The results obtained in the system Hg(II)/L2 and Hg(II)/L3 point out to the formation of both Hg^{2+} -receptor, and HgCl_4^{2-} -receptor species.

References:

- [1] García-Martín, J.; López-Garzón, R.; Godino-Salido, M. L.; Gutiérrez-Valero, M. D.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; Cuesta, R.; Carrasco-Marín, F. *Langmuir* **2005**, *21*, 6908-6914.
- [2] Arranz, P.; Bianchi, A.; Cuesta, R.; Giorgi, C.; Godino, M.L.; Gutiérrez, M.D.; López, R. Santiago, A., *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, *49*, 9321-9332.
- [3] Low, J. N.; López, M. D.; Arranz Mascarós, P.; Cobo Domingo, J.; Godino, M. L.; López Garzón, R.; Gutiérrez, M. D.; Melguizo, M.; Ferguson, G.; Glidewell, C. *Acta Cryst.* **2000**, *B56*, 882-892.
- [3] García-Martín, J.; López-Garzón, R.; Godino-Salido, M. L.; Cuesta-Martos, R.; Gutiérrez-Valero, M. D.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; Stoeckli-Evans, H. *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2005**, 3093-3103.
- [5] Godino-Salido, M. L.; López-Garzón, R.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; Gutiérrez-Valero, M. D.; Santiago-Medina, A.; García-Martín, J. *Polyhedron* **2009**, *28*, 3781-3787.

Studies of Metal Ion Binding of a Pyrimidine/Desferrioxamine B Conjugate as Ion Receptor

Antonio SANTIAGO-MEDINA, ^{a)} M^a Luz GODINO-SALIDO, ^{a)} Manuel MELGUIZO-GUIJARRO, ^{a)} M^a Dolores LÓPEZ DE LA TORRE, ^{a)} Manuel PÉREZ-MENDOZA, ^{b)} María DOMINGO-GARCÍA ^{b)}

^{a)} Dpto. Química Inorgánica y Orgánica. Fac. Ciencias Experimentales. Universidad de Jaén. 23071-Jaén (Spain)

^{b)} Dpto. Química Inorgánica. Fac. Ciencias. Universidad de Granada. 18071-Granada (Spain)

mlgodino@ujaen.es

The adsorption of metal ions onto activated carbon has been explained based on various mechanisms such as electrostatic attraction to the carbon surface, ion exchange and metal surface complexes formation [1]. In relation with the latter mechanism, we have reported in previous works a method to improve the metal ion adsorption capacities of activated carbons [2, 3]. This method is based on the attachment of appropriate ionic receptors on low-functionalized activated carbons. These receptors consist of an aromatic residue and a Lewis base function, both of them connected through a polymethylene fragment. The adsorption of these compounds on activated carbons, *via* irreversible π -stacking interactions between the aromatic moiety of the receptors and the arene centres of the activated carbons, generates efficient functionalization to the carbon surfaces, improving their metal ion-capture capacity.

In this context, we have synthesized a new ionic receptor (L, see scheme 1) consisting of a pyrimidine moiety, that can act as the anchoring unit to attach the receptor on the carbon surface, and a desferrioxamine B residue with excellent chelating properties [4], that can act as the specific ion receptor unit.

Scheme 1.

To get further insight into the affinity of L towards metal ions, the coordination ability of L against a series of trivalent and divalent metal cations (Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+}) has been studied by potentiometric and spectroscopic methods. We present herein the results of this study that reveal the formation of 1:1 metal/L complex species in all the studied systems and a higher affinity of L for the trivalent metal ions than for the divalent ones.

On the basis of the stability constants and the spectroscopic data, we propose that the main coordination mode for L in these metal complexes is the coordination through its chelating desferrioxamine residue, which, depending on the pH of the medium, can act as a mono, bi o trihydroxamate ligand. In spite of that, in some cases like in the Cu^{2+}/L system, the formation of binuclear species takes place. The spectroscopic data display that in these binuclear species L behaves as a bitopic ligand, coordinating to the metal cations through both its pyrimidine and its desferrioxamine moieties. Thus, the UV spectrophotometric measurements performed for a Cu^{2+}/L mixture at pH 4.5, show that an increase in the metal concentration produces significant changes in the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ bands (Figure 1) of the spectral curve. This fact highlights that L interacts with Cu^{2+} metal ions through its pyrimidine moiety, probably by the C(5)-NO and C(6)O groups in a bidentate mode [5].

Figure 1. Electronic spectra of L/Cu^{2+} mixtures with variable molar ratios values at pH 4.5

References:

- [1] Bansal, R. C.; Goyal, M.; *Activated Carbon Adsorption*. CRC Press: Boca Ratón, **2005**.
- [2] García-Martín, J.; Godino-Salido, M.L.; López-Garzón, R.; Gutiérrez-Valero M.D.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; Stoeckli-Evans, H., *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2008**,1095-1106.
- [3] Arranz, P. ; Bianchi, A.; Cuesta, R.; Giorgi, C.; Godino, M.L.; Gutiérrez, M.D.; López; R. Santiago, A., *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, 49, 9321-9332.
- [4] Enyedy, E.A.; Pócsi, I.; Farkas, E., *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* **2004**, 98, 1957-1966.
- [5] Moreno, J. M.; Arranz-Mascarós, P.; López-Garzón, R.; Gutiérrez-Valero, M. D.; Godino-Salido, M. L.; Cobo-Domingo, J., *Polyhedron* **1999**, 18, 1635-1640.

Studies of Hyperbranched Polyethyleneimine as an Efficient Anion Scavenger

Antonio PEÑAS-SANJUÁN ^{a)}, María D. GUTIÉRREZ-VALERO, ^{a)} Rafael LÓPEZ-GARZÓN, ^{a)} Antonio SANTIAGO-MEDINA, ^{a)} M. Luz GODINO-SALIDO, ^{a)} María DOMINGO-GARCÍA ^{b)}

^{a)} Department of Inorganic and Organic Chemistry, University of Jaén. Campus Las Lagunillas, 23071 Jaén (Spain)

^{b)} Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Granada. Fac. of Sciences, 18071 Granada (Spain)
mdgutie@ujaen.es

Studies on the reaction of a hyperbranched polyethyleneimine (PEI, $M_n = 600$) with a series of anions of environmental concern ($A = PO_4^{3-}$, AsO_4^{3-} , CrO_4^{2-} and $HgCl_4^{2-}$) were performed. The studies revealed that each of the functional triamine units, L, contained in the PEI macromolecules is capable to form several supramolecular complexes of 1/1 stoichiometry with the anions, A, in aqueous solutions [1]. In such 1/1 complexes the triamine units and the anions participate in the form of LH_n^{n+} ($n = 1-3$) and $AH_m^{(a-m)-}$ ($a = 2, 3; m = 0-3$), this is, at different degrees of protonation, depending on the pH of the aqueous medium (Table 1) [2].

Figure 1. Representative molecular structure of PEI / anion systems

The stability constants obtained point out the formation of very stable cation-anion complexes. The values of $\log K_{st}$ measured for the complexes with arseniate, phosphate and chromate are similar to the analogous complexes formed with a tris-(2-aminoethyl)amine (TREN) derivative, which has a triamine chelating functional unit [3]. But in the case of $HgCl_4^{2-}$ the values of $\log K_{st}$ for the complexes formed with PEI are clearly higher than those with the TREN derivative.

High values of maximum adsorption capacities, X_m , were found for the adsorption of the above mentioned anions onto a hybrid solid material obtained by grafting PEI to an activated carbon (AC). Nevertheless, the X_m values obtained do not correlate with the complexing abilities of PEI to the anions measured in the solution reactivity studies. This points out that the complexing ability of the L units is hindered when PEI is grafted onto the

AC surface. On the other hand, the similarity of the X_m values obtained for the anions (except chromate) suggests that a simple electrostatic model of interaction between the positively charged surface of the adsorbent and the charged anions operates in all the cases.

Table 2. Values of $\log K_{st}$ and X_m of anions adsorbed under AC-PEI ($T = 298,1 \text{ K}$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M KCl}$)

Anion	pH of adsorption	Specie	Log K	X_m (mmol anion/g adsorbent)
AsO_4^{3-}	6.7	$[\text{HL}(\text{HAsO}_4)]^-$	2.98(8)	0.16
PO_4^{3-}	6.7	$[\text{HL}(\text{HPO}_4)]^-$	3.12(7)	0.13
CrO_4^{2-}	5.0	$[\text{H}_2\text{L}(\text{HCrO}_4)]^+$	3.81(3)	0.55
HgCl_4^{2-}	3.0	$[\text{H}_3\text{L}(\text{HgCl}_4)]^+$	15.31(3) ^a	0.16

^a $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M KCl}$

References:

- [1] Jarvis, N.V.; Wagener, J., *Talanta* **1995**, 42, 219.
- [2] Bianchi, A.; Bowman-James, K.; García-España, E. *Supramolecular Chemistry of Anions*, Wiley-VCH: New York, **1997**.
- [3] Arranz, P.; Bianchi, A.; Cuesta, R.; Giorgi, C.; Godino, M.L.; Gutierrez, M. D.; López, R.; Santiago, A., *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, 49, 9321-9332.

Anion Binding by a Tren-based Ligand Containing a Pyrimidine Functionality

Paloma ARRANZ,^{a)} Carla Bazzicalupi,^{b)} Antonio BIANCHI,^{b)} Claudia GIORGI,^{b)}
Luz GODINO,^{a)} M. Dolores GUTIERREZ,^{a)} Rafael LOPEZ,^{a)}

^{a)} Department of Inorganic and Organic Chemistry, University of Jaen, Spain

^{b)} Department of Chemistry “Ugo Schiff”, University of Florence, Italy

antonio.bianchi@unifi.it

Anion coordination chemistry is a topic of increasing interest due to the role played by anions in both biological and abiotic systems [1,2]. In recent papers we showed that the protonated forms of the tren-based ligands HL (Figure 1) containing a pyrimidine functionality is able to bind anions of great environmental concern, such as CrO_4^{2-} , AsO_4^{2-} and HgCl_4^{2-} [3] as well as biological anions like ADP and ATP [4] in aqueous solution. This polyfunctional ligand binds anions through the formation of salt-bridge and anion- π interactions both in solution and in the solid state (Figure 2) [3]. It was shown that the ligand ability to form stable complexes with the inorganic anions is retained when HL is irreversibly adsorbed on activated carbon (AC) and the hybrid AC-HL material can be used for removal of these anions from aqueous media [3].

Figure 1: The HL ligand.

In the present work, we have extended this study to the interaction of protonated forms of HL with anions of different structures and natures, such as SeO_4^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{3-}$. The unfuctionalized tren ligand was also studied to highlight the effect brought about in anion binding by the insertion of the pyrimidine group. The study was performed by means of potentiometric (pH-metric) titration in aqueous solution affording the speciation of the complex systems and the determination of relevant stability constants. The results showed that both ligands are able to form rather stable complexes with these anions over a wide pH range. With the exception of $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, all anions form more stable complexes with HL than with tren, evidencing enhanced anion binding ability of the latter upon functionalization with the pyrimidine residue.

Preliminary studies showed that also an activated carbon functionalized with HL is able to bind these anions in aqueous media featuring possible applications of the hybrid AC-HL material in anion removal/recovering from water. The possibility of recovering $[\text{Au}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{3-}$ from water is of considerable interest for the industrial extraction of this precious metal from its ores. Indeed, thiosulfate is an alternative lixiviant to cyanide for extraction of gold. The advantage of this approach is that thiosulfate is essentially non-toxic and that ore types that are refractory to gold cyanidation can be leached by thiosulfate. The use of hybrid AC-HL materials could be a suitable technique to recover $[\text{Au}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]^{3-}$, since this complex is not adsorbed on activated carbons.

Figure 2: Crystal structure of the $[\text{H}_3\text{L}(\text{HgX}_4)]$ (X = Cl, Br) anion complexes showing salt-bridge and anion- π interactions [3].

References:

- [1] Sessler, J. L.; Gale, P. A.; Cho, W. S. *Anion Receptor Chemistry, Monographs in Supramolecular Chemistry*; RSC: Cambridge, **2006**.
- [2] *Supramolecular Chemistry of Anions*, Bianchi, A.; Bowman-James, K.; Garcia-España, E., Eds. Wiley-VCH: New York, **1997**.
- [3] Arranz, P.; Bianchi, A.; Cuesta, R.; Giorgi, C.; Godino, M. L.; Gutierrez, M. D.; Lopez, R.; Santiago, A.; *Inorg. Chem.* **2010**, 49, 9321-9332.
- [4] Arranz, M. P.; Bazzicalupi, C.; Bianchi, A.; Giorgi, C.; Godino, M. L.; Gutierrez, M. D.; Lopez, R.; Valtancoli, B. *Chem. Commun.* **2011**, 47, 2814-2816.

Gold-Copper Extraction and Separation by Micellar Enhanced Ultrafiltration

Sabriye AYDINOGLU, Tarita BIVER, Fernando SECCO, Marcella VENTURINI

*Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale, Università di Pisa. Via Risorgimento, 35.
56126 Pisa (Italy)
s.aydinoglu@ns.dcci.unipi.it*

The extraction and recovery of polluting and precious metals from waste fluids has recently gained increasing importance. We present here a study on the separation and extraction of gold(III) and copper(II) from aqueous media. The reason for choosing such a system is twofold: concerning gold, it should be noted that, besides to its main use in jewellery and investment, applications of gold are rapidly and widely expanding so that, the gold recovery from waste fluids or waste scraps is becoming important[1,2,3]. On the other hand, the risk potential of copper in the environment gains in significance due to application and special properties of copper with respect to toxicity and complexing ability with humic substances[4]. Studies on metal extraction suggest that surfactant based methodologies could be effective in the removal of these ions from waste fluids[5,6].

First the two metals have been extracted separately from solutions containing only gold and only copper using the ultrafiltration technique and employing two different micellar systems SDS (Sodium dodecyl sulphate) and DTAC (tetradodecylammonium chloride). (Table 1)

Table.1 *Extraction of Gold and separately of Copper using the SDS, and the DTAC system.*

[AuCl ₄ ⁻]	[Cu ⁺²]	[PADA]	[SDS]	[DTAC]	% EXTRACTION
0	1x10 ⁻⁴	0	0.04	0	100
0	1x10 ⁻⁴	0	0	0.04	0
1x10 ⁻⁴	0	0	0	0.04	97
1x10 ⁻⁴	0	5x10 ⁻⁶	0	0.02	100
1x10 ⁻⁴	0	0	0.04	0	24
1x10 ⁻⁴	0	5x10 ⁻⁶	0.04	0	92

The results of Table 1 show that while Cu²⁺ is 100% extracted by SDS, gold(III) needs to be complexed by PADA in order to be extracted by SDS with high yields; On the contrary, gold(III) can be directly completely extracted by DTAC without any assistance from complexing agents.

In the second part of study separation and extraction of the two metals from Au(III)/Cu(II) mixtures have been performed. The results are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The recovery studies have been performed as well.

Figure 1. The DTAC system: Percentage of retention of gold(III)-copper(II) dependence on pH; [DTAC] = 0,04M, 25 °C, [NaCl] = 0M.

Figure 2. The SDS system : Percentage of retention of gold(III)-copper(II) dependence on pH; [SDS] = 0,04M, 25 °C, [NaCl] = 0M.

Figure 1 shows that the DTAC system is able to extract gold with high yields in the presence of copper, which, on the contrary, stays in the aqueous phase, thus allowing an efficient separation. Figure 2 shows that the SDS system works in the opposite direction: about 100% of copper is extracted while gold remains in the aqueous phase.

References :

- [1] Akita S.; Yang L.; Takeuchi H., Solvent extraction of gold(III) from hydrochloric acid media by nonionic surfactants. *Hydrometallurgy* **1996**, Vol. 43, 37-46.
- [2] Pethar A.V.; Pakniar K.M., Recovery of gold from solutions using *Cladosporium cladorporreides* biomass beads. *Journal of Biotechnology* **1998**, Vol. 64, 121-136.
- [3] Hagelüken C.; Corti C.W., Recycling of gold from electronics: Cost-effective use through “Desing for Recycling”. *Gold Bulletin* **2010**, Vol 43, 209-220.
- [4] Wolf M.; Teichmann G.; Hoque E.; Szymcak W.; Schimmack W.; Copper speciation in aqueous solutions of fulvic acid and related molecular weight distributions. *Fresenius J Anal Chem* **1999**, Vol. 363, 596–599.
- [5] Akita S.; Yang L.; Takeuchi H., Micellar Enhanced Ultrafiltration of gold(III) with nonionic surfactant. *Journal of Membrane Science* **1997**, Vol. 133, 189-194.
- [6] Filippi B.R.; Scamehorn J.F.; Christian S.D.; Taylor R.W., A comparative economic analysis of copper removal from water by ligand-modified micellar-enhanced ultrafiltration and by conventional solvent extraction. *Journal of Membrane Science* **1998**, Vol. 145, 27-44.

Quantum-mechanical and spectral studies on the Thiazole Orange (TO) fluorophore: dimerisation and DNA intercalation

Alessandro BIANCARDI, Tarita BIVER, Alberto MARINI, Benedetta MENNUCCI,
Fernando SECCO

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale – Università di Pisa, Italy
ferdi@dcci.unipi.it

This communication is dedicated to the memory of Alberto Marini.

Despite the unquestionable importance of fluorescent dyes, theoretical studies, aimed to an in dept understanding of the photophysical characteristics of these molecules, are still limited [1-3]. In all cases, at the best of our knowledge, the effects of different environments have never been considered in a detailed fashion.

In this communication we present a combination of a Time-dependent Density Functional Theory (TDDFT) study of the absorbance and fluorescence emission characteristics of the cyanine thiazole orange (TO) free in solution and when intercalated in DNA with spectro-photometric and -fluorometric experiments under different conditions (temperature, concentration, solvent viscosity). Moreover, the ΔH and ΔS values for TO dimerisation are evaluated by T-jump experiments.

The comparison between experimental and calculated photo-physical properties shows that (TD)DFT approaches when combined with spectroscopic measurements represent a valid strategy not only to reproduce the experimental solvatochromic shifts, induced by both dimerisation and intercalation in the DNA, but also to rationalize quenching/enhancing of fluorescence when changing the environment conditions.

Figure 1: Emission energies of TO as a function of the dihedral angle ψ ($\phi = 10^\circ$) for the first two singlet excited states (Exc1 and Exc2) of TO in water; their oscillator strengths are also shown as open labels. For each value of ψ , all the other geometrical parameters have been optimized.

References:

- [1] Hunt, P. A.; Robb, M. A., Systematic Control of Photochemistry: The Dynamics of Photoisomerization of a Model Cyanine Dye. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2005**, 127, 5720-5726.
- [2] Silva, G. L.; Ediz, V.; Yaron, D.; Armitage, B. A., Experimental and computational investigation of unsymmetrical cyanine dyes: Understanding torsionally responsive fluorogenic dyes. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2007**, 129, 5710-5718.
- [3] Allan, C. S. M.; Lasorne, B.; Worth, G. A.; Robb, M. A., A straightforward method of analysis for direct quantum dynamics: application to the photochemistry of a model cyanine. *Journal of Physical Chemistry A* 114, 8713-8729.

Studies on Platinum(II) and Palladium(II) binding to PADA in SDS micellar medium: a kinetic method for metal ions separation and recovery

Tarita BIVER, Clara PAOLETTI, Fernando SECCO, Marcella VENTURINI

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale – Università di Pisa, Italy
marcella@dcci.unipi.it

Selective separation and recovery of metal-ions is a subject of importance both from an industrial and an environmental point of view. In particular, the increasing prices of the platinum group metals has promoted growing interest in their recovery. The replacement of the traditional organic phase by pseudo-phases built up with surfactants seems to offer an interesting and promising alternative to classical solvent extraction [1-3]. Separation of the micellar pseudo-phase from the aqueous medium can be then achieved by means of ultrafiltration techniques.

In this communication we present the results of a study devoted to the selective separation of platinum(II) (in the PtCl_4^{2-} form) from palladium(II) (in the PdCl_4^{2-} form) using the ligand PADA (pyridine-2-azo-*p*-dimethylaniline) in a micellar SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate) pseudo-phase. The separation is based on the much higher rate of Pd(II) binding to PADA, so that this metal is transported on the micelle while Pt(II) stays in the aqueous phase. First of all the kinetic features of formation of the Pt(II)/PADA and Pd(II)/PADA complexes were analysed. It was actually found that the latter complex do form faster with respect to the former. Therefore, the Pd(II)/PADA complex can be retained by the SDS micelles grace to hydrophobic interactions, whereas PtCl_4^{2-} is electrostatically repulsed by the negatively charged micelles. Ultrafiltration experiments show that the LM-MEUF (ligand modified – micellar enhanced ultrafiltration) approach is able indeed to separate Pt(II) from Pd(II) with promising results. Stripping data are also collected that provide information on the optimisation of Pd(II) recovery from the micellar pseudo-phase by using different acids or salts.

Figure 1: LM-MEUF separation of Pt(II) from Pd(II): the Pd(II)/PADA hydrophobic complex is rapidly formed and enters the micelle, whereas PtCl_4^{2-} is electrostatically repulsed and will not be retained upon ultrafiltration.

References:

- [1] Ghezzi, L.; Monteleone, G.; Robinson, B.; Secco, F.; Tine, M. R.; Venturini, M., Metal extraction in water/micelle systems: Complex formation, stripping and recovery of Cd(II). *Colloids and Surfaces A-Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2008**, 317, 717-721.
- [2] Ghezzi, L.; Robinson, B. H.; Secco, F.; Tine, M. R.; Venturini, M., Removal and recovery of palladium(II) ions from water using micellar-enhanced ultrafiltration with a cationic surfactant. *Colloids and Surfaces A-Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2008**, 329, 12-17.
- [3] Monteleone, G.; Morrioni, L.; Robinson, B.; Tine, M. R.; Venturini, M.; Secco, F., Metal ion extraction in surfactant solution: Ni²⁺(aq) and Cd²⁺(aq) with the ligands PADA and PAR in SDS micellar systems. *Colloids and Surfaces A-Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **2004**, 243, 23-31.

Fluorescence study of the conformational transitions in Mg²⁺ dependent RNA-ligating 7S11 Deoxyribozyme

Elisa TURRIANI,^{a,b)} Claudia HÖBARTNER,^{b)} Thomas M. JOVIN^{b)}

^{a)}Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa, Piazza dei Cavalieri 7, 56126 Pisa, Italy, and
Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale, via Risorgimento 35, 56126 Pisa, Italy

^{b)}Max Planck Institute for Biophysical Chemistry, Am Faßberg 11, 37077 Göttingen,
Germany

elisa.turriani@sns.it

The ability of DNA to function as a catalyst is well established and many artificial deoxyribozymes (DNAzymes) have been created in the laboratory via *in vitro* selection that can catalyze either the cleavage or the ligation of RNA strands [1]. The 7S11 DNAzyme under investigation in this project catalyzes the formation of a 2'-5' branched-RNA (Fig. 1a). The reaction is Mg²⁺-dependent and proceeds via the nucleophilic attack of a specific internal adenosine 2'OH group of one substrate RNA strand (L-RNA) on the 5'-triphosphate group of the second substrate RNA strand (R-RNA), leading to the release of PP_i [2] (Fig. 2a). The active structure of the DNA:RNA complex is a three helix junction [3] which presents four characteristic paired regions (P1-P4) (Fig. 1a,b). Although 7S11 has been extensively studied, the detailed reaction mechanism and kinetics, structural rearrangements, and Mg²⁺ binding sites are as yet unknown. The aim of this study is to investigate these aspects using steady-state and time-resolved (stopped-flow, lifetime) fluorescence spectroscopy.

In order to use Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) as a tool for the study, two fluorescent probes were introduced into the RNA strands (Fig. 2a). To provide the donor for the energy transfer, the branch site adenosine on the L-RNA was substituted with the fluorescent analog 2-aminopurine (AP) [4]. The second probe was introduced into the R-RNA in the γ position of a 5'-thiotriphosphate to serve as an acceptor for energy transfer from AP. Monobromobimane (B), a small thiol reactive dye, proved to be ideal for this task. The occurrence of FRET upon addition of Mg²⁺ was confirmed by quenching of the donor, sensitized emission of the acceptor (Fig. 2b,c), and changes in time resolved fluorescence and polarization. The roles of the loops and of the paired regions in the structural rearrangement and catalysis were studied synthesizing mutated analogs of the original 7S11 and of the L and E substrates.

Figure 1. *a*, Deoxyribozyme 7S11 with its RNA substrates[2]. *b*, Schematic description of the three helix junction structure that brings the nucleophile and the electrophile into close proximity [3].

The conformational change(s) induced by the addition of Mg^{2+} resulted in an enhancement of the FRET efficiency, confirming the role of the divalent cation in forming a trimolecular complex in which the branch-site adenosine and the triphosphate are closer together. The bimane probe also provides distinctive signals upon formation of the enzyme-substrate complex, interaction with Mg^{2+} and release of the labeled pyrophosphate product. It can thus be used for the continuous monitoring of the ligation reaction via the changes in its fluorescence intensity and anisotropy, and probably will constitute a useful tool for the general study of the reactivity of DNAzymes.

Figure 2. *a*, Deoxyribozyme 7S11 with its RNA substrates and the fluorescent probes. *b*, FRET abrogation during the reaction catalyzed by 7S11: RNA ligation to form 2'-5' branched bRNA in the presence of the fluorescent probes (structures). *c*, Emission spectra of a sample containing AP and B. Sensitized emission of the acceptor and quenching of the donor upon addition of Mg^{2+} (black, $[Mg^{2+}]$ 0 mM; red, $[Mg^{2+}]$ 40 mM)

References:

- [1] Silverman, S. K.; Baum, D. A.; Use of Deoxyribozymes in RNA Research. *Methods Enzymol.* **2009**, 469, 95-117.
- [2] Coppins, R. L.; Silverman, S. K.; A DNA Enzyme that Mimics the First Step of RNA Splicing. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **2004**, 11 (3), 270-274.
- [3] Coppins, R. L.; Silverman, S. K.; A Deoxyribozyme That Forms a Three-Helix-Junction Complex with its RNA Substrates and has General RNA Branch-Forming Activity. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, 127(9), 2900-2907.
- [4] Turriani, E.; Secco, F.; Höbartner, C.; Jovin, T. M.; Mg^{2+} -dependent Conformational Transitions of 7S11 Deoxyribozyme by Steady State Fluorescence and Stopped-flow Kinetics. XIX International Round Table on Nucleosides, Nucleotides and Nucleic Acids, IRT 2010, (research abstract in Proceedings). **2010**, 597-598.

Characterization of the interaction between Poly(rA)·Poly(rU) and Thionine. A thermodynamic approach.

**Begoña GARCÍA, José M. LEAL, Natalia BUSTO, Héctor LOZANO,
Antonia JIMENEZ**

*Universidad de Burgos, Departamento de Química, 09001 Burgos, Spain,
begar@ubu.es*

Thionine is a fully planar tricyclic cationic acridine derivative with two amino groups at the C3 and C7 sites (Figure 1). The interaction of thionine with double stranded DNA occurs via intercalation [1]. Furthermore, thionine is able to photoinactivate blade blaster cells and bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [2].

Acridines are able to interact with double and triple stranded polynucleotides. We have studied the nature of the interaction of thionine with the synthetic nucleotide Poly(rA)-Poly(rU) at pH = 7.0, 25°C and the dependence with the ionic strength at I = 0.01, 0.10 and 1.0 M using various thermodynamic techniques such as absorbance and fluorescence titrations, viscometry, circular dichroism, melting studies and differential scanning calorimeter experiments.

Figure 1: Thionine (3,7-diamino-5-phenothiazinium)

The data obtained from the titrations performed at I = 0.01, 0.10 and 1.0 M reveal an interaction between thionine and the double stranded RNA showing a decrease in the signal intensity of both absorbance and fluorescence studies with the increase of the C_D/C_P ratio. Likewise, the circular dichroism experiments showed conformational changes in the RNA structure which were strongly dependent on the ionic strength of the system. Finally, the relative viscosity (η/η_0) increased with the C_D/C_P ratio, causing the RNA elongation and suggesting that thionine interacts with RNA via intercalation. These observations are in agreement with the melting experiments, where T_m increased as the C_D/C_P ratio was raised, showing the stabilization of the double stranded RNA upon interaction with thionine.

References:

- [1] Paul, P.; Kumar, G. S., Toxic interaction of thionine to deoxyribonucleic acids: Elucidation of the sequence specificity of binding with polynucleotides. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 184, (1-3), 620-626.
- [2] Tuite, E. M.; Kelly, J. M., New trends in photobiology: Photochemical interactions of methylene blue and analogues with DNA and other biological substrates. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology* **1993**, 21, (2-3), 103-124.

Thermodynamic study of the interaction of 6-Anthracen-9-yl-[1,3,5] triazine-2,4-diamine with DNA

José M. LEAL, Begoña GARCÍA, Antonia JIMENEZ, Natalia BUSTO,
Héctor LOZANO, Gustavo ESPINO

University of Burgos, Chemistry Department, Pza. Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001 Burgos
jmleal@ubu.es

Some diamino 1,3,5-triazine compounds have been described as potential chemotherapeutic agents for leukaemia, melanoma and breast cancer because of their growth inhibition activity[1]. Their interaction with DNA proceeds by the ligand intercalation into the base-pairs of the polynucleotide[2].

The fluorescent 6-Anthracen-9-yl-[1,3,5] triazine- 2,4-diamine here depicted, was kindly provided by Prof. G. Espino (University of Burgos). The majority of the anthracen derivatives studied in the bibliography act out as intercalators, except a couple of exceptions that work as groove binders [3].

6-Anthracen-9-yl-[1,3,5]triazine-2,4-diamine

The interaction of this compound with CT-DNA was studied by spectrofluorimetric and circular dichroism titrations at 0.01, 0.10 and 1.0 M ionic strength, pH = 7.0 and 25 °C. No ionic strength effects both in the binding mode and in the extent of binding were observed. A differential scanning calorimetry study was also performed at I = 0.10 M. No thermal stabilization of CT-DNA was observed in the presence of 6-Anthracen-9-yl-[1,3,5] triazine-2,4-diamine. The sets of data gathered suggest groove binding as the mode of interaction of this compound with CT-DNA. Additionally, this anthracen derivative has been shown to self aggregate, the aggregation being favoured by the interaction with DNA.

References:

- [1] Saczewski, F.; Bulakowska, A., Synthesis, structure and anticancer activity of novel alkenyl-1,3,5-triazine derivatives. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* **2006**, 41, (5), 611-615.
- [2] Avendaño, C.; Menéndez, J. C., *Medicinal Chemistry of Anticancer Drugs* Elsevier: 2008.
- [3] Tan, W. B.; Bhambhani, A.; Duff, M. R.; Rodger, A.; Kumar, C. V., Spectroscopic Identification of Binding Modes of Anthracene Probes and DNA Sequence Recognition. *Photochemistry and Photobiology* **2006**, 82, (1), 20-30.

A spectroscopic study of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with hydroxylated carboxylic ligands in aqueous solution

Silvia BERTO, ^{a)} **Pier Giuseppe DANIELE,** ^{a)} **Enrico PRENESTI** ^{a)}, **Enzo LAURENTI** ^{b)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Analitica dell'Università, Via Pietro Giuria 5, 10125 Turin, Italy*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Chimica IFM dell'Università, Via Pietro Giuria 7, 10125 Turin, Italy*
silvia.berto@unito.it

This study is an enhancement of previous investigations on the vanadyl chemistry in water solution [1, 2] where our attention is addressed to the study of coordination compounds between vanadyl oxocation and carboxylic acids and, in particular, to their structural description by means of spectroscopic characterization of complexes. We report the investigation on coordination compounds of vanadyl ion with citric, D(+)-*threo*-isocitric, L-malic and L-tartaric acids in aqueous solution. The four acids were chosen in order to characterize the role of hydroxo groups and the effect of their position in the ligand molecule on the vanadyl coordination capability and on the structure of complexes. The different binary systems have been studied by potentiometric and spectroscopic techniques at $t = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $I = 0.1\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Electronic paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy (EPR) at room temperature and molecular absorption spectrophotometry were employed. A speciation model was proposed for all the metal/ligand systems from potentiometric data. Moreover, the joint elaboration of potentiometric and spectroscopic data obtained on the vanadyl-ligand containing solutions allowed us to strengthen the speciation model proposed and to achieve a deeper knowledge of the structure of complexes in solution. The interpretation of spectrophotometric and EPR data by the application of solution speciation models allowed us to calculate the visible absorption spectra and the values of theoretical isotropic hyperfine coupling constant A^0 of each complex species.

For all the systems studied the chemical models—assume the formation of monomeric species MLH_r and binuclear species M_2LH_r . All the ligands form ML complex, except L-tartaric acid, and dimeric complexes with general formula $M_2L_2H_r$. The dimeric complexes of citric, D(+)-*threo*-isocitric and L-malic acids are EPR silent, while the dimeric species of L-tartaric acid presents a characteristic EPR signal. These results suggest a magnetic coupling of two metal center due to the formation of an alcoholate-bridged dinuclear structure, but different complex structures for tartrate dimers with respect to the others hydroxylated ligands.

The spectrophotometric study of metal-ligand systems provide interesting information about the structure of complexes. The spectrophotometric behaviour of citrate and L-tartrate systems differs significantly from that of D(+)-*threo*-isocitric and L-malic acids. For both the ligands the two principal absorption bands (765 and 635 nm for aquoion) present an opposite shift suggesting an increase of tetragonal distortion for the dimeric species $M_2L_2H_r$. The spectra of dimeric complexes of L-tartrate, moreover, show the electronic transition band at $\sim 395\text{ nm}$, often hidden under a charge transfer band.

The results acquired are in accordance with the literature [3-7] and highlight the weight of the location of alcoholic group in relation to the coordination capability and the complex structure.

References:

- [1] Berto, S.; Daniele, P. G.; Foti, C.; Prenesti, E.; Sammartano, S., Interaction of oxovanadium(IV) with carboxylic ligands in aqueous solution: A thermodynamic and visible spectrophotometric study. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2008**, 142, 57-63.
- [2] Berto, S.; Daniele, P. G.; Prenesti, E.; Laurenti, E., Interaction of oxovanadium(IV) with tricarboxylic ligands in aqueous solution: A thermodynamic and spectroscopic study. *Inorganica Chimica Acta* **2010**, 363, 3469–3476.
- [3] Tsaramyrsi, M., Kaliva, M., Salifoglou, A., Raptopoulou, C. P., Terzis, A., Tangoulis, V., Giapintzakis, J., Vanadium(IV)-citrate complex interconversions in aqueous solutions. A pH-dependent synthetic, structural, spectroscopic, and magnetic study, *Inorganic Chemistry* **2001**, 40, 5772-5779.
- [4] Velayutham, M., Varghese, B., Subramanian, S., Magneto-structural correlation studies of a ferromagnetically coupled dinuclear vanadium(IV) complex. Single-crystal EPR study, *Inorganic Chemistry* **1998**, 37, 1336-1340.
- [5] Jørgensen, C. K.; Comparative ligand field studies. IV. Vanadium(IV), Titanium(III), Molybdenum(V) and other systems with one d-electron, *Acta Chimica Scandinavica* **1957**, 11, 73-85.
- [6] Tapscott, R. E., Belford, R. L., Oxovanadium(IV) tartrates. Characterization and evidence for intermetallic coupling un anionic species, *Inorganic Chemistry* **1967**, 6, 735-743.
- [7] Lodyga-Chruscinska, E., Sanna, D., Garibba, E., Micera, G., Potentiometric, spectroscopic, electrochemical and DFT characterization of oxovanadium(IV) complexes formed by citrate and tartrates in aqueous solution at high ligand to metal molar ratios: the effects of the trigonal bipyramidal distortion in bis-chelated species and biological implications, *Dalton Transactions* **2008**, 4903-4916

Analytical determination of total acidity in some Sardinian wines: evaluation of the contribute of different acids.

Valeria Marina NURCHI, Guido CRISPONI, Miriam CRESPO-ALONSO,
Leonardo TOSO, Delara MANSOORI

^{a)} Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università di Cagliari, Cittadella Universitaria, 09042
 Monserrato - Cagliari
l.toso@unica.it

The acidity is one of the main factors that contributes to the taste and to the armonic equilibrium of wines [1]. Disregarding the so called volatile acidity, which is a negative property due to acetic acid, the total wine acidity is determined by a mixture of variously protonated polyprotic acids, above all tartaric (2/6 g/L), malic (0/5 g/L), lactic (1/5 g/L), succinic (0.6/1.2 g/L) and citric (0/0.7 g/L) acids. Each of these acids gives its own contribute to the quality of wine in terms of sourness, smoothness etc.

The quantification and the speciation of these acids is therefore of great concern at different stages of the life of wines, starting from must and from early fermented wine, in order to plan in a correct way the enological treatments, to the final product for evaluating one of the principal quality parameters.

In this work we would present a preliminary evaluation of the possibility of obtaining, with the use of proper calculation methods, the content and the speciation of the principal acids. This will be accomplished on the basis of a simple pH-metric titration and of the knowledge of the protonation constants of the evaluated acids. In this respect it has to be taken into account that the evaluation of the matrix effects on the protonation constants is not a simple task, having each single wine its own composition in term of content in sugar, alcohol, and minor components. We will here present the evaluation of the protonation constants of tartaric, malic, lactic, succinic and citric acids as a function of alcohol and sugar content, and the results obtained on some white and red Sardinian wines.

References:

- [1] Prenesti, E.; Toso, S.; Daniele, P.G.; Zelano, V., Ginepro, M., Acid-base chemistry of red wine: analytical multi-technique characterization and equilibrium-based chemical modelling. *Analytica Chimica Acta* **2004**, 507, 263-273.

A new hydroxypyrrone chelating agent for Fe^{III} and Al^{III}: a structural and equilibrium study.

Miriam CRESPO-ALONSO,^{a)} **Guido CRISPONI,**^{a)} **Alicia DOMÍNGUEZ-MARTÍN,**^{b)}
Josefa M. GONZÁLEZ-PÉREZ,^{b)} **Juan NICLÓS-GUTIÉRREZ,**^{b)} **Leonardo TOSO,**^{a)}
Valeria M. NURCHI^{a)}

^{a)} Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Cagliari, 09042 Monserrato,
Cagliari (Italy), +39 0706754471

^{b)} Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Granada,
Campus Cartuja, 18071 Granada (Spain).

m.crespo@unica.it

We have studied the complexation equilibria of the trivalent metal ions Fe^{III} and Al^{III} with several derivatives of kojic acid (5-hydroxy-2-hydroxymethyl-4-pyrone) [1,2] with the aim of designing new chelators for the clinical treatment of various diseases involving these metal ions. The 3-hydroxy-4-pyrone ligands constitute an important class of biologically active compounds. The exocyclic keto group and the ortho oxyanion derived from the hydroxyl group can efficiently bind a variety of di- and trivalent metal ions by forming a five-membered chelate ring since charge delocalization is possible within the heterocyclic ring [3].

One of the kojic acid derivatives 2-2'-methanediylbis[3-hydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)-4H-pyran-4-one] (H₂MbK), found *in vitro* as a suitable ligand for the mobilization of ferritin-bound iron from mammalian cells[4], was assessed, using a hepatocyte cell system assay, to satisfy simultaneously cellular iron uptake and toxicity requirements. The very favourable pFe value obtained for this ligand [1] encouraged us to examine other, new kojic acid derivatives in which different substituents are placed on the linker between the two kojic units [2].

In this Symposium we present the synthesis and the equilibrium studies of a new derivative, 2-2'-ethanediylbis[3-hydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)-4H-pyran-4-one] (H₂EbK). The crystal structure of this ligand was determined by the C.I.C of the University of Granada (Spain). The determination of stability constants was performed by combined potentiometric-spectrophotometric techniques (Fe^{III} complex formation and protonation equilibria) and potentiometry (Al^{III} complex formation equilibria).

Figure: Crystal structure of H₂EbK

It is well known that the ring nitrogen atom confers to hydroxypyridinones better chelating capacity compared to hydroxypyrones which have an oxygen atom in the ring [5,6]. We have therefore embarked on a program of synthesis, characterization and complexation studies of compounds related to kojic acid with a nitrogen atom in place of the ring oxygen atom. These new molecules will combine the advantageous chelating capacity of hydroxypyridinones with the favourable structure of kojic acid derivatives.

References:

- [1] Nurchi, V.M.; Crisponi, G.; Lachowicz, J.I.; Murgia, S.; Pivetta, T.; Remelli, M.; Rescigno, A.; Niclòs-Gutiérrez, J.; González-Pérez, J.M.; Domínguez-Martin, A.; Castiñeiras, A.; Szewczuk, Z., Iron(III) and aluminum(III) complexes with hydroxypyrene ligands aimed to design kojic acid derivatives with new perspectives. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* **2010**, 104, 560-569.
- [2] Nurchi, V.M.; Crisponi, G.; Lachowicz, J.I.; Murgia S.; Arca, M.; Pintus, A.; Gans, P.; Niclòs-Gutiérrez, J.; Domínguez-Martin, A.; Castiñeiras, A.; Remelli, M.; Szewczuk, Z.; Lis, T., New kojic acid derivatives aimed for iron(III) and aluminium(III) chelation. *Dalton Trans*; DOI 10.1039/C1DT00005E
- [3] Thomson, K.H.; Barte, C. A.; Orvig, C., Metal complexes of maltol and close analogues in medicinal inorganic. *Chemical Society Reviews*, **2006**, 35, 545-556.
- [4] Porter, J. B.; Gyparak, M.; Huehns, E.R.; Hider, R.C., The relationship between lipophilicity of hydroxypyrid-4-one iron chelators and cellular iron mobilization, using an hepatocyte culture model. *Biochemical Society Transactions* **1986**, 14, 1180.
- [5] Nurchi, V.M.; Crisponi, G.; Pivetta, T.; Donatoni, M.; Remelli, M., Potentiometric, spectrophotometric and calorimetric study on iron(III) and copper(II) complexes with 1,2-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-4-pyridinone. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* **2008**, 102 (4), 684-692.
- [6] Crisponi, G.; Nurchi, V.M.; Pivetta, T.; Galezowska, J.; Gumienna-Kontecka, E.; Bailly, T.; Burgada, R.; Kozłowski, H., Towards a new attenuating compound: a potentiometric, spectrophotometric and NMR equilibrium study on Fe(III), Al(III) and a new tetradentate mixed bisphosphonate-hydroxypyridinonate ligand. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* **2008**, 102 (7), 1486-1494.

Figure. Complex molecule of $[\text{Cu}_2(1,4\text{-CDTA})(\text{Hicyt})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Bond distances: Cu(1)-O(11) 1.949(2), Cu(1)-O(21) 1.955(2), Cu(1)-N(10) 2.023(2), Cu(1)-N(3) 2.031(2), Cu(1)-O(1) 2.337(2), Cu(1)-O(4) 2.693(2) Å. Non-coordinated water omitted for clarity.

B) To display an asymmetric N3,O4-H(N1)icyt chelating role. That occurs in compounds $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\alpha\text{-ala-gly})(\text{Hicyt})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [XOTXOT] (Cu-N3 2.003 or 2.008 Å and Cu-O4 2.638 or 2.702 Å respectively) and $\{[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{L-tyr-gly})(\text{Hicyt})]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (Cu-N3 2.000 Å and Cu-O4 2.747 Å) [XOTXUZ], where $\Sigma_{\text{vdw radii}} = 1.50 (\text{O}) + 1.40 (\text{Cu}) = 2.90 \text{ \AA}$.

C) The asymmetric N3,O4-H(N1)icyt chelating role has been also described in cooperation to an intra-molecular interligand interaction (Hicyt)N2-H \cdots O(apical, aqua) (2.847 Å, 174.46°) in the compound $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{gly-gly})(\text{Hicyt})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ [PULPOB] (Cu-N3 1.949 Å, Cu-O4 2.747 Å).

D) Alternatively, the use of the H(N3)icyt tautomer can favour the formation of a metal-N1 coordination bond that can cooperate with a N2-H \cdots A(acceptor atom) interaction (without implication of the exocyclic O4 atom in metal binding). This metal binding pattern has been referred to the binuclear compound $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{N-sal-ser})(\mu_2\text{N1},\text{N2-H}(\text{N3})\text{icyt})_2]$ [GELGAK]. In this latter case the exocyclic amino group -N2H₂ is involved in two complementary roles, metal coordination and N2-H \cdots O intra-molecular interligand interaction (2.631 Å, 141.10°). Hence, the tautomer H(N3)icyt displays a $\mu_2\text{-N1},\text{N2}$ -bridging role where the Cu-N1 bond is reinforced by the referred H-bond.

E) The tautomer H(N3)icyt also plays an unidentate role in $\text{trans-}[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{en})_2(\text{H}(\text{N3})\text{icyt})_2][\text{B}(\text{Ph})_3]$ [NOKBAQ] where each Ni^{II}-O4 coordination bond cooperates with an (en)N-H \cdots N1 intra-molecular interaction (2.990 Å, 127.74°).

In *conclusion*, H(N1)icyt in the novel compound displays the same molecular recognition pattern previously reported for PULPOB, by cooperation of the asymmetric N3,O4-chelating role and one N2-H \cdots O(aqua) intra-molecular interaction. That dictates the nearly perpendicular orientation of the Hicyt plane respect to the mean plane defined by the four closest donor atoms in the elongated octahedral copper(II) coordination polyhedron.

Reference:

- [1] Dracinsky, M.; Jansa, P.; Ahonen, K.; Budesinsky, M., Tautomerism and the protonation/deprotonation of Isocytosine in liquid- ad solid-state studied by NMR spectroscopy and theoretical calculations. *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2011**, (8), 1544-1551.

Evaluation of hydroxypyridinecarboxylic acids as new possible chelating agents for Iron(III) and Aluminium(III)

Annalisa DEAN,^{a)} **Maria Grazia FERLIN,**^{b)} **Denis BADOCCO,**^{a)}
Paolo PASTORE,^{a)} **Ignazio CASTAGLIUOLO,**^{c)} **Alfonso VENZO,**^{d)}
Robert A. YOKEL,^{e)} **Valerio DI MARCO**^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Padova, via Marzolo 1,
35131 Padova (Italy)*

^{b)} *Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Padova, via Marzolo 5,
35131 Padova (Italy).*

^{c)} *Department of Histology, Microbiology and Medical Biotechnologies,
University of Padova, via Gabelli 63, 35121, Padova, Italy*

^{d)} *C.N.R. Institute of Sciences and Molecular Technologies, via Marzolo 1,
35131 Padova (Italy)*

^{e)} *Pharmaceutical Sciences Department, 511C Pharmacy Building, University of Kentucky
Academic Medical Center, Rose Street, Lexington, KY 40536-0082 (USA)*

annalisa.dean@unipd.it

Chelation therapy is the most efficient therapeutic approach for metal ion overload [1]. The chelators presently used for Fe(III) and Al(III) overload therapies, desferal and deferiprone, have several drawbacks. A multidisciplinary search for alternative molecules is being actively pursued [1, 5] We proposed some hydroxypyridinecarboxylic acids (HP) ([6,7] and references therein) as potential chelating agents for Al, as they have several requirements for an ideal chelator [3]. They have negligible or low toxicity, high stability of the Fe(III) and Al(III) complexes at physiological conditions, low affinity towards essential metal ions to reduce undesired metal depletion, low molecular mass (less than 400 Dalton) to allow oral administration, no redox activity *in vivo*, and their Fe(III) and Al(III) complex at physiological pH are hydrophilic so to enhance metal ion urinary elimination. In the present poster, the following results of several HP derivatives will be reported: Fe(III)/HP and Al(III)/HP solution chemistry, electrochemistry, cytotoxicity, octanol/water partitioning, and chelation efficiency.

References

- [1] C. Hershko, *Sem. Hematol.* **2005**, *42*, Issue 2, Supplement 1
- [2] M. J. Cunningham, *Curr. Opin. Hematol.*, **2005**, *12*, 129.
- [3] R. C. Hider, *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.*, **2005**, *1054*, 141.
- [4] R. A. Yokel, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, **2002**, *228*, 97.
- [5] G. J. Kontoghiorghes, *Drugs Fut.*, **2005**, *30*, 1241.
- [6] A. Dean, *Dalton Transactions*, **2008**, 1689
- [7] A. Dean, *Dalton Transactions*, **2009**, 1815

Complexation of thorium(IV) with sulfate at variable temperatures. A microcalorimetric study from 10 to 70 °C

**Plinio DI BERNARDO, ^{a)} Pier Luigi ZANONATO, ^{a)} Francesco ENDRIZZI, ^{a)}
Arturo BISMONDO, ^{b)} Linfeng RAO, ^{c)}**

^{a)}*Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche dell'Università di Padova*

^{b)}*Istituto di Chimica Inorganica e delle Superfici del CNR (Padova)*

^{c)}*Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory*

plinio.dibernardo@unipd.it

Thorium, a member of the actinide family, has a relatively high natural abundance: about 6000 ppb, three times higher than that of uranium [1]. Like uranium, thorium is also a source of nuclear energy that could be generated in nuclear fuel cycles based on thorium. However, in contrast to the relatively large number of nuclear plants based on uranium, the use of thorium in nuclear fuel cycle has been very limited [2]. Due to the increasingly large demand for nuclear energy and the inherently safer and cleaner nature of the thorium-based fuel cycles than those based on enriched uranium [3, 9], the use of thorium in advanced nuclear systems has recently become a subject of interest. Fundamental understanding of the behavior of thorium in the used fuel reprocessing and in environmental transport is critically important to the development of safe and sustainable fuel cycle based on thorium. Therefore, thermodynamic data concerning the interactions of thorium with various ligands are needed.

Thorium is found in nature only as tetravalent Th(IV), which can be mobilized through complexation with inorganic and organic ligands [10]. Though inorganic ligands are usually weaker complexants with Th(IV) than organic ligands, it was estimated that, in the absence of organic complexants and below pH 3, the Th(SO₄)_{2(aq)} complex is the most important in solutions containing F⁻, Cl⁻, PO₄³⁻, and SO₄²⁻ in concentrations typical of ground waters [10]. Hence, knowledge of the thermodynamic data for the complexation of Th(IV) with sulfate are important for the modelling of the Th(IV) behavior in acidic systems such as mine water and raffinate, acidic sulfate soils and sulfuric acid leachates from hydrothermal uranium ores, and high-level nuclear waste (HLW) repositories. In addition, because the temperature in HLW repositories could remain significantly higher than the ambient even thousands of years after their closure, data concerning the thermodynamic properties of Th(IV) sulfate complexes at high temperatures are also needed to predict the risk of thorium release from radioactive wastes.

Studies of complexation of Th(IV) with various inorganic ligands have recently been reviewed [11]. Numerous studies of the aqueous Th(IV) sulfate system have been conducted using different experimental techniques (solvent extraction, ion exchange) and different ionic media, but all these studies, except one [12], reported the stability constants of Th(IV) complexes with sulfate at 25 °C. In the study by Patil et al. [12], the values of equilibrium constants at 10, 25 and 40°C were reported, and, based on these values, the enthalpies and entropies of complex formation were calculated. There has been only one study that was dedicated to the determination of the enthalpies of formation of Th(SO₄)²⁺ and Th(SO₄)_{2(aq)} at ionic strength 2 M [13].

In this work, a microcalorimetric method was used to determine simultaneously the equilibrium constants and enthalpies of formation of Th(IV) sulfate complexes in 1 M (Na,H)ClO₄ at 10, 25, 40, 55, and 70 °C. In order to obtain reliable values for the complexation reactions, the study was extended to the simultaneous determination of the free energy and enthalpy of protonation of sulfate at the same temperatures and ionic medium. The results of this study for the Th(IV)/SO₄²⁻ system are summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overall thermodynamic parameters for the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes of Th(IV)Th with SO₄²⁻ in 1 M (Na,H)ClO₄ at different temperatures.

The complex formation reactions are entropy-driven. As the temperature is increased, the entropy term (TΔS) increases more than the unfavorable ΔH and, as a consequence, the complexes become more stable at higher temperatures.

References:

- [1] Paiva, A. P.; Malik, P., *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.* **2004**, 261, 485-496.
- [2] Sokolov F., Fukuda K., Nawada H. P., *Thorium fuel cycle: Potential benefits and challenges* International Atomic Energy Agency, IAEA-TECDOC-1450, May 2005.
- [3] David S., Huffer E., Nifenecker H., *Europhys. News* **38** (2007) 24-27.
- [4] Talamo A., *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.* **43** (2006) 1379–1394.
- [5] Le Brun C., *J. Nucl. Mater.* **360** (2007) 1–5.
- [6] Hyde R., Ishikawa M., Myhrvold N., Nuckolls J., Wood L., *Progr. Nucl. Energy* **50** (2008) 82-91.
- [7] Sahin S., Sahin H. M., Acir A., *Nucl. Eng. Des.* **240** (2010) 2066–2074.
- [8] Breza J., Darilek P., Necas V., *Ann. Nucl. Energy* **37** (2010) 685-690.
- [9] Gupta H.P., Menon S. V. G., Banerjee S, *J. Nucl. Mater.*, **383** (2008) 54-62.
- [10] Langmuir, D; Herman, J. S., *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **1980**, 44, 1753-1766.
- [11] Rand, M; Fuger, J.; Grenthe, I.; Neck, V.; Rai, D., *Chemical Thermodynamics of Thorium*, OECD Publishing, 2007
- [12] Patil, S. K.; Ramakrishna, V. V., *Radiochim. Acta*, **18**, (1972), 190-192.
- [13] Zielen, A. J., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **81**, (1959), 5022-5028.

Experimental and theoretical study of the complexation of uranyl(VI) with acetate in dimethylsulfoxide

Plinio Di BERNARDO, ^{a)} Pier Luigi ZANONATO, ^{a)} Arturo BISMONDO, ^{a)}
Franco BENETOLLO, ^{b)} Linfeng RAO, ^{c)} Andrea MELCHIOR, ^{d)} Marilena TOLAZZI ^{d)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università di Padova, Italy*

^{b)} *Istituto di Chimica Inorganica e delle Superfici del CNR, Padova, Italy*

^{c)} *Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Berkeley, CA, USA*

^{d)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Fisica e Ambiente, Università di Udine, Udine, Italy,*

marilena.tolazzi@uniud.it

An extensive literature exists on the complexation of actinide ions in aqueous solution [1-2] where they typically behave as hard cations and prefer to form complexes with charged hard bases like carboxylates. On the contrary, very few studies (e.g. [3-4]) have been done on the thermodynamics of complexation in non-aqueous solvents where interesting aspects on the chemistry of actinide in solution can be obtained. As far as acetate anion is considered, it has been found [5] that uranium(VI) forms in aqueous solution three mononuclear successive complexes stabilized by highly positive entropy changes which decrease at each complexation step so that $\Delta S_1 > \Delta S_2 > \Delta S_3$. The stepwise reaction enthalpies follow the order $\Delta H_1 > \Delta H_2 > \Delta H_3$ with the latter weakly exothermic [5]. These trends have been related to the progressive decrease of solvation of the complexes on increasing the ligand number and to the different coordination mode of acetate in the complexes which, as demonstrated by EXAFS spectra [5], changes from bidentate (in the 1:1 and 1:2 species) to mono/bi-dentate coordination in the third complex. To date, thermodynamic studies on actinide complexation in nonaqueous solution are almost absent in the literature, irrespective of the organic solvent, while structural investigations have been carried out mainly with vibrational and X-ray absorption spectroscopy [6]. In this context, we carried out a first thermodynamic, spectroscopic and computational study on acetate coordination to uranium(VI) in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) to improve the understanding of the role of a non hydrogen-bond-donor solvent on the thermodynamic parameters of complex formation. Thermodynamic parameters for the protonation of acetate and for the complexation of uranium(VI) by acetate in DMSO were already determined by potentiometry and calorimetry [7]. In this work, to establish the changes in the metal ion coordination sphere due to the acetate coordination, IR spectra have been collected in acetonitrile (AN), containing a fixed DMSO/U(VI) molar ratio ($R_{\text{DMSO/U(VI)}} = 15$) and variable molar ratios of Ac/U(VI) from 0 to 6. The spectra of pure AN and of the sample solutions were recorded separately, ratioed against the background, and converted to absorbance units. The AN spectrum was then numerically subtracted from the sample solution spectra, in order to obtain the difference spectra. For quantitative analysis, the concentration of free DMSO in solution was obtained by means of a calibration curve and by the peak absorbance at 1060 cm^{-1} , characteristic of free DMSO and calculated by spectral deconvolution. The mean number of DMSO molecules bounded to each metal ion (NC_{DMSO} in Figure 1) was finally obtained by the difference

between the stoichiometric and free DMSO ratioed against the metal ion concentration. Density functional theory calculations were performed on the Uranyl-acetate complexes using Gaussian09 program. The three-parameter hybrid functional B3LYP and the Stuttgart-Dresden small core potential for uranium was employed because their combination gave previously good agreement with the experimental values for the reaction energies and the vibrational frequencies of U(VI) complexes[8]. The analyses of IR spectra of DMSO-AN/DMSO solutions are compatible with several coordination modes for acetate. However, the combination with the theoretical results indicates that the three Ac⁻ in [UO₂(Ac)₃] are bidentate, differing from what was proposed in water [5]. Similarly, both spectroscopic and theoretical results suggest that acetate is bidentate also in [UO₂(Ac)]⁺ and that two DMSO molecules are displaced upon coordination. For [UO₂(Ac)₂] the situation is less clear since theoretical and experimental results are consistent with both mono or bi-dentation of one of the acetates. Moreover, the small energy gap found by DFT calculations for the two isomers suggests a possible equilibrium in solution. In this respect further investigations would be needed.

Figure 1. N_CDMSO vs. Ac⁻/U(VI) molar ratio for R_{DMSO/U(VI)} = 15

References:

- [1] Szabo, Z.; Toraishi, T.; Vallet, V.; Grenthe, I., Solution coordination chemistry of actinides: Thermodynamics, structure and reaction mechanisms, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, **2006**, 250 (7-8), 784-815.
- [2] Choppin, G. R.; Thakur, P.; Mathur, J. N.; Complexation thermodynamics and structural aspects of actinide-aminopolycarboxylates, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, **2006**, 250(7-8) 936-947.
- [3] Cassol, A.; Di Bernardo, P.; Portanova, R.; Tolazzi, M.; Tomat, G.; Zanonato, P., Complex-formation reactions of uranyl(VI) with neutral N-donors in dimethyl-sulfoxide, *Inorg. Chem.*, **1990**, 29, 1079-1084.
- [4] Cassol, A.; Di Bernardo, P.; Portanova, R.; Tolazzi, M.; Zanonato, P.L., Thermodynamic and spectroscopic investigations on the interaction of uranyl(VI) with neutral N-donors and O-donors in dimethyl-sulfoxide, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, **1995**, 733-739.
- [5] Jiang, J.; Rao, L.; Di Bernardo, P.; Zanonato, P. L.; Bismondo, A., Complexation of uranium(VI) with acetate at variable temperatures, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.* **2002**, 1832-1838.
- [6] Goerller-Walrand, X.Y.; De Houwer, S.; Fluylt, L.; Binnemans, K., Spectroscopic properties of uranyl chloride complexes in non-aqueous solvents, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **2004**, 6, 3292–3298.
- [7] Rao, LF; Jiang, J; Di Bernardo, P; Zanonato, P; Bismondo, A., 2002. Comparative study of uranyl(VI) complexation with acetate in water and dimethyl sulfoxide. *Abstract of Papers of the ACS*, 224:449-INOR, Part 1.
- [8] Iche-Tarrat, N.; Marsden, C. J., Examining the Performance of DFT Methods in Uranium Chemistry Does Core Size Matter for a Pseudopotential? *J. Phys. Chem. A*, **2008**, 112, 7632-7642.

Molecular dynamics simulation of cisplatin in water with an improved intermolecular interaction potential

Jose M. MARTÍNEZ,^{a)} Rafael R. PAPPALARDO,^{a)} Enrique SÁNCHEZ MARCOS,^{a)}
Andrea MELCHIOR^{b)}

^{a)} *Departamento de Química Física, Universidad de Sevilla*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Fisica e Ambiente Università di Udine*
andrea.melchior@uniud.it

Cisplatin (*cis*-diamminedichloroplatinum(II)) has been employed for over 30 years in the chemotherapy of a large number of tumours. The mechanism of action of cisplatin proceeds through the intracellular activation by hydrolysis of one chloride ligand followed by the covalent binding of the Pt-complex to DNA and the successive formation of intra-strand crosslinks leading to cell death[1]. In this framework, the quantitative study of complex hydration and of the chloride hydrolysis reactions has been considered fundamental for the understanding of its pharmacological activity, as well as of its analogues.

In the last decade, a large number of theoretical studies have been done to characterize hydrolysis reactions of platinum-based anticancer compounds. These studies use continuum models to account for the solvent effects [2]. However it has been recently shown [2,3] that a complete understanding of the solvent effects on the hydrolysis requires a molecular description of the solvent. In this respect both classical [4,5] and *ab initio* Car-Parrinello molecular dynamics[3] approaches have been applied to study cisplatin hydration structure and hydrolysis reactions. Although *ab initio* MD methods have the advantage of on-the-fly updating of the system wavefunction, they can only compute short simulation times and a reduced number of water molecules. This limits the sampling of the configurational and phase space and the physicochemical properties which can be examined.

[PtCl₂(NH₃)₂]-H₂O Lennard-Jones potentials have been recently developed by fitting *ab initio* interaction energies in order to study the hydration of the *cis*- [4,5] and *trans*-platin[5]. The number of water molecules obtained by the integration of the first peak of the Pt-O radial distribution function for cisplatin was very different in the two cases[4,5]. This could be due to a limited sampling of the structures employed to fit these LJ potentials. Another point of interest is that the absence of the axial hydration region, already reported [6,7] for the Pt(II) and Pd(II) aqua ions, and related compounds, concluding that this region should disappear for the neutral Pt(II) complexes.

In this contribution, we present the preliminary MD results obtained employing a new *ab initio* cisplatin-water interaction potential.

The geometry optimization of cisplatin and the energy calculations for the complex-water dimers were carried out at MP2 level using a 6-31+G(d) basis set for all atoms except Pt atom, which was described by the quasi-relativistic Stuttgart-Dresden pseudopotential. The SPC/E geometry has been used for water. The quantum-mechanical interaction energy used was that calculated for the complex in the continuum solvation model PCM in order to have a situation close to that of the condensed phase. This accounts for a part of the many-body

effect. The interaction energy has been corrected for BSSE energy using the 50% of the calculated value for the cisplatin-water dimers.

The following 4-6-8-12 plus Coulomb potential was chosen to describe the solute-solvent interaction (i = cisplatin sites, j water sites):

$$E_{pot} = \sum_{ij} \frac{C4_{ij}}{r_{ij}^4} + \frac{C6_{ij}}{r_{ij}^6} + \frac{C8_{ij}}{r_{ij}^8} + \frac{C12_{ij}}{r_{ij}^{12}} + \frac{q_i \cdot q_j}{r_{ij}}$$

The electrostatic term is calculated using the charges fitting the electrostatic solute potential. A total of about 3200 *ab initio* interaction energies were used for the fitting (by adjusting the coefficients C_{ij}).

MD simulations were carried out with the DL_POLY 2.20 program in the NVT ensemble at 298.15K. The simulation box, containing 1 cisplatin complex and 500 SPC/E water molecules, was adjusted to reproduce a density of 0.997 g/cm³. The total simulation time was 1ns with a timestep of 1 fs. Solute and water molecules are kept rigid during the simulation. Results analysis evidence differences with respect to the previous simulations, in particular concerning the first hydration shell around cisplatin which is less defined and containing more water molecules with respect to the previous works [4,5].

References:

- [1] Jamieson, E.R.; Lippard, S.J. Structure, Recognition, and Processing of Cisplatin-DNA Adducts, *Chem. Rev.*, **1999**, 99, 2467-2498
- [2] Melchior, A.; Sánchez Marcos, E.; Pappalardo, Rafael R.; Martínez J.M. Comparative study of the hydrolysis of a third- and a first-generation platinum anticancer complexes, *Theor. Chem. Acc.*, **2011**, 128(1), 627-638
- [3] Kai-Chi Lau, J.; Ensing, B., Hydrolysis of Cisplatin - A Metadynamics Study, *Phys.Chem.Chem.Phys.*, **2010**, 12, 10348–10355
- [4] Fedoce Lopes, J.; Ströele de A. Menezes V.; Duarte H. A.; Rocha, W. R, De Almeida, W. B.; Dos Santos H. F., Monte Carlo Simulation of Cisplatin Molecule in Aqueous Solution, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2006**, 110, 12047-12054
- [5] Fu, C-F; Shan Xi Tian, S.; Molecular dynamics study of solvation differences between cis- and transplatin molecules in water, *J.Chem.Phys.* **2010**, 132 174507
- [6] Martínez J.M.; Torrico, F.; Pappalardo, Rafael R.; Sánchez Marcos, E., Understanding the Hydration Structure of Square-Planar Aquaions: The [Pd(H₂O)₄]²⁺ Case, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2004**, 108, 15851-15855
- [7] Torrico, F.; Pappalardo, Rafael R.; Sánchez Marcos, E.; Martínez J.M., Hydration structure and dynamic properties of the square planar Pt(II) aquaion compared to the Pd(II) case, *Theor. Chem. Acc.*, **2006**, 115, 196–203

Thermodynamics Aspects and Analytical Applications of Hg(II)-TTCN Complexes

Elena PERALTA, ^{a)} Marilena TOLAZZI, ^{a)} Andrea MELCHIOR, ^{a)}
Manuel VALIENTE ^{b)}

^{a)} *Università degli Studi di Udine. Dipartimento di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche.
I-33100 Udine ITALY.*

^{b)} *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Departament de Química, Química Analítica, Centre
GTS 08193 Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain
manuel.valiente@uab.es*

The complex formation between a Thio derivative macrocycle (Trithiocyclononane, TTCN) and Hg(II) have been studied by Liquid-liquid distribution technique.

Aqueous insoluble TTCN becomes soluble in presence of aqueous Hg²⁺ because of corresponding aqueous soluble Hg(II)-TTCN complex formation.

Decane solutions of TTCN were contacted with aqueous Hg(NO₃)₂. The observed distribution of TTCN vary with aqueous mercury.

Analysis of data have shown the formation of 1:2 and in less extent 1:1 Hg(II):TTCN aqueous complexes. Obtained results are compared with those obtained by Polarographic techniques.

The mercury complex formation reported here have been applied to determine traces of Hg(II) in aqueous solutions. A preconcentration system including a TTCN impregnated sponge can provide more than one order of magnitude (20 to 30 fold) on Hg concentration. This system uses field portable XFR technique that allows the method to be applied for in situ determinations of mercury.

Acknowledgements: The present work is part of a current cooperation between the Università di Udine and the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.

Hazardous Heavy Metals Washing by Rainwater in Chronically Polluted Areas

Naiara GOIENAGA, ^{a)} **Leire KORTAZAR,** ^{a)} **Raquel GLEZ-TURRIÓN,** ^{a)}
Jose Antonio CARRERO, ^{a)} **Maitane OLIVARES,** ^{a)} **Alfredo SARMIENTO,** ^{b)}
Luis Ángel FERNÁNDEZ, ^{a)} **Juan Manuel MADARIAGA** ^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country (UPV-EHU),
P.K. 644, 48080 Bilbao, Spain*

^{b)} *SGIkerUniversity Services, University of the Basque Country (UPV-EHU),
P.K. 644, 48080 Bilbao, Spain
luis-angel.fernandez@ehu.es*

Acidification is one of the most severe causes of contamination in aquatic systems, not only as a toxicant itself, but also through its effects on the speciation, mobility, and bioavailability of other toxicants such as heavy metals. Acid mine drainage (AMD) from underground blende and galena mines and ore refuse piles is one of the most persistent industrial pollution problems. The most common source of AMD is the exposure of sulphide containing minerals to air and water, which promotes chemical reactions resulting in sulphide containing lixivates [1].

The present work's aim was to learn the leaching pattern of several pollutants (i.e. to find any correlation that may exist between the soil heavy metal contents and the heavy metal ions dissolved in rainwater). The chosen place for the study was an abandoned blende-galena mine located in Karrantzas' Valley (Biscay, Basque Country, north of Spain). To achieve that aim, a heavy rainy day (temperature: 7.4 °C; relative humidity 103%; precipitation in 24h, 42.5 L/m²) was chosen for the sampling. This procedure focused on two main objectives. On the one hand, a sampling of the superficial water that finally reaches the downstream and, on the other hand, the collection of the soils present under each water-sampling points.

The soil composition was determined by a newly developed "green technique" that tried to avoid the microwave based extraction method for sample measurements by ICP-MS and ICP-AES. This alternative uses an external calibration that consisted in measuring 35 pills formed by a mix of 10 CRMs. The measurements were done by means of the non-destructive techniques SEM-EDX and μ XRF. The aqueous samples were measured with ICP-AES, CE and UV-vis-NIR.

Table 1 shows several measurements obtained in points arranged in altitude, from a point above the mine (sample 1) down to the Calera River (sample 10). The data obtained give different information. (1) Here, the acid water generated by the oxidation of ZnS and PbS reacts with local rock, resulting in the leaching of many elements. Thus, AMD presents high contents of several risky heavy metals (i.e. Pb, Zn, Hg, Cd) among other unhealthy compounds (i.e., As or sulphide). While some of them may be transported as dissolved free ions or complexes downstream, others may be quickly removed from the water by precipitation as solid phases, depending on the physiochemical conditions along their migration path. These migrations may be influenced by the presence of pine plantations

(which use to acidify the topsoil increasing the heavy metals leaching processes) and pastures that appears alternately in the way to the river. (2) Taking into account that the impacts that the AMD may have in the Calera River (located at approximately 300 m downhill) were never considered and that some of the risky ion concentrations were so high, the necessity of studying such impacts from now on can be pointed out. (3) The rainfall washing of several hazardous heavy metals may give an idea of their potential migration to the groundwaters. At this point, it should be highlighted that calcareous sedimentary rocks [2], characteristic for their porosity, dominate the geology of the studied area.

Table 1. Values in ppm of different hazardous elements dissolved in rainwater collected at different altitudes.

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 6	Sample 7	Sample 8	Sample 9	Sample 10
As	0.25 ± 0.05	< LOD	0.018 ± 0.06	< LOD	< LOD	0.07 ± 0.02	0.16 ± 0.03	0.60 ± 0.03	0.47 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.01
Cd	< LOD	0.90 ± 0.02	1.63 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.01	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.05 ± 0.003	< LOD
Co	0.48 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.03	0.32 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.01	0.52 ± 0.01	0.43 ± 0.01	0.48 ± 0.01
Cr	1.63 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.04	1.22 ± 0.06	1.21 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.07	1.53 ± 0.04	1.27 ± 0.02	1.68 ± 0.03	1.86 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.03
Cu	2.39 ± 0.04	0.38 ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.02	1.08 ± 0.02	0.27 ± 0.01	0.54 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.02	2.78 ± 0.05	1.74 ± 0.02
Fe	513.46 ± 5.36	60.26 ± 2.29	417.35 ± 7.19	292.03 ± 2.48	36.50 ± 0.07	375.69 ± 4.44	536.96 ± 4.08	1011.23 ± 8.70	584.76 ± 4.91	394 ± 2.78
Hg	0.42 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.01	0.43 ± 0.01	0.43 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.01	0.40 ± 0.01
Mn	14.06 ± 0.15	3.73 ± 0.01	6.81 ± 0.06	0.58 ± 0.02	5.61 ± 0.02	6.91 ± 0.04	9.58 ± 0.11	17.16 ± 0.15	4.39 ± 0.02	8.23 ± 0.11
Ni	0.55 ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.01	< LOD	0.14 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.04	1.79 ± 0.02	1.44 ± 0.03
Pb	31.09 ± 0.41	29.86 ± 0.55	156.71 ± 0.36	37.54 ± 0.57	5.26 ± 0.10	0.43 ± 0.01	4.44 ± 0.07	23.76 ± 0.15	13.30 ± 0.09	< LOD
Sb	0.22 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.01	0.14 ± 0.005	0.19 ± 0.006	0.19 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01	< LOD
Sn	0.10 ± 0.02	< LOD	< LOD	0.15 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.005	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
V	1.35 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.01	0.79 ± 0.04	0.43 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.01	0.72 ± 0.004	1.33 ± 0.01	1.66 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.02
Zn	282.88 ± 2.68	2289.40 ± 32.30	1836.89 ± 14.18	335.03 ± 4.38	582.84 ± 1.89	9.91 ± 0.08	158.57 ± 0.85	226.67 ± 1.81	209.26 ± 2.30	< LOD

The studied mine stopped its commercial activities almost half a century ago. However, the chronic pollution status in which it remains is still so relevant that the environmentally adverse effects that the pollutants there present may have at any ecological level and compartment (i.e. air, water) are considerable. Thus, and based on this kind of investigations, the area should be included as highly polluted in the map of polluted lands of the Basque Country that the Basque Government has made. This way, the application of ecological and health risk assessment protocols can be carried out before taking any action in the area.

References:

- [1] Ceto, N., *Abandoned mine site characterization and cleanup handbook*. EPA 910-B-00-001. Seattle, **2000**; pp. 129.
- [2] Goienaga, N.; Arrieta, N.; Carrero, J.A.; Olivares, M.; Sarmiento, A.; Martinez-Arkarazo, I.; Fernández, L.A.; Madariaga, J.M. Micro-Raman spectroscopic identification of natural mineral phases and their weathering products inside an abandoned zinc/lead mine. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A*. In Press, DOI: 10.1016/j.saa.2011.01.032.

Seawater H⁺ Affinity Spectrum: A Chemometric Exercise

Marian OLAZABAL DUEÑAS, Elisa ASTIGARRAGA ALLENDE, Janire SÁEZ
CASTAÑO, Luis Ángel FERNÁNDEZ CUADRADO

Department of Analytical chemistry, University of The Basque Country, Faculty of Science
and Technology, P.O. Box 644, 48080 Bilbao, Spain

luis-angel.fernandez@ehu.es

Seawater is a complex aqueous media whose composition is affected by many processes, both natural (including evaporation, freezing, rainfall, melting, fresh water flow from the continents, etc.) and anthropogenic (i.e., extra CO₂ release to the atmosphere). The study of seawater composition may be traced back to Lavoisier, who analysed deep seawater in the English Channel, and continues today, particularly stimulated by the controversies raised by ocean acidification and its capability of absorbing CO₂.

Models of seawater speciation can be built up with the help, among others, of chemical equilibrium tools such as computer programs integrating equilibrium constant databases and the ability to make complex calculations and plots of the results.

While using one of these tools, namely the MEDUSA computer program [1] we realized the peculiar behaviour of the *H⁺ Affinity Spectrum* in the pH area in the vicinity of natural seawater common values (pH ~ 8). This spectrum is defined as the plot of the first derivative of H_{Bound} (H_{Bound} = H_{Tot} - [H⁺] - [OH⁻]) vs, i.e., pH and it is calculated numerically by the program. The Figure below shows this spectrum for a *common* 35 %Salinity composition as stated by Dyrssen and Sillén in 1967 [2].

H⁺ Affinity Spectrum

[F ⁻] _{TOT} = 74.00 μM	I = 0.700 M
[Sr ²⁺] _{TOT} = 93.00 μM	[B(OH) ₃] _{TOT} = 0.41 mM
[Ca ²⁺] _{TOT} = 10.30 mM	[CO ₃ ²⁻] _{TOT} = 2.34 mM
[Mg ²⁺] _{TOT} = 53.15 mM	[SO ₄ ²⁻] _{TOT} = 28.23 mM
[K ⁺] _{TOT} = 10.21 mM	[Br ⁻] _{TOT} = 0.84 mM
[Na ⁺] _{TOT} = 468.30 mM	[Cl ⁻] _{TOT} = 545.87 mM

At the sight of this kind of *spectra* and somewhat influenced by the large possibilities of using chemometric tools to deal this kind of spectroscopic information, 3 questions aroused:

- (1) Can we disclose which of the 11 major seawater components are responsible for the shape of these spectra?

- (2) If the variation of the spectral shape is linked with seawater composition, could we use the spectra to classify seawater samples?
- (3) Given the constancy in the proportions of major seawater components, could we use spectra obtained at different salinities to *calibrate* the composition of these constituents?

To address the first question, different types of experimental designs were proposed and analyzed with the help of The Unscrambler computer program [3]. Thus, the composition of theoretical seawaters was varied at two levels (corresponding with the somewhat *extreme* salinity compositions of 32 % and 38%, respectively) according to Plackett-Burman and Factorial Fractionate designs. Response values, i.e. the spectra, were constructed with the help of the MEDUSA program at the concentration levels dictated by the design. The phenomenological approach provided by these chemometric techniques not only agrees with the background chemical knowledge of this complex system but adds some insight to its interpretation.

The second question was addressed by mixing experimental evidence and chemometric analysis. Thus, potentiometric seawater titrations as those recommended by Dyrssen [2] were used as the basis to obtain the experimental H⁺ Affinity Spectra of several samples collected at different places, times and tides. The scores diagram of the principal component analysis (PCA) carried out, reveals several groupings of the samples. Although is not straightforward to interpret the relationship of the latent with the real variables, this analysis seems to indicate the possibility to classify samples according to their origin and characteristics.

To answer the last question, a theoretical *calibration set* was constructed with the help of the MEDUSA program considering seawater compositions ranging from 1 to 40 %Salinity. Again, the *common* 35 %Salinity composition stated by Dyrssen and Sillén was used as the reference. Analysis of the obtained spectra by means of Partial Least Squares (PLS2, namely) reveals a good correspondence with the composition of each of the 11 major components studied. For the moment, the comparison of the *predicted* composition obtained from the theoretical and inexpensive *PLS2 calibration model* and experimental values of total carbonate and fluoride concentrations (lacking a complete analysis of the composition for the other components) obtained by potentiometric titration and F- ion selective electrode measurements, respectively, is encouraging and is under way.

References:

- [1] Puigdomenech, I. *Windows software for the graphical presentation of chemical speciation*, in: 219th ACS National Meeting. Abstracts of Papers, Vol.1. Amer. Chem. Soc., San Francisco, Ca, March 26-30, **2000**. Abstract I&EC-248.
- [2] Dyrssen, D.; Sillén, L. G., *Alkalinity and total carbonate in sea water. A plea for p-T-independent data*, Tellus XIX, **1967**; Vol. 1, pp 113-120.
- [3] The Unscrambler, CAMO Software AS, Nedre Vollgate 8 N-0158 Oslo, Norway.
<http://www.camo.com>

Influence of Soil Organic Matter in the Leaching Processes of Hazardous Heavy Metals

Naiara GOIENAGA, Leire KORTAZAR, Raquel GLEZ-TURRIÓN, Olivia GÓMEZ,
Jose Antonio CARRERO, Luis Ángel FERNÁNDEZ, Juan Manuel MADARIAGA

*a) Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country (UPV-EHU), P.K. 644, 48080 Bilbao, Spain.
luis-angel.fernandez@ehu.es*

The structure and function of the soil organic matter together with other chemicals and biophysical properties such as biological activity and mineral nutrients is the base of the soil health. Humic (HA) and fulvic (FA) substances are widely known organic compounds [1]. These, which are found in most soils, are originated from the transformation of animal and plant matter into relatively stable macromolecules with high molecular weights [2]. Their huge amount of abilities make them excellent ligands for metal ions in aqueous solutions [2]. Therefore, the HA and FA play a vital role in the transport, bioavailability, and deposition of many toxic heavy metal ions (i.e. Pb, Zn, Hg, As) and organic pollutants (i.e. biocides).

The aim of this work was the determination of the soil health based on the soil organic matter in an abandoned Pb-Zn mine located in Karrantzas' Valley (Biscay, North of Spain). Thus, over 50 topsoil samples were collected. The analyses carried out were mainly: (1) soil total extraction, measured by means of ICP-MS; (2) application of a lixiviation test using naturally occurring weathering agents as reagents, the analytes were monitored by IC and ICP-MS; (3) determination of HA and FA by means of a sequential extraction procedure and NIR. A summary of the obtained results is shown in Table 1.

In order to learn what was going on a chemical modelling was applied. The thermodynamic speciation was conducted through chemical simulations using the MEDUSA software [3]. Figure 1 shows the simulation made with blende, maintaining a fixed pH and changing the total amount of CO₂.

Figure 1. Chemical modelling of the situation.

The combination of sequestration and bioremediation by the HA and FA commonly lead to significant decreases in the pollutants bioavailability. However, in this highly polluted

area, the artificial income overcomes thoroughly the original concentrations, in a way that the HA and FA present in the soils are not enough to account for the large amount of available metals. Therefore, the adverse effects that this difference may generate in the surrounding environment require a deep analysis in both the environmental and health risk assessments.

Table 1. ICP-MS and ICP-AES values (in ppm) of the soil total extractions together with the concentrations obtained for humic and fulvic acids per sample.

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
Al	26446.57 ± 143.3	7410.29 ± 101.3	8560.73 ± 73.2	12565.77 ± 89.7
As	5.25 ± 0.7	42.18 ± 2.7	8.94 ± 0.74	14.93 ± 2.9
Cd	0.61 ± 0.04	180.61 ± 6.3	3.33 ± 0.75	23.58 ± .7
Co	< LOD	2.29 ± 0.8	1.61 ± 0.08	2.28 ± 0.08
Cr	7.34 ± 0.9	10.98 ± 2.4	10.35 ± 0.98	18.79 ± 3.7
Cu	3.42 ± 0.05	236.62 ± 24.2	9.56 ± 0.9	42.24 ± 7.9
Fe	40269.62 ± 98.7	44999.59 ± 46.6	12394.97 ± 33.1	19835.43 ± 72.1
Hg	1.03 ± 0.09	232.39 ± 13.2	3.83 ± 1.1	9.02 ± 2.1
Mg	1827.84 ± 38.8	5916.28 ± 61.1	602.87 ± 34.5	2498.16 ± 22.2
Mn	23.43 ± 2.2	324.84 ± 22.1	97.68 ± 7.3	334.78 ± 24.1
Ni	9.23 ± 1.1	11.3 ± 1.5	6.68 ± 2.1	15.94 ± 3.3
Pb	2113.44 ± 33.3	138225.84 ± 49.9	6414.52 ± 43.3	17312.28 ± 31.6
Sn	0.96 ± 0.07	25.31 ± 3.1	2.55 ± 0.78	7.88 ± 1.2
V	13.15 ± 1.5	18.93 ± 2.6	17.19 ± 1.1	33.27 ± 2.9
Zn	1599.36 ± 41.3	116234.01 ± 98.7	2230.61 ± 78.2	19061 ± 27.7
HUMIC ACIDS	4457.42 ± 26.80	24007.43 ± 16.02	6758.69 ± 5.32	14134.35 ± 35.07
FULVIC ACIDS	20168.42 ± 19.18	20160.56 ± 4.45	31084.08 ± 7.76	16661.40 ± 1.57

Bearing in mind that soil productivity and ecological functionality is closely related to the soil organic matter and the man-made pollutants inputs, based on the results, the studied area may be classified as rather poor and unhealthy. Thus, the application to some extent -as far as the local environment allows- of some of the recommendations listed in the “Guidelines for assessing human health risks from environmental hazards” seems to be necessary in order to minimize the heavy metals leaching processes.

References:

- [1] Nieman, J.K.C.; Sims, R.C.; Sorensen, D.L.; McLean, J.E., Humic acid toxicity and biologically treated soil contaminated with polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and pentachlorophenol. *Environmental contamination and toxicology* **2005**, 49, 283-289.
- [2] Palmer, N. E.; von Wandruszka, R., Dynamic light measurements of particle size development in aqueous humic materials. *Fresenius Journal of Analytical Chemistry* **2001**, 371, 951-954.
- [3] Puigmomenech, UI. MEDUSA: Make Equilibrium Diagrams Using Sophisticated Algorithms (<http://www.kemi.kth.se/medusa>), KTH, Stockholm, 2004.

Raman Spectroscopy study of a salt weathering process in mortars of a Historical Palace House

**Olivia GÓMEZ-LASERNA, Héctor MORILLAS, Nagore PRIETO-TABOADA,
Iratxe IBARRONDO, Irantzu MARTINEZ-ARKARAZO,
Marian OLAZABAL, Juan Manuel MADARIAGA**

University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Department of Analytical Chemistry, Barrio Sarriena s/n, 48940, Leioa, Spain. Tel.: +34 946018294.

marian.olazabal@ehu.es

The stone and mortars alteration is a natural and irreversible process of degradation that historical buildings are destined to suffer. In this process, the crystallization of soluble salts into the building materials is considered one of the most destructive damage processes. The salts not only alter the appearance of the building when they become visible as an efflorescence, but also cause considerable damage when they crystallize/dissolve within the pores and capillaries. They are able to produce internal fractures when solubilised ions, coming from any other salts, recrystallize as another salt or the same compound but with a different number of hydrate waters. For these reasons the characterization of salts found in the pores and surfaces of damaged building materials is very important to diagnose the chemical process leading to the deterioration. This must be done always prior to conservation interventions.

In this work, a study of mortars building materials (both original and decaying compounds) of the Basozabal Palace is presented. This is a historic building of the fifteenth century located close to the river Urola, in the old quarter of Azpeitia (North of Spain). Throughout history the building has undergone several restoration actions, the last one performed in 1990.

The main objective of this work was to identify the degradation products formed by combination of the atmospheric pollutants and infiltration waters. For this purpose on-site analysis were carried out by an ultramobile Raman spectrometer (B&WTEK_{INC}). Moreover, some samples of mortars (and cements of past restoration works) of the internal walls were taken to perform further analyses in the laboratory. The walls of the ground floor, erected from the river course, are clearly affected by infiltration waters that ascend by capillarity.

A variety of carbonate salts were found as original compounds of the mortars in interior walls, like Calcite (CaCO_3), Natrite (Na_2CO_3), Natron ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and Trona ($\text{Na}_3(\text{HCO}_3)(\text{CO}_3) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The Raman spectra of all of them are collected in the Figure.

The distribution of the salts found at different zones of the wall seems to depend on the ionic mobility and salt solubility. For instance, nitrates (the most abundant decaying compounds) are able to achieve the upper parts of the wall while unaltered carbonates remain in the lower part. The source of nitrates is likely the infiltration of waters charged with NH_4NO_3 , a common decomposition product of the organic matter. As a consequence of the high reactivity of NH_4NO_3 , this salt was not identified but niter (KNO_3) and nitratine (NaNO_3) were found instead.

Raman Spectra showing all the original carbonates: Trona (a), Natron (b), Sodium carbonate (c) and Calcite (d)

Niter (KNO_3) was found as efflorescence on the joint mortars of limestones whereas nitratine (NaNO_3) was identified as the most predominant subefflorescence inside the sandstones. The source of potassium seems to be the degraded K-feldspar while that of sodium seems to be either natron or sodium carbonate, thus the chemical degradation processes could be described by the following reactions (1,2):

A similar degradation was observed in cements of the restored areas. In these areas Thenardite (Na_2SO_4), which is related to the impact of atmospheric SO_2 and subsequent migration of sulphate anion through the original material, was found (see reaction 3):

Thenardite is known to be a very hazardous salt due to its continuous changes on number of hydration water molecules [2]. The results indicate a substantial impact on the mortars of the building by the action of infiltration waters and SO_2 acid gas. Both sources introduce acids that react with different carbonate mineral phase forming the corresponding more soluble nitrate and sulphate salts.

Acknowledgements: This work has been financially supported by the project IMDICOGU (ref. BIA 2008-06592) from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICINN). O. Gómez-Laserna and I. Ibarrodo acknowledge their grants from the University of the Basque Country and N. Prieto-Taboada acknowledges her grant from the Spanish MICINN.

References:

- [1] Maguregui. M.; Sarmiento.A.; Martínez-Arkarazo. I.; Angulo. M.; Castro. K.; Arana. G.; Etxebarria. N.; Madariaga. J.M., Analytical diagnosis methodology to evaluate nitrate impact on historical building materials. *Anal Bioanal Chem* **2007**, 391, 1361–1370.
- [2] Hamilton. A.; Menzies. R.I., Raman spectra of mirabilite, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the rediscovered metaestable heptahydrate, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy* **2010**, 41, 1014–1020.

Extraction method of soluble salts from bricks samples located in deteriorated building using focused ultrasound

Cristina ZARZA, Nagore PRIETO-TABOADA, Silvia FDEZ-ORTIZ DE VALLEJUELO, Irantzu MARTINEZ-ARKARAZO, Alberto DE DIEGO, Nestor ETXEBARRIA, Marian OLAZABAL, Juan Manuel MADARIAGA

Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), P.O. Box 644, E-48080 Bilbao, Basque Country, Spain
marian.olazabal@ehu.es

Bricks located in buildings are normally exposed to different climatic conditions or influences from atmospheric acid gases or infiltrations by aqueous solution [1]. Water or humidity allows salt to be transported outside of the brick (efflorescence), enables it to crystallize.

The soluble salts formation in bricks produces a decrease in aesthetic quality of the buildings, and when the crystallization pressure exceeds the tensile strength, the brick cracks, and then it is possible that the material lose can affect the integrity of building. For such problems, it is important to characterise the construction material in order to determine the salt content and their nature when the conservation state of constructive elements of buildings is going to be restored or a construction material is going to be reused [2, 3]. This is the case of some buildings located in Metropolitan Bilbao (north of Spain), especially buildings constructed in the first of the twentieth century that show substantial damage on their facade materials.

The aim of this study was to develop and optimise a extraction method of soluble salts for bricks using focused ultrasound (USF) with titanium probe, trying to get smaller extraction times that normal protocol UNI 11087 (2 hours of agitation) [4]. Previous works carried out in our research group have proved that extraction times are possible to be reduced using ultrasound energy as an alternative to classical normalized protocols for different matrices [5,6].

Brick samples were collected from seven facades of deteriorated buildings (Fig. 1) located in Zorrozaurre (Bilbao, north of Spain) and one of them was selected to optimize the extraction procedure.

The influence of several variables such as mass of sample (0.1-0.2 g), volume of extraction medium (25-45 mL), length of the probe immersed in the extractant (0.5-2 cm), ultrasound amplitude (10-90 %), cycle (1-9) and sonication time (5-60 min.) was first screened in preliminary experiments to identify the factors with significant influence on the extraction procedure (fractional factorial design). Analysis of the extracts was carried out by a Dionex ICS 2,500 ionic chromatograph.

Only sonication time, mass of brick sample and ultrasound amplitude were found to significantly influence on extraction procedure. A central composite design (CCD) was used to define the best conditions for the extraction of soluble salts. Finally, compromise conditions were defined for the simultaneous extraction of K^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , F^- , NO_3^-

and SO_4^{2-} . Best set of variables found was as follows: 11 minutes of sonication time, 90% ultrasound power and mass 0.5 g of sample.

The extraction method proposed here has demonstrated to be an efficient, repetitive (RSD obtained were always below of 5%) and extremely fast alternative to classical method used.

Finally, seven brick samples collected were analysed following the procedure proposed, allowed us to know the real state of these seven deteriorated building.

Figure 1. Localization of seven samples that were taken in different buildings of Zorrozaurre (Bilbao, north of Spain). The picture shows the wall of brick with the highest concentration of soluble salts.

Acknowledgments: This work has been financially supported by the IMDICOGU project (ref.:BIA2008-06592) from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICINN). N. Prieto-Taboada is grateful for her predoctoral grant from the MICINN.

References:

- [1] Maguregui M.; Sarmiento A.; Escribano R.; Martinez-Arkarazo I.; Castro K.; Madariaga J. M., *Anal Bioanal Chem* **2009**, 395,2119–2129.
- [2] Rincón J.M.; Romero M., *Materiales de Construcción* **2000**, 50, 63-69.
- [3] Cultrone G.; Sebastian E., *Environ Geol* **2008**, 56, 729–740.
- [4] UNI 11087/2003 Method: Dossagio dei Sali Solubili, CNR (Centri Di Studio Di Milano e Roma Sulle Cause Di Deperimento e Sui Metodi di Conservazione Delle Opere Dârte ICR Instituto Centale de Restauro.) Roma, Italy, 2003.
- [5] Fdez-Ortiz de Vallejuelo S.; Barrena A., Arana G.; de Diego A.; Madariaga J.M., *Talanta* **2009**, 80, 434-439.
- [6] Maguregui M.; Sarmiento A.; Martinez-Arkarazo I.; Angulo M.; Castro K.; Arana G.; Etxebarria N.; Madariaga J.M., *Anal Bioanal Chem* **2008**, 391,1361-1370.

Buildings as repositories of hazardous compounds resulted from atmospheric pollution

Nagore PRIETO-TABOADA, Olivia GÓMEZ-LASERNA, Irantzu MARTINEZ-ARKARAZO, Marian OLAZABAL and Juan Manuel MADARIAGA

*University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Department of Analytical Chemistry, Barrio Sarriena s/n, 48940, Leioa, Spain. Tel.: +34 946018294
marian.olazabal@ehu.es*

Atmospheric contamination has an important role in most of the important cities of the world because it is considered the main factor affecting building degradation, causing in some cases a significant loss of cultural heritage [1]. However the effect in building without historical relevance usually is not taking into account, although they could provide essential information about the degradation processes of different building materials.

Pollution in form of particulate matter or acid rain is deposited in the buildings surfaces, and accumulates the hazardous pollutant trapped in the surface [2]. In this way, buildings act as pollution repositories even after the emission source is removed.

Grey-to-black crust formation is produced by gypsum crystals and carbon particles which have been widely demonstrated to be an important factor to take into account due to their potential catalytic action [1].

In this work, a historical building located in the metropolitan area of Bilbao was analysed in order to determinate the impact of the polluted atmosphere in the construction. The sampling area is located near an old industry activity and a harbour.

In a first attempt, an elemental analysis was carried out by μ -XRF to compare the internal and external side of samples, in order to determinate the grade of pollution penetration. This analysis revealed the presence of metals with an anthropogenic origin such as Pb, Cu or As. In this case, no significant differences between both sides were found, which indicated that pollutants have reached depth through the building materials.

A molecular analysis by Raman spectroscopy was performed to identify the original compounds of the construction material, in order to understand the degradation process suffered. In this way, calcite and aragonite (CaCO_3) as well as iron (III) oxides as limonite $\text{FeO}(\text{OH})$ and hematite (Fe_2O_3), were identified as major original composition. As degradation compounds, gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and anhydrite (CaSO_4) were identified, resulted from the attack of SO_x acid gases over the original calcium carbonate.

Furthermore, acid gases can interact with marine aerosols according to reaction (1) to form thenardite (Na_2SO_4) and nitratine (NaNO_3) by the action of both SO_x and the emergent NO_x .

The particulate matter deposited on the facade can also react with atmospheric acid gases. For example, barium sulphate (BaSO₄) was identified as secondary product of the deposited barium. Moreover, iron sulphate in the coquimbite form (Fe₂(SO₄)₃·9H₂O) was also identified. This compound is referenced to be formed by the attack of the free sulphate ions over the iron deposits following equation (2) [2].

In order to determine quantitatively the level of pollution, ICP-MS, GC-MS and IC (Ionic Chromatographic) analysis was carried out. The elemental analysis revealed the deposition of pollutants such as Pb, Cr, Cu or As in a high concentrations up to 806 ppm, 752 ppm, 159 ppm and 220 ppm respectively. The Phenanthrene/anthracene and Fluoranthene/pyrene relation determined by PHAs analysis indicated the pyrolytic source related to combustion of fuel-oils [3]. The IC analysis confirmed the results obtained by Raman spectroscopy because sulphate and nitrate were found as main soluble salts. Moreover, soluble salts contents up to 5% in samples without black crust and up to 93% in black crusted mortars were found. A Principal Components Analysis of the quantitative results was carried out by the Unscrambler 9.2 software in order to evaluate the possible source of the pollutant, confirming the key role of sulphates and nitrates [4].

Acknowledgements: This work was financially supported by the Spanish Government (MICINN) through IMDICOGU project (ref. BIA2008-06592). N. Prieto-Taboada acknowledges her grant from the Spanish MICINN, and O. Gómez-Laserna acknowledges her grant from the University of the Basque Country.

References:

- [1] Sabbioni, C.; Ghedini, N.; Bonazza, A., Organic anions in damage layers on monuments and buildings. *Atmos. Environ.* **2003**, 37 (9-10), 1261-1269.
- [2] Prieto-Taboada, N.; Maguregui, M.; Martinez-Arkarazo, I.; Olazabal, M.; Arana, G., Madariaga, J., Spectroscopic evaluation of the environmental impact on black crusted modern mortars in urban–industrial areas. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry* **2010**, 399 (9), 2949-2959.
- [3] Bartolomé, L.; Cortazar, E.; Raposo, J. C.; Usobiaga, A.; Zuloaga, O.; Etxebarria, N., Fernández, L. A., Simultaneous microwave-assisted extraction of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, polychlorinated biphenyls, phthalate esters and nonylphenols in sediments. *J. Chromatogr. A* **2005**, 1068 (2), 229-236.
- [4] Camo Process, Unscrambler v9.2.

Cr(VI) removal from metal binary mixtures by using biosorbents

Marc BARTROLÍ,^{a)} Jana BEYTS,^{a)} Núria FIOL,^{a)} Florencio de la TORRE,^{a)}
Jordi POCH,^{b)} Isabel VILLAESCUSA^{a)}

^{a)} *Chemical Engineering Department, Escola Politècnica Superior, Universitat de Girona,
Avda. Lluís Santaló, s/n, 17071 Girona (Spain)*

^{b)} *Applied Mathematics Department, Escola Politècnica Superior, Universitat de Girona,
Avda. Lluís Santaló, s/n, 17071 Girona (Spain)*

nuria.fiol@udg.edu

Hexavalent chromium is present in the effluents coming from electroplating industries together with other metal ions. During the last years, biosorption has been an alternative to costly wastewaters treatments for metal removal. Among the low cost biomaterials recently investigated, grape stalks (GS) coming from the wine production and exhausted coffee (EC) from the manufacture of soluble instant coffee have been used to remove Cr(VI) from single metal solutions [1,2]. Nevertheless, the performance of these two sorbents for Cr(VI) removal from metal binary mixtures has not yet been evaluated.

In this work, Cu(II), Ni(II) and Cr(VI) removal from Cr(VI)-Cu(II) and Cr(VI)-Ni(II) mixtures by using grape stalks and exhausted coffee is studied. The effect of pH, contact time and metal concentration on metal sorption has been investigated.

Before starting the study of metal removal from binary mixtures, experiments with single metal solution were performed in order to determine the best sorption conditions. In single solutions, pH 2-3 for Cr(VI) and pH 4-5 for Cu(II) and Ni(II) resulted to be the optimum pHs. The time of contact to achieve equilibrium was 6 days for Cr(VI) and 2 hours for Cu(II) and Ni(II). When studying metal sorption in binary mixtures similar optimum pH values and contact time were found. Experiments performed with binary mixtures of Cr(VI)-Cu(II) and Cr(VI)-Ni(II) were carried out at pH 3 as at this pH reduction of Cr(VI) to Cr(III) was found to be favourable [1] and the agitation was maintained for six days.

The obtained results show that capacity of both sorbents (GS and EC) for the investigated metals (Cu(II), Ni(II) and Cr(VI)) is higher when they are removed from binary mixtures than from single solutions. Therefore, each metal exerts a synergism effect to each other.

Acknowledgements: This work has been financially supported by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, Spain, Project CTM2008-06776-C02-01. An Erasmus scholarship was attributed to Jana Beyts.

References

- [1] Fiol, N., Escudero, C., Villaescusa, I. (2008) Chromium sorption and Cr(VI) reduction to Cr(III) by grape stalks and yohimbe bark, *Bioresource Technology*, 99: 5030-5036.
- [2] Fiol, N., Escudero, C., Villaescusa, I. (2008) Re-use of exhausted ground coffee waste for Cr(VI) sorption, *Separation Science & Technology*, 43: 582-596.

Potentiometric and ESI MS investigation on Cd(II), Pb(II) and Zn(II) cations-L-cystine interaction in aqueous media

**Emilia FURIA, Fabio MAZZOTTI, Anna NAPOLI,
Giovanni SINDONA, Antonio TAGARELLI**

*Dipartimento di Chimica, Università della Calabria, Via Pietro Bucci,
87036 Arcavacata di Rende(CS)
e.furia@unical.it*

L-Cystine results from cysteine oxidation with the formation of a disulfide bridge and displays four protonation sites. The two most basic protonation steps for L-cystine relate to its two amino groups whereas the two most acidic steps correspond to its two carboxylate functions. Both types of donor sites are likely to participate in metal coordination; in addition, the disulfide bond may also be involved in some specific cases. The interaction of cations with L-cystine is more important than that with cysteine, that is rapidly oxidised in human blood [1]. Therefore, it is interesting evaluate the complexing ability of L-cystine towards Cd(II), Pb(II) and Zn(II) whose toxicity is well known. These systems should be form two, three and four coordination monomeric complexes with the same ligand. Fewer examples of these complexes have been characterized structurally [2] whilst structural studies are required to understand the sequestering ability of natural ligands towards toxicological cations.

The solubility of L-cystine increases proportionally with the ionic medium concentration [3,4], therefore the complexation equilibria have been studied at 25°C and in 3 mol·dm⁻³ NaClO₄ ionic medium by measuring with a glass electrode the competition of the L-cystine, H₂L, for the metal and H⁺ ions. The potentiometric measurements, carried out as titrations, were performed with cell (G)

where RE, reference electrode, = Ag/AgCl/0.01 mol·dm⁻³ AgClO₄, 2.99 mol·dm⁻³ NaClO₄/3 mol·dm⁻³ NaClO₄, and Test Solution = C_M mol·dm⁻³ M(ClO₄)_z, C_L mol·dm⁻³ H₂L, C_A mol dm⁻³ HClO₄, and C_B mol·dm⁻³ NaOH, (3-z C_M-C_A-C_B) mol·dm⁻³ NaClO₄. The concentrations of ligand (C_L) and metal ions M^{z+} (C_M) were varied between (0.5·10⁻³ and 5·10⁻³) mol dm⁻³, and the ligand-to-metal ratio was varied between 1 and 10 (1 ≤ C_L/C_M ≤ 10). The hydrogen ion concentration was decreased stepwise to the incipient precipitation of a basic salt of each metal. The general equilibrium can be written, schematically, for all four systems as equation 1:

Equilibrium formation constants, β_{pqr} , are given for the investigated ionic medium. The speciation model and equilibrium data were determined on the basis of potentiometric evidences as well as the bonding sites by means of electrospray ionization (ESI) mass

spectrometry [5]. Electrospray ionization is one of the softest ionization techniques and makes possible to determine the molecular weight of many metal complex compounds. ESI MS and MS/MS are used for the structure elucidation *in situ* of Cd(II), Pb(II) and Zn(II) cations-L-cystine complexes in aqueous solution, as obtained at room temperature from simply mixing solutions of cations and ligand in different conditions of pH and metal to ligand ratios.

References:

- [1] Bohrer, D.; Gabbi Polli, V.; Cícero do Nascimento, P.; Mendonça, J.K.A.; Machado de Carvalho, L.; Garcia Pomblum, S., Ion-exchange and potentiometric characterization of Al–cystine and Al–cysteine complexes. *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.* **2006**, 11, 991-998.
- [2] Kulkarni, A.D.; Patil, S.A.; Badami, P.S., Electrochemical Properties of some Transition Metal Complexes: Synthesis, Characterization and *In-vitro* antimicrobial studies of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II) and Fe(III) Complexes. *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, **2009**, 4, 717-729.
- [3] Furia, E.; Falvo, M.; Porto, R., Solubility and acidic constants of L-cystine in NaClO₄ solutions at 25°C. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data* **2009**, 54, 3037-3042.
- [4] Furia, E.; Sindona, G., Complexation of L–cystine with metal cations. *Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data* **2010**, 55, 2985-2989.
- [5] Cardiano P.; Giuffré O.; Napoli A.; Sammartano S., Potentiometric, ¹H-NMR, ESI-MS investigation on dimethyltin(IV) cation-mercaptocarboxylate interaction in aqueous media. *New journal of chemistry = Nouveau journal de chimie* **2009**, 33, 2286-2295.

Speciation of Cadmium - D-penicillamine, mercaptosuccinic acid and glutathione systems in NaNO₃ ionic medium

Alba GIACALONE, ^{a)} Antonio GIANGUZZA, ^{a)} Daniela PIAZZESE, ^{a)} Anna NAPOLI ^{b)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica “Stanislao Cannizzaro”. Università di Palermo, Viale delle Scienze, I-90128 Palermo, Italia*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Chimica, Università della Calabria, Via P. Bucci, 87036 Arcavacata di Rende (CS), Italy*
agiacalone@unipa.it

Cadmium shows a high affinity towards most of the binding groups present in biologically active molecules. In particular, the thiol ligands present in the amino acid residues, are the main vectors through which transport and distribution of cadmium in the human body occur. In spite of the large number of investigations reported in the literature about the toxic effects of cadmium and its environmental impact [1], relatively few quantitative data are reported on the stability of species formed by the interaction between Cd²⁺ and S-donor ligands in aqueous solution [2]. Therefore, it is difficult to define the speciation picture of this element in natural waters and biological fluids where thiol ligands are often naturally present. With the aim to contribute to the knowledge of cadmium(II) speciation in the presence of sulphur containing ligands, we report here the preliminary results of a study on the interaction of Cd²⁺ with 2-mercaptosuccinic (or thiomalic) acid (*tma*), penicillamine (*psh*) and glutathione (*gsh*) ligands. The complex species formation and the relative stability constants were determined by potentiometric (ISE-H⁺ and ISE-Cd²⁺) measurements in NaNO₃ aqueous medium at I = 0.1 mol L⁻¹ and t = 25 °C. ElectroSpray Ionization (ESI) mass spectrometry measurements confirmed the complexation model proposed on the basis of potenziometric results. For all the Cd²⁺- L (L = *psh*, *tma*, *gsh*) systems investigated, the calculations gave evidence for the formation of ML and ML₂ complex species. In addition, some protonated M(L)H_i species were found, in particular for the Cd-gluthatione system. By using the stability data obtained for all the complex species formed, the sequestering capacity of the ligands considered here towards cadmium(II) ion, expressed as pL₅₀ parameter [i.e. the -log(total ligand concentration) necessary to bind 50% of cadmium ion], was calculated at different pH values.

References:

- [1] Nriagu J.O. In Cadmium in the Environment. Part I: Ecological Cycling; Nriagu, J.O., Ed.; Wiley:New York, 1980
- [2] Martell A.E., Smith R.M. and Motekaitis R.J. NIST Critically selected stability constants of metal complexes database, 8.0; National Institute of Standard and Technology: Garthersburg, MD (2004).

Complexation of DNA with partially negatively charged gold nanoparticles in salt solution.

Rafael PRADO-GOTOR, Elia GRUESO

Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Sevilla, C/Profesor García González, s/n, 41012, Sevilla, Spain.

elia@us.es

The binding of Gold nanoparticles capped with N-(2-mercaptopropionyl)glycine (AuNPs) of 1.4 nm core size with double stranded DNA has been investigated and quantified in terms of free energies based on changes on DNA molar ellipticity. Working at different salt concentrations, the non-electrostatic and electrostatic components of the free energy of the binding have been quantified. The result obtained revealed that the binding has, fundamentally, a non-electrostatic character.

Circular dichroism experiments show that gold nanoparticles can significantly change the helicity conformation of DNA. Further support to this insight is shown in Fig. 1a corresponding to the zeta potential of DNA as a function of AuNPs concentration in the presence and in the absence of salt. Zeta potential increases initially with increasing gold nanoparticle concentration due to the binding of a few slightly anionic AuNPs molecules to DNA. Consequently, the original exposed charges in the DNA chain become hidden on the surface of the DNA molecules. With further increasing AuNPs concentration, the transition to more negatively charged complexes occurs over a small increment of AuNPs concentration. This behaviour is attributed predominantly to a process of compaction of DNA induced by gold nanoparticles [1]. Also, from Fig. 1 it can be seen that zeta potential is a minimum when the effective particle diameter corresponds to a more DNA compact globule conformation, due to the shear plane is located close to the complex surface [2]. These results represented that binding of gold nanoparticles to DNA resulted in significant changes in the structure of DNA in a concentration dependent manner of gold nanoparticles and salt. Viscosity measurements, melting experiments and competitive binding study with SYBR Green I, indicates a groove binding mode has been assigned to the interaction of DNA with the gold nanoparticles.

References:

- [1] Gagnon, Z.; Senapati, S.; Gordon, J.; Chang, H. Dielectrophoretic detection and quantification of hybridized DNA molecules on nano-genetic particles. *Electrophoresis*. **2008**, 29, 4808-4812.
- [2] Probstein, R. F.; *Physicochemical Hydrodynamics*, Wiley: New York, **1994**, pp. 211.

Gold nanoparticles-DNA Interactions: An atomic force microscopy and circular dichroism study.

Rafael PRADO-GOTOR, ^{a)} Consuelo CERRILLOS, ^{b)} Elia GRUESO, ^{a)}

^{a)} *Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Sevilla, C/Profesor García González, s/n, 41012, Sevilla, Spain.*

^{b)} *CITIUS (Center of Investigation, Technology and Innovation) University of Seville, Avda Reina Mercedes 4, 41012, Sevilla, Spain*
elia@us.es

Using circular dichroism technique and an atomic force microscope (AFM), we studied the condensation of DNA induced by tiopronin gold nanoparticles of 1.4 nm core size. These particles were highly stable and soluble in aqueous solution. Structure alterations of the DNA caused by its interaction with nanoparticles are reflected in changes in the intrinsic and induced CD spectra of the complex. A positive ICD signal in the range of 280-400 nm was observed, when CT DNA was added, suggesting the interaction of tiopronin nanoparticles onto DNA surface. On the other hand, AFM has been an important tool in the study of DNA structure since its invention [1]. Experiments with AFM microscopy technique reveals stepwise condensation events at increasing [AuNPs]/[DNA] binding ratio. The results lead to a model in which, during condensation, intermediates of the compactation process show flower-like structures containing loops of DNA exterior to a densely packed center [2]. As the local density of gold nanoparticles in the intermediates increases, they compact into globular features and aggregates. It was shown, therefore that tiopronin gold nanoparticles are highly water soluble DNA-binders and condense the DNA into a compact globular shape, which is a desired property for gene transfection agents [3].

References:

- [1] Hansma, P. K.; Elings, V. B.; Marti, O.; Bracker, C. E., Scanning tunneling microscopy and atomic force microscopy: application to biology and technology. *Science*. **1988**, 242 (4876), 209-216.
- [2] Prado-Gotor, R.; Grueso, E., A kinetic study of the interaction of DNA with gold nanoparticles: mechanistic aspects of the interaction. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2011**, 13, 1479-1489.
- [3] Ren, T.; Zheng, G. S.; Liu, D. X., Synthesis of galactosyl compounds for targeted gene delivery. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* **2001**, 9, 2969-2978.

Metal Interaction in Polytopic Receptors

Jorge GONZÁLEZ,^{a)} Salvador BLASCO,^{a)} Mario INCLÁN,^{a)} Javier PITARCH,^{a)}
Raquel BELDA,^{a)} Begoña VERDEJO,^{a)} Carmen E. CASTILLO,^{b)} M. Angeles
MAÑEZ,^{b)} José M. LLINARES,^{c)} Hermas R. JIMÉNEZ,^{d)} Roberto TEJERO,^{e)} Manuel
G. BASALLOTE,^{b)} Concepción SORIANO,^{c)} Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA^{a)}

^{a)} Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol), Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Universidad de Valencia, C\ Catedrático José Beltrán n° 2, 46980, Paterna, Valencia, SPAIN

^{b)} Departamento de Ciencia de los Materiales e Ingeniería Metalúrgica, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Cádiz, Polígono Río San Pedro, s/n Puerto Real, 11510, Cádiz, SPAIN

^{c)} Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol), Departamento de Química Orgánica, Universidad de Valencia, C\ Catedrático José Beltrán n° 2, 46980, Paterna, Valencia, SPAIN

^{d)} Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Universidad de Valencia, Burjassot, Valencia, SPAIN

^{e)} Departamento de Química-Física, Universidad de Valencia, Burjassot, Valencia, SPAIN

jollibe@uv.es

Recently, multitopic ligands have received and increased interest. The interest stems from their potential applications in fields such as molecular recognition, molecular devices, enzyme mimicking and pharmaceutical chemistry. [1-3]

Bicylam, bicyclen and tricyclen molecules linked by different alkyl and aryl groups display interesting activity as antiviral drugs for the treatment of HIV-1 and HIV-2. Additionally, it has postulated that metal coordination can reinforce or decrease the activity.[4]

Herein, it is described the synthesis of two new tritopic receptors in which two equivalent 5-(2-aminoethyl)-2,5,8-triaza[9]-(2,6)-pyridinophane moieties have been linked with 2,6 dimethylpyridine (**L1**) or 2,6-dimethylphananthroline (**L2**) units. Their acid-base behaviour and Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ coordination chemistry have been studied by potentiometric titrations, NMR, UV-Vis and X-Ray. These receptors are able to form mono-, bi and trinuclear metal complexes. The interaction of **L1** and **L2** with pyrophosphate (PPi), tripolyphosphate (TPP) and adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP) has been followed by titrations, ¹H and ³¹P NMR techniques and molecular dynamic analysis. Finally, formation of mixed complexes Zn²⁺-**L**-PPi, Zn²⁺-**L**-TPP and Zn²⁺-**L**-ATP has been studied for both receptors by potentiometric titrations.

References:

- [1] Lehn, J. M. *Supramolecular Chemistry. Concepts and Perspectives*, VCH, Weinheim
- [2] Schneider, H.J. *Principles and Methods in Supramolecular Chemistry*, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, UK, 2000.
- [3] Bianchi, A; Bowman-James, K.; García-España, E. *Supramolecular Chemistry of Anions*, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, UK, 1997.
- [4] Bridger, G. J.; Skerlj, R. T.; Padmanabhan, S.; Martellucci, S. A.; Henson, G. W.; Abrams, M. J.; Joao, H. C.; Witvrouw, M.; De Vreese, K.; Pauwels, R.; De Clercq, E. *J. Med. Chem.* **1996**, *39*, 109-119.

Complex-formation equilibria between Fe(III) and hydroxamic derivatives of bile acids

Sara CHIEREGHIN, Dimitri BACCO, Marco FOGAGNOLO, Maurizio REMELLI

Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Ferrara, Via L. Borsari 46, 44121, Ferrara
rmm@unife.it

The first target of chelation therapy is to alleviate the toxic effects of metal excess in metal-overload diseases. However, the central role played by metal ions in both normal metabolism and many serious illnesses recently suggested to extend the application of some iron or copper chelators to other clinical situations, like cancer chemotherapy [1,2] and treatment of neurodegenerative diseases [3].

In designing new chelators for clinical application, the metal selectivity and the ligand-metal complex stability are of primary importance: the determination of the binding constants and the binding energies (in enthalpic/entropic terms) of the target metal ion with the designed ligand occupies a key position among the information that is commonly considered crucial (molecular weight of both the ligand and the complex, solution structure of the species prevailing under the physiological conditions, water solubility and lipophilicity of both the chelator and the complex species, redox properties, toxicity) [4]. Moreover, the binding affinity for other biologically relevant metal ions and the competition with other biologically relevant ligands should be carefully evaluated, in order to predict the species distribution and the authentic chelating efficiency, *in vivo*.

In this context, we decided to focus our attention on some hydroxamic derivatives of bile acids (Figure 1); they can be considered as bifunctional ligands containing a transport moiety and a chelating side chain. Bile acids are steroids derived from the catabolism of

Figure 1. Structures of phocaecholic (a), chenodeoxycholic (b), cholic (c) and deoxycholic (d) hydroxamic acids.

cholesterol and essential for the digestion and absorption of lipids. They can go through cell membranes and are involved in both active and passive transport processes. Bile acids have recently been used both as prodrugs and as carriers of drugs [5,6]. Hydroxamic acids are strong chelators for the Fe(III) ion; they use two oxygens as donor atoms thus forming a five-membered chelate ring. In the absence of charged side chains, neutral octahedral tris-complexes can be formed, with good potential of cross biological membranes. This feature is important for their possible application in the iron removal from tumor cells and/or brain.

In the present work, the results of a preliminary study on the ability of the above hydroxamic-acid derivatives to bind the Fe(III) ion, are reported. Protonation constant of the ligands have been determined by potentiometric titrations and complex-formation equilibria have been studied by UV-Vis spectrophotometry, in hydro-alcoholic solution. The stoichiometry of complex species has been checked by ESI Mass Spectrometry.

References:

- [1] Kontoghiorghes, G. J.; Efstathiou, A.; Loannou-Loucaides, S.; Kolnagou, A., Chelators controlling metal metabolism and toxicity pathways: Applications in cancer prevention, diagnosis and treatment. *Hemoglobin* **2008**, 32 (1-2), 217-227.
- [2] Whitnall, M.; Howard, J.; Ponka, P.; Richardson, D. R., A class of iron chelators with a wide spectrum of potent antitumor activity that overcomes resistance to chemotherapeutics. *Proc. Nat.l Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2006**, 103 (40), 14901-14906.
- [3] Hider, R. C.; Roy, S.; Ma, Y. M.; Le Kong, X.; Preston, J., The potential application of iron chelators for the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. *Metallomics* **2011**, 3 (3), 239-249.
- [4] Crisponi, G.; Remelli, M., Iron chelating agents for the treatment of iron overload. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2008**, 252 (10-11), 1225-1240.
- [5] Sievanen, E., Exploitation of Bile Acid Transport Systems in Prodrug Design. *Molecules* **2007**, 12 (8), 1859-1889.
- [6] Chong, H. S.; Song, H. A.; Ma, X.; Lim, S.; Sun, X.; Mhaske, S. B., Bile acid-based polyaminocarboxylate conjugates as targeted antitumor agents. *Chem. Commun.* **2009**, (21), 3011-3013.

Sequestration of Pd²⁺ by polyamino-polycarboxylic ligands

Antonio GIANGUZZA, ^{a)} Alberto PETTIGNANO, ^{a)} Silvio SAMMARTANO ^{b)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica “Stanislao Cannizzaro”, Università di Palermo, Viale delle Scienze, I-90128 Palermo, Italy,*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica, Università di Messina, Via Ferdinando Stagno d’Alcontres, 31, I-98166 Messina (Vill. S. Agata), Italy*
pettignano@unipa.it

The increase of the worldwide demand of “Platinum group elements” (PGE) for application in several fields such as industry, medicine, jewellery and, especially, in catalyst converter production [1], caused a noticeable increasing of PGE concentration in the environment. [2-4]. Though palladium, among the anthropogenic PGE, is not the most abundant one, it is the most hazardous since it undergoes easily and quickly oxidation to palladium(II) when in contact with soils [2-4], with a consequent increase of its mobility in the environment. The presence of complexing agents, which form soluble complex species with palladium(II), favours the mobility of the ion with an increase of its availability to plants, animals and humans. Among anthropogenic complexing molecules, an important role is played by synthetic aminopolycarboxylic chelating agents (usually called with the acronym APC) whose concentration in the environment is progressively increasing owing to their considerable use in several fields (agriculture, industry, medicine) [5] and a low biodegradability of most of them [5-7]. The interaction of these ligands with palladium(II) ion leads to the formation of soluble complex species whose stability influences strongly the availability of palladium(II) in the environment. With the aim to assess the strength of interaction of Pd²⁺ with aminopolycarboxylic ligands, here we report the results of a systematic study, , on the formation of palladium(II) complex species with five APCs [ethylenediamine-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetate (EDTA), (*S,S*)-Ethylenediamine-*N,N'*-disuccinic acid (S,S-EDDS), Nitritotriacetate (NTA) and diethylenetriamine-*N,N,N',N'',N'''*-pentaacetate (DTPA) and triethylenetetraamine-*N,N,N',N'',N''',N''''*-hexaacetate (TTHA)]. Owing to the high stability of the Pd²⁺ - APC complex species, the calculation of their stability constants was very difficult and was possible only by combining the results obtained from two series of ISE-H⁺ potentiometric titration (in NaNO₃ and in mixed NaNO₃ /NaI ionic medium) and from ISE-H⁺ potentiometric /spectrophotometric titrations (in NaClO₄). As expected, the stability of Pd-APC complex species is function of the number of carboxylic and amino groups present in the ligand molecules (e.g., logK_{Pd(APC)} = 37.00, 36.31, 23.60, 23.07 and 17.82 for TTHA, DTPA, EDTA, S,S-EDDS and NTA in Na⁺ ionic media, at I = 0.1 mol L⁻¹ and T = 25°C). Results obtained on the stability of species in the Pd- S,S-EDDS show that this ligand, which is the most biodegradable APC ligand, can be used successfully as environmental friendly chelating agent in substitution of the other less degradable APCs in all their application fields.

From the stability data of the Pd²⁺ - APCs the sequestration capacity [expressed as pL₅₀, i.e. the -log (APC concentration) necessary to bind the 50% of the metal ion [8]) of the ligands under investigation towards palladium(II) ion was determined in the pH range

considered. The pL_{50} is easily correlated to important physico-chemical parameters (pH, ionic strength, temperature, etc.) as shown in the Figure, where the dependence on pH of pL_{50} of the APCs towards Pd^{2+} ion is reported.

Figure. Dependence on pH of sequestration capability of APCs, in terms of pL_{50} , towards Pd^{2+} ion. Experimental conditions: $C_{Pd^{2+}} = 10^{-14} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (trace), Na^+ ionic medium, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ and $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$

As can be seen, TTHA and DTPA show almost the same sequestering ability in the pH range 2 – 10, clearly higher than that of EDTA, S,S-EDDS and NTA where a minor number of amino and carboxylic groups is present in the molecule.

References:

- [1] H. Renner, G. Schmuckler, Platinum-Group Metals, in: E. Merian (Ed.) Metals and Their Compounds in the Environment: Occurrence, Analysis, and Biological Relevance, VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 1991, pp. 893-908.
- [2] B. Sures, S. Zimmerman, J. Messerschmidt, A. Von Bohlen, *Ecotoxicol.*, 11 (2002) 385-392.
- [3] M. Moldovan, M.A. Palacios, M.M. Gomez, G. Morrison, S. Rauch, C. McLeod, R. Ma, S. Caroli, A. Alimonti, F. Petrucci, B. Bocca, P. Schramel, M. Zischka, C. Pettersson, U. Wass, M. Luna, J.C. Saenz, J. Santamaria, *Sci. Tot. Environ.*, 296 (2002) 199-208.
- [4] C. Colombo, A.J. Monhemius, *J.A. Plant, Sci. Tot. Environ.*, 389 (2008) 46-51.
- [5] *Biogeochemistry of Chelating Agents*, American Chemical Society, Washington, DC, 2005.
- [6] S. Tandy, A. Ammann, R. Schulin, B. Nowack, *Environmental Pollution*, 142 (2006) 191-199.
- [7] S. Metsärinne, P. Rantanen, R. Aksela, T. Tuhkanen, *Chemosphere*, 55 (2004) 379-388.
- [8] F. Crea, C. Foti, S. Sammartano, *Talanta*, 75 (2008) 775-785.

Integrated Composite Kinetic Molecular Devices for Slow Anion Releasing

Giuseppe ALIBRANDI,^{a)} Greta BERGAMASCHI,^{b)} Riccardo DOLLENZ^{a)}
Luigi FABBRIZZI,^{b)} Maurizio LICCHELLI,^{b)} Carmelo LO VECCHIO^{a)}

^{a)} Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica, Università di Messina, Viale F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31, Vill. S. Agata, 98166 Messina, Italy.

^{b)} Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Pavia, Viale Taramelli 12, 27100 Pavia, Italy.
clovecchio@unime.it

Kinetic molecular devices (KMDs) perform a specific work at a molecular level by using the kinetics of the process in which they are involved. Particularly, variable-parameter kinetic molecular devices (VPa KMDs) are able to change in a controlled way an environmental parameter (pH, T , I , $[Nu]$, etc.) inside a reaction vessel making it possible to follow automatically parameter-sensitive processes without using external physical devices.[1] Variable-pH and variable-temperature KMDs have been used to carry out, respectively, spectrophotometric and NMR variable-pH kinetic experiments or automatic titrations and variable-temperature kinetic experiments. In some cases *cooperative* composite KMDs have been used, formed by two chemical systems working as a molecular apparatus, able both to change the parameter and to monitor it.[2]

In this contribution a first example of *integrated* composite KMD is proposed where two chemical devices operate together in the same environment, interacting with each other, to perform a work different from those peculiar to the single ones. It is formed by [1.1.1]cryptand,[3] able to change slowly and irreversibly the pH in a linear way,[1] and $[Cu_2(bis-tren-ter-2,5-dimethylfuran)]^{4+}$, able to capture rapidly and reversibly anions (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , N_3^-).[4] The two devices, together, act as a variable-anion concentration KMD by releasing slowly and almost linearly with time anions, in this way making it possible to follow automatically anion-sensitive processes without using physical devices (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Way of action for the slow anion releasing by the composite kinetic molecular device.

A mathematical model has been derived to describe the behavior of this complex system and a computer simulation for various anions in various conditions has been carried out. A

spectrophotometric method to follow the concentrations of the involved species and the pH has been devised.

An experiment has been carried out in a 1 mm quartz cuvette containing, in water at 25°C, [1.1.1]cryptand 0.1 M, [Cu₂(bis-tren-ter-2,5-dimethylfuran)]⁴⁺ 0.003 M and Cl⁻ 0.003 M. The change in absorbance, processed by the mathematical model, gave, without using external pH and anion sensors, the increasing values of both pH and chloride concentration.

Many useful applications of this kind of molecular devices are possible.

References:

- [1] G. Alibrandi, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, **2008**, *47*, 3026–3028; G. Alibrandi, C. Lo Vecchio, G. Lando, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, **2009**, *121*, 6450–6452. G. Alibrandi, D. G. Lister, C. Lo Vecchio, *ChemPhysChem* **2009**, *10*, 3209–3211.
- [2] G. Alibrandi, C. Lo Vecchio, A. Villari, I. Villari, *Chem. Eur. J.*, **2010**, *16*, 7700-7703; G. Alibrandi, C. G. Arena, G. Lando, C. Lo Vecchio, M. F. Parisi, *Chem. Eur. J.*, **2011**, *17*, 1419-1422.
- [3] J. Cheney, J. M. Lehn, *J. Chem. Soc. Chem. Commun.* **1972**, 487–488. P. B. Smith, J. L. Dye, J. Cheney, J. M. Lehn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1981**, *103*, 6044–6048.
- [4] V. Amendola, E. Bastianello, L. Fabbri, C. Mangano, P. Pallavicini, A. Perotti, A. Manotti Lanfredi, F. Ugozzoli, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, **2000**, *39*, 2917–2920; V. Amendola, M. Bonizzoni, D. Esteban-Gomez, L. Fabbri, M. Licchelli, F. Sancenon, A. Taglietti, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, **2006**, *250*, 1451–1470.

Thermodynamic dissociation constants of some dronates using potentiometric titration data

Zuzana FERENČÍKOVÁ,^{a)} Milan MELOUN,^{a)} Tomáš PEKÁREK^{b)}

^{a)} Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemical Technology,
 University Pardubice, CZ-532 10 Pardubice, Czech Republic

^{b)} ZENTIVA Group k.s., U kabelovny 130, Praha, Czech Republic
zuzka.ferencikova@seznam.cz

Mixed dissociation constants of three nitrogen-containing bisphosphonates acids H₅L, alendronate, ibandronate and risedronate at various ionic strengths *I* and at 25°C and at 37°C have been determined with the use of regression analysis of potentiometric titration data. Three nitrogen-containing bisphosphonates *i.e.* risedronate, ibandronate and alendronate denoted as N-BPs are the antiresorptive drugs [1] most widely used to treat osteoporosis owing to their particularly high potency at inhibiting osteoclast-mediated bone resorption [2]. Bisphosphonates N-BPs are now the major drugs used in the treatment of postmenopausal osteoporosis and represent the first-line therapy in the majority of patients. Early studies showed that the P–C–P backbone in bisphosphonates was a major contributor to bone binding affinity. Hounslow et al. [1] showed that the macroscopic p*K*_as and chemical shifts in NMR for the macrospecies were deconvoluted into microconstants by determining the site-specific protonation mole fraction. This can be achieved by assuming that the chemical shift of a nucleus *I* in the H₂L²⁻ species differs from that in HL³⁻ only as a consequence of protonation of the **N** site and not of the **P** site (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Dissociation of nitrogen-containing bisphosphonates N-BPs according to [1].

In general, all three N-BPs are pentaprotic acids, but after dissolution, they may be treated as tetraprotic or triprotic acids. Titration of tetraprotic weak acid H₄L with a strong base (e.g. NaOH) involves eight solution species H₃O⁺, OH⁻, H₄L, H₃L⁻, H₂L²⁻, HL³⁻, L⁴⁻, and the sodium cation Na⁺. For adjusted value of ionic strength the potentiometric titration of a mixture of HCl and N-BPs drug acid with potassium hydroxide was carried out. The initial tentative value of dissociation constant of the drug studied corresponding to the midpoint value in each plateau of the potentiometric titration curve data (Figure. 2) has been applied by

the nonlinear regression ESAB and/or HYPERQUAD programs and gave the values of pK_{a2} , pK_{a3} , pK_{a4} and pK_{a5} . The pK_a values obtained by deconvolution of the potentiometric titration curve indicated that this N-BP dissociates in a manner similar to that elucidated for risedronate (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Protonation equilibria of risedronate analyzed with ESAB (a) potentiometric titration curve of risedronate; (b) plot of residuals; (c) distribution diagram of relative presentation of all species of protonation equilibrium, (d) dependence of the mixed dissociation constant pK_a of risedronate on the square root of an ionic strength, which leads to parameter estimates $pK_{a2}^T = 2.365(20)$, $pK_{a3}^T = 6.158(7)$, $pK_{a4}^T = 7.270(8)$ and $pK_{a5}^T = 11.600(123)$, in the brackets are the standard deviations in last valid digits.

Acknowledgments: The financial support of the Grant Agency IGA MZ ČR (No NS9831-4/2008) and of the Czech Ministry of Education (Grant No MSM0021627502) is gratefully acknowledged.

References:

- [1] Hounslow, A. M.; Carran, J.; Brown, *et al.* Determination of the Microscopic Equilibrium Dissociation Constants for Risedronate and Its Analogues Reveals Two Distinct Roles for the Nitrogen Atom in Nitrogen-Containing Bisphosphonate Drugs, *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* **2008**, *51*, 4170
- [2] Fleisch, H. *Bosphosphonates in Bone Disease. From laboratory to the Patient.* The Parthenon Publishing Company: New York and London, **1995**.

Recent progress in calculation methods to determine the dependence of stability constant values on ionic strength. Results for the nickel(II) / glycine system for $0.06 \leq I / \text{mol L}^{-1} \leq 5.3$.

**Rosalia Maria CIGALA, ^{a)} Concetta DE STEFANO, ^{a)} Peter GANS, ^{b)}
Demetrio MILEA, ^{a)} Silvio SAMMARTANO ^{a)}**

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica, Università di Messina, V.le F. Stagno D'Alcontres, 31, I-98166 Messina (Vill. S. Agata), Italy.*

^{b)} *Protonic Software, 2, Templegate Avenue, Leeds LS15 0HD, England*
peter.gans@hyperquad.co.uk

A study of the dependence on ionic strength of ligand protonation constants and metal-ligand stability constants is particularly important for the understanding of complexation phenomena in naturally occurring fluids, such as sea water, river waters and biological fluids, where there are wide variations in the concentrations of “background” salts. Ionic strength variation may also be important for the determination of equilibrium constants by potentiometric titration, especially when using the “self-medium” method.

The program BSTAC [1] has been developed to enable the dependence of stability constants on ionic strength to be quantified by means of a parametric equation such as

$$\log \beta = \log \beta^0 - z^* A \frac{\sqrt{I}}{1 + 1.5\sqrt{I}} + CI + DI^{3/2} + EI^2$$

where C, D and E are empirical parameters, z^* depends on ionic charges and I is the ionic strength. This program was developed as an extension of the program SUPERQUAD [2]; it runs under the DOS operating system. We are now in the process of developing a new program, Visual BSTAC, which uses the Windows operating system, to perform similar calculations, with the hope that it might be used more widely. VBSTAC, written entirely in Visual Basic, can be seen as an extension of the program Hyperquad [3] in that Hyperquad is used for potentiometric data obtained at a single ionic strength.

The new program has been used to process some new data on the nickel(II) / glycine system. This system was subjected to a detailed study by various research groups more than thirty years ago [4]. One result of this study was the production of general guidelines for the experimental procedures to be used in studies involving potentiometric titrations, so much so that the system is often used to check a new titration set-up. We have now extended the range of experimental measurements to cover ionic strengths of $0.06 \leq I / \text{mol L}^{-1} \leq 5.3$ with sodium chloride as the supporting electrolyte.

References:

- [1] De Stefano, C.; Mineo, P.; Rigano, C.; Sammartano, S., Ionic Strength Dependence of Formation Constants. XVII. The Calculation of Equilibrium Concentrations and Formation Constants. *Ann. Chim. (Rome)* **1993**, 83, 243-277.
- [2] Gans, P.; Sabatini, A.; Vacca, A., SUPERQUAD: an improved general program for computation of formation constants from potentiometric data. *J. Chem. Soc Dalton Trans.* **1985**, (6), 1195-1200.
- [3] Gans, P.; Sabatini, A.; Vacca, A., Hyperquad2008.
<http://www.hyperquad.co.uk/HQ2008.htm>
- [4] Braibanti, A.; Ostacoli, G.; Paoletti, P.; Pettit, L. D.; Sammartano, S., Recommended Procedure for Testing the Potentiometric Apparatus and Technique for the pH-metric Measurement of Metal-Complex Equilibrium Constants. *Pure & Appl. Chem.* **1987**, 59, 1721-1728.

Speciation of Sn²⁺ - hydroxocarboxylic ligand solutions: thermodynamic and spectroscopic study

Francesco CREA, ^{a)} Concetta DE STEFANO, ^{a)} Gabriele LANDO, ^{a)}
Demetrio MILEA, ^{a)} Silvio SAMMARTANO, ^{a)} Michelangelo SCOPELLITI ^{b)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica, Università di Messina, V.le F. Stagno D'Alcontres, 31, I-98166 Messina (Vill. S. Agata), Italy.*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Chimica "Stanislao Cannizzaro", Università di Palermo, Viale delle Scienze, I-90128 Palermo, Italy.*

glando@unime.it

Inorganic tin is rarely rated among the most common "pollutants", though its presence in the environment is strictly connected with human activity. As a consequence, while the chemistry of organotin compounds has been extensively studied because of their high toxicity toward numerous living organisms, less work has been achieved on the inorganic forms. Nevertheless, the knowledge of the speciation and the chemical behavior of inorganic tin forms is of great importance to understand the activity of both inorganic and organic tin forms. In fact, the alkylation of inorganic tin frequently occurs in the environment, as a consequence of biotic and abiotic activities, and it is influenced by its speciation. Moreover, the presence of ¹²⁶Sn in the nuclear wastes of ¹²⁶Sn (coming from fission; with a half-life value close to 105 years) requires a better knowledge of the chemistry of inorganic tin to understand and model its speciation. Despite this, the experimental knowledge of the chemical behaviour and the species distribution of tin in natural waters is practically nonexistent. Only vague predictions of the various species can presently be determined from the available thermodynamic data. In particular, the solution behaviour of tin(II) is not very well defined, so that we have recently undertaken a systematic study of tin(II) speciation in aqueous solution. As a first step, we defined both the acid base properties and the inorganic speciation of tin(II), and we successively extended this study to its speciation in the presence organic ligands of biological and environmental interest.

In particular, we report in this contribution some results of a potentiometric and Mössbauer investigation on the formation and stability of Sn²⁺ complexes with three hydroxocarboxylic ligands, namely malate (*mala*), citrate (*cit*) and tartrate (*tar*), at *t* = 25°C in different ionic media and ionic strengths (0.15 mol L⁻¹ in NaCl_{aq}, 1.0 mol L⁻¹ in NaNO_{3aq} and NaCl_{aq}). The stability constants of various Sn_{*i*}H_{*j*}L_{*k*}^(2i+j-kz) species are reported, as well as those relative to the formation of mixed Sn_{*i*}H_{*j*}L_{*k*}Cl_{*l*}^(2i+j-kz-l) species. The corresponding speciation diagrams of Sn²⁺ in the presence of these ligands are presented in different conditions, and structural information derived from Mössbauer measurements is provided.

Acknowledgements: we thank Procter & Gamble Co. for financial support

References:

- [1] Bulten, E. J.; Meinema, H. A., Tin. In *Metals and their compounds in the environment. Occurrence, analysis and biological relevance*, Merian, E., Ed. VHC: Weinheim, **1991**; pp 1243-1260.
- [2] Schapira, J. P. *Le dossier des déchets nucléaires*; Société Française de Physique: **1997**; pp 3-24.
- [3] Chen, B.; Zhou, Q.; Liu, J.; Cao, D.; Wang, T.; Jiang, G., Methylation mechanism of tin(II) by methylcobalamin in aquatic systems. *Chemosphere* **2007**, 68 414-419.

Even-Odd Alternation of some Thermodynamic Properties of α - ω -Alkanedicarboxylic Acids.

Rosalia Maria CIGALA, ^{a)} **Francesco CREA**, ^{a)} **Stefano MATERAZZI** ^{b)}

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica dell'Università, Viale F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31, 98166 Messina (Vill. S. Agata), Italy.*

^{b)} *Dipartimento di Chimica dell'Università "La Sapienza", Piazzale A. Moro 5, I-00185 Roma*
rmcigala@unime.it

Carboxylic ligands are a class of organic compound widely present in natural and biological fluid as degradation product of many high molecular weight compounds. They are most important owing to their large employment in many industrial sectors and in commercial products. Among these ligands, linear dicarboxylic acids represent a class of ligands of primary importance since are naturally present in many food products, or exhibit biological functions; for example, azelaic acid is an antineoplastic and dermatologic agent and the adipic acid is used as antioxidant and as primary matter in the production of Nylon-66, etc. The literature reports many data on the chemical-physic properties of such ligands, and on their behaviour in aqueous and solid state. Linear dicarboxylic acids are very interesting because they exhibit, for many properties (i.e. solubility, thermal behaviour, thermodynamic data, etc.) undulatory behaviour depending on whether the number of methylene groups are odd or even. These effects, are generally more pronounced for the first few members of the series. For example this behaviour can be observed for the melting point, which are alternate in the series: malonic, succinic, glutaric, adipic, pimelic, etc. It has been also observed an alternation in the C-C- bond lengths in the even acids. For these particular characteristics the chemical-physic properties of dicarboxylate were widely investigated by means of many different techniques. In particular structural investigation of crystalline solids undergoing phase transformation has been one of the classical areas of research among chemists and physicists; dicarboxylic acids are molecular solids that for example exhibit polymorphism. The first few members of the series, except adipic acid, are known to exist in two forms, α and β , the latter being more stable at room temperature. In the β form other than that of malonic acid, the molecule possesses an internal symmetry. In the even members, there is an inversion center on the central C-C bond and the molecule is virtually planar. The odd members have a twofold axis of symmetry through the central carbon atom and the chain is slightly twisted.

All the information about the chemical-physic properties of such ligands are many important because they can give information about their behaviour in the environment (such as the mobility, absorption from mineral, toxicity, etc.).

The information obtained by such studies can serve to delineate correlations between the thermodynamic parameters and the chemical-physics properties of the ligands, such to be able to allow the formulation of mathematical models that facilitates the speciation studies, but that at the same time allows to improve and to facilitate the technologies of treatment of the natural waters, of unloading and of basins particularly polluted.

Here we report the results of a thermal investigation (thermogravimetric and calorimetric) on the dicarboxylic acids belonging to the series $\text{HOOC}-(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{-COOH}$, with $1 \leq n \leq 10$, in order to know their thermal decomposition steps (solid state), and to determine the protonation enthalpies ($\Delta H/\text{J mol}^{-1}$) from calorimetric titrations.

Study of the Thermodynamic Properties of DL-Tyrosine and DL-Tryptophan by Using Different Techniques. Determination of the Protonation Constants, Solubility and Activity Coefficients in NaCl_(aq) and (CH₃)₄NCl_(aq) at Different Ionic Strengths and Temperatures

Clemente BRETTI, Agatino CASALE, Francesco CREA, Giuseppina VIANELLI

*Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica dell'Università,
Viale F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31, 98166 Messina (Vill. S. Agata), Italy*

gvianelli@unime.it

Amino acids are molecules containing at least an amine group, a carboxylic group and a side chain that varies between the different amino acids. Amino acids are critical to life, and have many functions in metabolism; one particularly important function is to serve as the building blocks of proteins. Due to their central role in biochemistry, amino acids are important in nutrition and are commonly used in food technology and industry. Among all the amino acids, tyrosine and tryptophan are two amino acids that contribute to our emotional well-being and mental alertness, as well as participating in a wide variety of other healthful benefits.

Tyrosine is an aromatic nonessential amino acid synthesized from the essential amino acid phenylalanine; it is found in animal meat, wheat products, oatmeal and seafood, and is important to overall metabolic. It is a precursor for several important neurotransmitters (epinephrine, norepinephrine, dopamine), which regulate mood and stimulates metabolism and the nervous system [1-3].

Tryptophan is an essential amino acid provided by food and transported into the brain through the high affinity LAT1/r4F2hc L-system transporter [4]. It increases the amount of serotonin in the brain, allowing crucial "serotonin neural circuits" to function more effectively and with greater reliability. Tryptophan plays a role very important in many biological processes.

Despite these amino acids are very important in the industrial and biological fields, the thermodynamic data concerning their behaviour in aqueous solutions are often confusing [5-7]; therefore from our point of view, it was significant to improve the knowledge on their acid-base properties in solutions containing different supporting electrolytes, such as sodium chloride, which is important in the studies of the component potentially present in biological fluids.

We focused our attention on the determination of the protonation constants both in sodium chloride (NaCl) and tetramethylammonium chloride ((CH₃)₄NCl), at different ionic strengths and in quite different ligand concentrations, by using two different techniques (potentiometry and spectrophotometry). The spectrophotometric measurements for the determination of the protonation constants, were carried out at different temperatures, namely T = 293.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K and at different ionic strengths in NaCl aqueous solutions. This allowed us to calculate the enthalpy and entropy changes associated to the protonation reactions. In order to check the suitability of the enthalpy changes for the protonation of DL-

Tyrosine, some isoperibol calorimetric titrations were made at $T = 298 \text{ K}$ in NaCl aqueous solution at different ionic strengths.

The dependence of protonation constants on ionic strength in the two ionic media was studied by means of both a Debye-Hückel type equation [8, 9] and of the SIT [10-12] (Specific ion Interaction Theory) approach.

As a further investigation, solubility measurements were carried out in both ionic media, in order to determine the total solubility and the solubility of the zwitterionic neutral species, as well as the Setschenow coefficient [13] and the activity coefficients at different ionic strength values.

References:

- [1] Arora, A.; Scholar, E. M. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* **2005**, 315, 971-979.
- [2] Banderet, L. E.; Lieberman, H. R. *Brain Research Bulletin* **1989**, 22, 759-762.
- [3] Patel, R.; Okun, M.; Yee, W.; Wilgram, G.; Edelstein, L. *J. Invest. Dermatol.* **1973**, 61, 55-59.
- [4] Kanai, Y.; Segawa, H.; Miyamoto, K.; Uchino, H.; Takeda, E.; Endou, H. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **1998**, 273, 23629-32.
- [5] Martell, A. E.; Smith, R. M.; Press, P., Ed. New York, 1977; Vol. 3
- [6] May, P. M.; Murray, K. *Joint Expert Speciation System* Murdoch Western Australia 2000.
- [7] Pettit, D. L.; Powell, K. *Stability Constants Database*; IUPAC: Otley, U.K. , 1997.
- [8] Daniele, P. G.; De Robertis, A.; De Stefano, C.; Sammartano, S.; Rigano, C. *Journal of the Chemical Society, Dalton Transactions* **1985**, 2353-2361.
- [9] Daniele, P. G.; Rigano, C.; Sammartano, S. *Analytical Chemistry* **1985**, 57, 2956-2960.
- [10] Brønsted, J. N. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **1922**, 44, 877-898.
- [11] Ciavatta, L. *Ann. Chim. (Rome)* **1980**, 70, 551-567.
- [12] Guggenheim, E. A.; Turgeon, J. C. *Transactions of the Faraday Society* **1955**, 51, 747-761.
- [13] Setschenow, J. *Z. Physik. Chem* **1889**, 4, 117-125.

Potentiometric and voltammetric study on the interaction of Sn²⁺ with phosphate and polycarboxylic ligands in aqueous solution

Daniela CUCINOTTA, Ottavia GIUFFRÈ, Gabriele LANDO, Giuseppe MANFREDI

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica, Università di Messina, Viale Ferdinando Stagno d'Alcontres 31, 98166 Messina, Italy
dcucinotta@unime.it

Tin is used in a very wide variety of industrial applications, often in combination with other elements. The major commercial applications of tin are in tinsplate, solder alloys bearing metals, alloy coatings, pewter, bronzes, and fusible alloys. Tin can also exist as organic compounds (e.g., tributyltin, dimethyltin) that are commonly used in various industrial sectors because of their biocide properties. While the chemistry of organotin compounds has been studied extensively because of their high toxicity toward numerous living organisms, less work has been achieved on the inorganic forms that are generally considered to be non hazardous. Furthermore the chemistry of Sn²⁺ is not well defined also for its rapid oxidation to Sn⁴⁺. The potentiometric study of equilibria of Sn²⁺ in aqueous solution is strongly limited by the hydrolysis, since precipitation already occurs at acidic pH.

For these reasons, a potentiometric and voltammetric study on the interaction of Sn²⁺ with different phosphate ligands, such as phosphate (PO₄), pyrophosphate (PP), tripolyphosphate (TPP), monofluorophosphate (MFP) and adenosine-5 triphosphate (ATP), at *t* = 25°C and different ionic strengths in NaNO₃ was carried out. The results obtained gave evidence of the formation of different stable complexes; phosphate and pyrophosphate ligands form four stable complexes with the metal, namely: MLH₂, MLH, ML and MLOH. The ML is the only common species determined for all the investigated systems.

The interaction of Sn²⁺ with polycarboxylic ligands, such as mellitate (*mlt*), malonic acid (*mal*), 1,2,3,-propanetricarboxylic acid (*tca*), 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid (*btc*), was also studied by potentiometry at *t* = 25°C and different ionic strengths. Among the polycarboxylates, mellitate proved to be a good sequestering agent toward Sn²⁺, since it manages to keep it in solution, allowing measurements to be made in a fairly wide pH range (up to pH ≅ 6). The speciation model showed the formation of MLH, ML and MLOH species. The formation constants of Sn²⁺-*mlt* species showed fairly high stabilities (for example, for ML species, logβ = 10.50 at *I* = 0.15 mol L⁻¹ and *t* = 25°C). As expected, the other polycarboxylates showed a complexing ability lower than *mlt*, so the pH range investigated by potentiometry was smaller (pH ≤ 4.5) than the system containing *mlt*. Speciation models obtained include the following species: MLH and ML, for *mal*; MLH₂, MLH and ML, for *tca*; MLH₃, MLH₂, MLH and ML, for *btc*. Formation constants (logβ), referring to ML species of *mal*, *tca* and *btc*, are in the range about 6 and 8, and the stabilities showed a regular trend as a function of the ligand charge.

Binding ability of reduced glutathione towards $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Sn}^+$, at different temperatures and ionic strengths

Paola CARDIANO, Alessandro DE ROBERTIS, Gabriella FALCONE, Claudia FOTI

*Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica, Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica. Università di
Messina, Via F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31, I-98166, Messina (Vill. S. Agata), Italy
falconeg@unime.it*

Glutathione (γ -L-Glutamyl-L-cysteinylglycine, GSH) is one of the most important and ubiquitous small biomolecules present in cells of all organisms at millimolar concentrations. It possesses a variety of physiological functions and plays a key role in several biochemical processes in the human body and in plants. The interest in the study of glutathione is due to the fact that, despite its structural simplicity, it exhibit a number of roles in detoxification of heavy metal ions, in preventing oxidation stress damages and as a shuttle in transport of metal ions and complexes. Moreover, the knowledge of coordination chemistry of GSH is essential to understand the mechanism of action of phytochelatin, which are important metal chelating bioligands with very relevant roles in prevention of heavy metal ions stress and phytoremediation. The presence in the literature of thermodynamic studies on its binding ability toward many metal and organometal cations published over many years is still not sufficient to give a complete picture of the network of interactions of this ligand, even if it is well-known that these aspects are essential for a thorough understanding of its reactions in natural waters and biological fluids. In particular, very few data are reported on the interaction with organotin(IV) cations ($\text{R}_x\text{Sn}^{(4-x)+}$, with R = alkyl group and $x = 1$ to 3), whose presence in natural ecosystems is derived both from their industrial use and from microbial alkylation processes of the inorganic tin in the presence of detritus organic matter in sediments.

In this work, we investigated the coordination behaviour of GSH in the formation of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Sn}^+$ complexes. Equilibria were studied by potentiometry (ISE- H^+) and ^1H -NMR spectroscopy at $t = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, using NaCl as ionic medium. For both systems, the formation of ML, MLH and MLH₂ species were found [with $\text{M} = (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$ or $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Sn}^+$, and $\text{L} = (\text{GSH})^{3-}$], together with the hydrolytic $\text{ML}(\text{OH})^{2-}$, for dimethyltin(IV) cation only. Formation constant values obtained by the two different instrumental techniques (potentiometry and ^1H -NMR spectroscopy) are in agreement. The dependence of complex formation constants on ionic strength (in the range $0.1 \leq I \leq 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and on temperature (in the range $15 \leq t \leq 45^\circ\text{C}$) was also studied, and rough ΔH values were calculated.

This study is an essential first step in the development of models to predict the alkyltin(IV) cation transport and fate and, moreover, can provide useful information to evaluate methods of removing undesirable compounds from biological systems. With this aim, sequestering ability of GSH towards $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Sn}^+$ was quantitatively evaluated by determining an empirical parameter ($\text{pL}_{0.5}$) that numerically represents the ligand concentration necessary to sequester the 0.5 of metal ion fraction. The $\text{pL}_{0.5}$ values were determined in different conditions of temperature and ionic strength.

Intramolecular Weak Interactions Determining the Thermodynamic Stereoselectivity of Copper(II) Complexes with Carnosine-trehalose Conjugates

**Giuseppa Ida GRASSO,^{a)} Giuseppe ARENA,^{a)} Francesco BELLIA,^{a)}
Giuseppe MACCARRONE,^{a)} Michele PARRINELLO,^{b)} Adriana PIETROPAOLO,^{a,b)}
Graziella VECCHIO,^{a)} Enrico RIZZARELLI^{a)}**

^{a)} *Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università di Catania, v.le A. Doria, 6 –
95125 Catania - Italy*

^{b)} *Computational Science Department of Chemistry and Applied Biosciences, ETH Zurich,
USI-Campus, CH-6900 Lugano – Switzerland*
gigrasso@unict.it

Sugar-peptide interactions play a subtle role in a wide range of fundamental biological processes that include metabolic regulation, growth, embryogenesis, and apoptosis among many others. The mechanisms by which carbohydrates recognize proteins and the specific structural factors determining stereoselectivity (D- sugars vs. L-amino acids) remain a fundamental question in biochemistry[1,2]. Carnosine (β -alanyl-L-histidine) is a naturally occurring dipeptide present in the muscle and brain tissues of humans, and other vertebrates in relatively high concentrations (1-20 mM). Carnosine is synthesized by carnosine synthetase and hydrolyzed in blood plasma by carnosinases[3]. There is a considerable interest in the development of carnosine-related structures with increased metabolic stability[4] in view of their potential therapeutic applications, owing to the role of carnosine in Alzheimer disease, nitrosative and oxidative stress as well as to its ability to complex zinc and copper ions. D-trehalose- conjugated L-carnosine (LCar) resists carnosinase hydrolysis and possesses an antioxidant activity higher than that of L-carnosine[5]. D-trehalose (Tr) has been reported to increase human neuroblastoma cell viability in the presence of A β aggregates and to alleviate the polyglutamine induced symptoms in mouse models of Huntington disease[6]. L-carnosine enantiomer (DCar) is not hydrolyzed by carnosinase and maintains the same quenching activity as L-carnosine in vitro[7], though it does not show the beneficial effects of the L-enantiomer on cultured human fibroblasts.

In view of its potential therapeutic applications we have performed an extensive combined experimental and theoretical investigation of the dimeric Copper(II) complexes with D-trehalose-L-carnosine (TrLCar) and D-trehalose-D-carnosine (TrDCar). The two diastereoisomers, and especially so the dimeric species, are characterized by a significantly different affinity for copper(II) ($\log\beta^L_{22-2} - \log\beta^D_{22-2} = 3.6$). Potentiometric, spectroscopic, isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) measurements and free-energy calculations provide details for the copper-dipeptide interaction allowing for a detailed description of the factors determining the different stability[8].

References:

- [1] Boltje, T. J.; Buskas, T.; Boons, G. J., Opportunities and challenges in synthetic oligosaccharide and glycoconjugate research. *Nat Chem* **2009**, 1, 611-622.
- [2] Corrigan, J. J., D-amino acids in animals. *Science* **1969**, 164, 142-149.
- [3] Bellia F.; Calabrese V.; Guarino F.; Cavallaro M.; Cornelius C.; De Pinto V.; Rizzarelli E., Carnosinase levels in aging brain: redox state induction and cellular stress response. *Antioxid. Redox Signal.* **2009**, 11, 2759-2775.
- [4] Bonomo R. P.; Bruno V.; Conte E.; De Guidi G.; La Mendola D.; Maccarrone G.; Nicoletti F.; Rizzarelli E.; Sortino S.; Vecchio G., Potentiometric, spectroscopic and antioxidant activity studies of SOD mimics containing carnosine. *Dalton Trans.* **2003** 4406-4415.
- [5] Bellia F.; Amorini A. M.; La Mendola D.; Vecchio G.; Tavazzi B.; Giardina B.; Di Pietro V.; Lazzarino G.; Rizzarelli E., New glycosidic derivatives of histidine-containing dipeptides with antioxidant properties and resistant to carnosinase activity. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **2008**, 43, 373-380.
- [6] Tanaka M.; Machida Y.; Niu S.; Ikeda T.; Jana N. R.; Doi H.; Kurosawa M.; Nekooki M.; Nukina N., Trehalose alleviates polyglutamine-mediated pathology in a mouse model of Huntington disease. *Nat. Med.* **2004**, 10, 148-154.
- [7] Vistoli G.; Orioli M.; Pedretti A.; Regazzoni L.; Canevotti R.; Negrisoni G.; Carini M.; Aldini G., Design, Synthesis, and Evaluation of Carnosine Derivatives as Selective and Efficient Sequestering Agents of Cytotoxic Reactive Carbonyl Species. *ChemMedChem* **2009**, 4, 967-975.
- [8] Grasso G. I.; Arena G.; Bellia F.; Maccarrone G.; Parrinello M.; Pietropaolo A.; Vecchio G.; Rizzarelli E., Intramolecular Weak Interactions Determining the Thermodynamic Stereoselectivity of Copper(II) Complexes with Carnosine-trehalose Conjugates. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2011**, in press.

AUTHORS' INDEX

A

<i>Albelda</i>	<i>M. Teresa</i>	<i>OC25</i>
<i>Alberti</i>	<i>Giancarla</i>	<i>OC1, P1, P2</i>
<i>Alibrandi</i>	<i>Giuseppe</i>	<i>P36</i>
<i>Amato</i>	<i>Filippo</i>	<i>OC9</i>
<i>Arelas</i>	<i>Laurinda</i>	<i>OC30</i>
<i>Arena</i>	<i>Giuseppe</i>	<i>OC22, P44</i>
<i>Arranz Mascarós</i>	<i>Paloma</i>	<i>OC7, P3, P6</i>
<i>Astigarraga Allende</i>	<i>Elisa</i>	<i>P23</i>
<i>Aydinoglu</i>	<i>Sabriye</i>	<i>P7</i>

B

<i>Bacco</i>	<i>Dimitri</i>	<i>P34</i>
<i>Badocco</i>	<i>Denis</i>	<i>P17</i>
<i>Barone</i>	<i>Gianpaolo</i>	<i>OC31</i>
<i>Bartrolí</i>	<i>Marc</i>	<i>P28</i>
<i>Basallote</i>	<i>Manuel G.</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>Bazzicalupi</i>	<i>Carla</i>	<i>P6</i>
<i>Beccia</i>	<i>Maria Rosa</i>	<i>OC21</i>
<i>Belda</i>	<i>Raquel</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>Bellia</i>	<i>Francesco</i>	<i>P44</i>
<i>Benetollo</i>	<i>Franco</i>	<i>P19</i>
<i>Bergamaschi</i>	<i>Greta</i>	<i>P36</i>
<i>Bernal-Perez</i>	<i>Eva</i>	<i>OC18</i>
<i>Berto</i>	<i>Silvia</i>	<i>P13</i>
<i>Beyts</i>	<i>Jana</i>	<i>P28</i>
<i>Biancardi</i>	<i>Alessandro</i>	<i>P8</i>
<i>Bianchi</i>	<i>Antonio</i>	<i>P6</i>
<i>Biesuz</i>	<i>Raffaella</i>	<i>OC1, P1, P2</i>
<i>Bismondo</i>	<i>Arturo</i>	<i>P18, P19</i>
<i>Biver</i>	<i>Tarita</i>	<i>OC21, OC23, OC26, P7, P8, P9</i>
<i>Blasco</i>	<i>Salvador</i>	<i>OC24, P33</i>
<i>Bonaduce</i>	<i>Ilaria</i>	<i>OC8</i>
<i>Bramanti</i>	<i>Emilia</i>	<i>OC8</i>
<i>Bretti</i>	<i>Clemente</i>	<i>P41</i>
<i>Bugella-Altamirano</i>	<i>Elena</i>	<i>OC14</i>
<i>Busto</i>	<i>Natalia</i>	<i>OC23, OC26, P11, P12</i>

C

<i>Capelo</i>	<i>Anabela</i>	<i>OC30</i>
<i>Cardiano</i>	<i>Paola</i>	<i>P43</i>
<i>Carrero</i>	<i>Jose Antonio</i>	<i>P22, P24</i>
<i>Casale</i>	<i>Agatino</i>	<i>P41</i>
<i>Castigliuolo</i>	<i>Ignazio</i>	<i>P17</i>

<i>Castillo</i>	<i>Carmen E.</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>Castiñeiras</i>	<i>Alfonso</i>	<i>OC14, P16</i>
<i>Cerrillos</i>	<i>Consuelo</i>	<i>OC27, P32</i>
<i>Chaves</i>	<i>Silvia</i>	<i>OC30</i>
<i>Chiereghin</i>	<i>Sara</i>	<i>P34</i>
<i>Choquesillo Lazarte</i>	<i>Duane</i>	<i>OC14</i>
<i>Cigala</i>	<i>Rosalia Maria</i>	<i>P38, P40</i>
<i>Clares</i>	<i>M. Paz</i>	<i>OC24</i>
<i>Companys</i>	<i>Encarnació</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>Crea</i>	<i>Francesco</i>	<i>P39, P40, P41</i>
<i>Crespo Alonso</i>	<i>Miriam</i>	<i>P14, P15</i>
<i>Crisponi</i>	<i>Guido</i>	<i>P14, P15</i>
<i>Cruz-Gonzalez</i>	<i>Sara</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>Cucinotta</i>	<i>Daniela</i>	<i>P42</i>
<i>Cukrowski</i>	<i>Ignacy</i>	<i>PL1</i>

D

<i>Dacarro</i>	<i>Giacomo</i>	<i>OC1</i>
<i>Dallavalle</i>	<i>Francesco</i>	<i>OC20</i>
<i>Daniele</i>	<i>Pier Giuseppe</i>	<i>P13</i>
<i>David</i>	<i>Calin</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>De Diego</i>	<i>Alberto</i>	<i>P26</i>
<i>De La Torre</i>	<i>Florencio</i>	<i>OC2, P28</i>
<i>De Robertis</i>	<i>Alessandro</i>	<i>P43</i>
<i>De Stefano</i>	<i>Concetta</i>	<i>P38, P39</i>
<i>Dean</i>	<i>Annalisa</i>	<i>P17</i>
<i>Del Castillo</i>	<i>Lucas</i>	<i>OC24</i>
<i>Di Bernardo</i>	<i>Plinio</i>	<i>P18, P19</i>
<i>Di Marco</i>	<i>Valerio</i>	<i>P17</i>
<i>Diaz Fernandez</i>	<i>Yuri</i>	<i>P1</i>
<i>Dollenz</i>	<i>Riccardo</i>	<i>P36</i>
<i>Doménech</i>	<i>Antonio</i>	<i>OC24</i>
<i>Domingo García</i>	<i>María</i>	<i>P4, P5</i>
<i>Domínguez Martín</i>	<i>Alicia</i>	<i>OC14, P15</i>
<i>Duce</i>	<i>Celia</i>	<i>OC8</i>

E

<i>El Bakkali</i>	<i>Hanan</i>	<i>P16</i>
<i>Emma</i>	<i>Giovanni</i>	<i>OC1, P1</i>
<i>Endrizzi</i>	<i>Francesco</i>	<i>P18</i>
<i>Espino</i>	<i>Gustavo</i>	<i>OC23, P12</i>
<i>Esteves</i>	<i>M. Alexandra</i>	<i>OC30</i>
<i>Etxebarria</i>	<i>Nestor</i>	<i>P26</i>

F

<i>Fabbrizzi</i>	<i>Luigi</i>	<i>P36</i>
<i>Falcone</i>	<i>Gabriella</i>	<i>P43</i>
<i>Fdez Ortiz de Vallejuelo</i>	<i>Silvia</i>	<i>P26</i>
<i>Ferencikova</i>	<i>Zuzana</i>	<i>P37</i>
<i>Ferlini</i>	<i>Maria Grazia</i>	<i>P17</i>
<i>Fernández Cuadrado</i>	<i>Luis Ángel</i>	<i>P22, P23, P24</i>
<i>Fiol</i>	<i>Núria</i>	<i>OC2, P28</i>
<i>Fogagnolo</i>	<i>Marco</i>	<i>P34</i>
<i>Foti</i>	<i>Claudia</i>	<i>P43</i>
<i>Frías</i>	<i>Juan</i>	<i>OC25</i>
<i>Furia</i>	<i>Emilia</i>	<i>P29</i>

G

<i>Galceran</i>	<i>Josep</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>Gano</i>	<i>Lurdes</i>	<i>OC30</i>
<i>Gans</i>	<i>Peter</i>	<i>P38</i>
<i>García</i>	<i>Begoña</i>	<i>OC21, OC23, P11, P12</i>
<i>García Gallarín</i>	<i>Celeste</i>	<i>OC7, P3</i>
<i>García-España</i>	<i>Enrique</i>	<i>OC24, OC25, P33</i>
<i>García-Martin</i>	<i>Javier</i>	<i>P3</i>
<i>Gaspar</i>	<i>Jorge F.</i>	<i>OC23</i>
<i>Ghezzi</i>	<i>Lisa</i>	<i>OC8</i>
<i>Giacalone</i>	<i>Alba</i>	<i>P30</i>
<i>Gianguzza</i>	<i>Antonio</i>	<i>P30, P35</i>
<i>Giorgi</i>	<i>Claudia</i>	<i>P6</i>
<i>Giuffrè</i>	<i>Ottavia</i>	<i>P42</i>
<i>Glez Turrion</i>	<i>Raquel</i>	<i>P22, P24</i>
<i>Godfrey</i>	<i>Simon</i>	<i>OC5</i>
<i>Godino Salido</i>	<i>M^a Luz</i>	<i>P4, P5, P6</i>
<i>Goienaga</i>	<i>Naiara</i>	<i>P22, P24</i>
<i>Gomez Laserna</i>	<i>Olivia</i>	<i>P24, P25, P27</i>
<i>González</i>	<i>Jorge</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>González</i>	<i>José Luis</i>	<i>OC9</i>
<i>González Pérez</i>	<i>Josefa María</i>	<i>OC14, P15, P16</i>
<i>Grasso</i>	<i>Giuseppa Ida</i>	<i>P44</i>
<i>Grueso</i>	<i>Elia</i>	<i>OC27, P31, P32</i>
<i>Guiso</i>	<i>Maria Giovanna</i>	<i>OC1, P1, P2</i>
<i>Gutiérrez Valero</i>	<i>María Dolores</i>	<i>P3, P5, P6</i>

H

<i>Havel</i>	<i>Josef</i>	<i>OC9</i>
<i>Höbartner</i>	<i>Claudia</i>	<i>P10</i>

I

<i>Ibarrondo</i>	<i>Irantxe</i>	<i>P25</i>
<i>Inclán</i>	<i>Mario</i>	<i>OC24, OC25, P33</i>
<i>Isaia</i>	<i>Francesco</i>	<i>OC29</i>

J

<i>Jimenez</i>	<i>Antonia</i>	<i>OC23, P11, P12</i>
<i>Jiménez</i>	<i>Hermas R.</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>Jovin</i>	<i>Thomas M.</i>	<i>P10</i>

K

<i>King</i>	<i>Peter</i>	<i>OC12</i>
<i>Kortazar</i>	<i>Leire</i>	<i>P22, P24</i>

L

<i>Lando</i>	<i>Gabriele</i>	<i>P39, P42</i>
<i>Latorre</i>	<i>Julio</i>	<i>OC24</i>
<i>Laurenti</i>	<i>Enzo</i>	<i>P13</i>
<i>Leal</i>	<i>José M.</i>	<i>OC21, OC23, P11, P12</i>
<i>Licchelli</i>	<i>Maurizio</i>	<i>P36</i>
<i>Lim</i>	<i>Choong Sun</i>	<i>OC20</i>
<i>Llinares</i>	<i>José M.</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>Lo Vecchio</i>	<i>Carmelo</i>	<i>P36</i>
<i>Lopes-Costa</i>	<i>Tania</i>	<i>OC17</i>
<i>Lopez Cornejo</i>	<i>Maria del Pilar</i>	<i>OC17, OC26, OC27</i>
<i>López De La Torre</i>	<i>M^a Dolores</i>	<i>P3, P4</i>
<i>López Garzón</i>	<i>Francisco Javier</i>	<i>P3</i>
<i>López Garzón</i>	<i>Javier</i>	<i>OC7</i>
<i>López Garzón</i>	<i>Rafael</i>	<i>P3, P5, P6</i>
<i>Lopez Lopez</i>	<i>Manuel</i>	<i>OC19</i>
<i>Lozano</i>	<i>Héctor</i>	<i>OC23, P11, P12</i>

M

<i>Maccarrone</i>	<i>Giuseppe</i>	<i>P44</i>
<i>Madariaga</i>	<i>Juan Manuel</i>	<i>P22, P24, P25, P26, P27</i>
<i>Maeder</i>	<i>Marcel</i>	<i>OC12</i>
<i>Majlesi</i>	<i>Kavosh</i>	<i>OC10, OC11</i>
<i>Mañez</i>	<i>M. Angeles</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>Manfredi</i>	<i>Giuseppe</i>	<i>P42</i>
<i>Mansoori</i>	<i>Delara</i>	<i>P14</i>
<i>Marchena</i>	<i>María</i>	<i>OC18, OC19</i>
<i>Marini</i>	<i>Alberto</i>	<i>P8</i>
<i>Marques</i>	<i>Sérgio</i>	<i>OC30</i>

<i>Martin Herrera</i>	<i>Victoria Isabel</i>	<i>OC26</i>
<i>Martinez</i>	<i>Jose M.</i>	<i>P20</i>
<i>Martinez Arkarazo</i>	<i>Irantzu</i>	<i>P25, P26, P27</i>
<i>Martins</i>	<i>Célia</i>	<i>OC23</i>
<i>Materazzi</i>	<i>Stefano</i>	<i>P40</i>
<i>Matilla Hernandez</i>	<i>Antonio</i>	<i>P16</i>
<i>May</i>	<i>Peter</i>	<i>OC4</i>
<i>Mazzotti</i>	<i>Fabio</i>	<i>P29</i>
<i>McCann</i>	<i>Nichola</i>	<i>OC12</i>
<i>Medici</i>	<i>Serenella</i>	<i>OC32</i>
<i>Melchior</i>	<i>Andrea</i>	<i>OC28, P19, P20, P21</i>
<i>Melguizo Guijarro</i>	<i>Manuel</i>	<i>OC7, P4</i>
<i>Meloun</i>	<i>Milan</i>	<i>OC13, P37</i>
<i>Mennucci</i>	<i>Benedetta</i>	<i>P8</i>
<i>Milea</i>	<i>Demetrio</i>	<i>P38, P39</i>
<i>Millero</i>	<i>Frank J.</i>	<i>PL2</i>
<i>Mongin</i>	<i>Sandrine</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>Monné</i>	<i>Josep</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>Montilla</i>	<i>Francisco</i>	<i>OC17</i>
<i>Morillas</i>	<i>Héctor</i>	<i>P25</i>
<i>Morillo Martín</i>	<i>D.</i>	<i>OC3</i>

N

<i>Napoli</i>	<i>Anna</i>	<i>P29, P30</i>
<i>Navarrete Casas</i>	<i>Ricardo</i>	<i>P16</i>
<i>Niclós Gutierrez</i>	<i>Juan</i>	<i>OC14, P15, P16</i>
<i>Nikolayenko</i>	<i>Igor Vasyl</i>	<i>OC15</i>
<i>Nurchi</i>	<i>Valeria Marina</i>	<i>P14, P15</i>

O

<i>Olazabal Dueñas</i>	<i>Marian</i>	<i>P23, P25, P26, P27</i>
<i>Olivares</i>	<i>Maitane</i>	<i>P22</i>
<i>Operschall</i>	<i>Bert P.</i>	<i>OC16</i>

P

<i>Pani</i>	<i>Alessandra</i>	<i>OC29</i>
<i>Paoletti</i>	<i>Clara</i>	<i>P9</i>
<i>Pappalardo</i>	<i>Rafael R.</i>	<i>P20</i>
<i>Parrinello</i>	<i>Michele</i>	<i>P44</i>
<i>Pastore</i>	<i>Paolo</i>	<i>P17</i>
<i>Peacock</i>	<i>Anna F. A.</i>	<i>PL3</i>
<i>Peana</i>	<i>Massimiliano</i>	<i>OC32</i>
<i>Pecoraro</i>	<i>Vincent L.</i>	<i>PL3, OC20</i>
<i>Pekarek</i>	<i>Tomáš</i>	<i>P37</i>
<i>Peñas Sanjuán</i>	<i>Antonio</i>	<i>OC7, P5</i>

<i>Peralta</i>	<i>Elena</i>	<i>OC28, P21</i>
<i>Pérez González</i>	<i>G.</i>	<i>OC3</i>
<i>Pérez Mendoza</i>	<i>Manuel</i>	<i>OC7, P4</i>
<i>Pesavento</i>	<i>Maria</i>	<i>P2</i>
<i>Pettignano</i>	<i>Alberto</i>	<i>P35</i>
<i>Piazzese</i>	<i>Daniela</i>	<i>P30</i>
<i>Pietropaolo</i>	<i>Adriana</i>	<i>P44</i>
<i>Pilla</i>	<i>Federica</i>	<i>OC29</i>
<i>Pitarch</i>	<i>Javier</i>	<i>P33</i>
<i>Pivetta</i>	<i>Tiziana</i>	<i>OC29</i>
<i>Poch</i>	<i>Jordi</i>	<i>OC2, P28</i>
<i>Prado Gotor</i>	<i>Rafael</i>	<i>OC26, P31, P32</i>
<i>Prencipi</i>	<i>Enrico</i>	<i>P13</i>
<i>Prieto Taboada</i>	<i>Nagore</i>	<i>P25, P26, P27</i>
<i>Pujol Oriola</i>	<i>David</i>	<i>OC2</i>
<i>Puy</i>	<i>Jaume</i>	<i>OC6</i>

R

<i>Rao</i>	<i>Linfeng</i>	<i>P18, P19</i>
<i>Raymond</i>	<i>Kenneth N.</i>	<i>OC22</i>
<i>Remelli</i>	<i>Maurizio</i>	<i>OC20, OC21, P34</i>
<i>Rey-Castro</i>	<i>Carlos</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>Rezaiejad</i>	<i>Saghar</i>	<i>OC10, OC11</i>
<i>Rizzarelli</i>	<i>Enrico</i>	<i>P44</i>
<i>Rowland</i>	<i>Darren</i>	<i>OC4</i>

S

<i>Saez Castaño</i>	<i>Janire</i>	<i>P23</i>
<i>Salvador</i>	<i>José</i>	<i>OC6</i>
<i>Sammartano</i>	<i>Silvio</i>	<i>P35, P38, P39</i>
<i>Sánchez Burgos</i>	<i>Francisco</i>	<i>OC17, O18, OC19</i>
<i>Sánchez Marcos</i>	<i>Enrique</i>	<i>P20</i>
<i>Santiago Medina</i>	<i>Antonio</i>	<i>P4, P5</i>
<i>Santos</i>	<i>M. Amélia</i>	<i>OC30</i>
<i>Sarmiento</i>	<i>Alfredo</i>	<i>P22</i>
<i>Scopelliti</i>	<i>Michelangelo</i>	<i>P39</i>
<i>Secco</i>	<i>Fernando</i>	<i>OC21, OC26, P7, P8, P9</i>
<i>Sgarlata</i>	<i>Carmelo</i>	<i>OC22</i>
<i>Sigel</i>	<i>Helmut</i>	<i>OC16</i>
<i>Sigel</i>	<i>Astrid</i>	<i>OC16</i>
<i>Sindona</i>	<i>Giovanni</i>	<i>P29</i>
<i>Soriano</i>	<i>Concepción</i>	<i>OC24, P33</i>
<i>Spepi</i>	<i>Alessio</i>	<i>OC8</i>
<i>Spinelli</i>	<i>Jacopo</i>	<i>OC26</i>
<i>Spinello</i>	<i>Angelo</i>	<i>OC31</i>

Stuckey *Jeanne* *PL3*

T

Tagarelli *Antonio* *P29*
Taglietti *Angelo* *OC1, P1*
Tavagnacco *Claudio* *OC28*
Tegoni *Matteo* *PL3, OC20, OC21*
Tejero *Roberto* *P33*
Terenzi *Alessio* *OC31*
Theron *Thomas John* *OC15*
Tinë *Maria Rosaria* *OC8*
Tolazzi *Marilena* *OC28, P19, P21*
Toso *Leonardo* *P14, P15*
Turriani *Elisa* *P10*

V

Valiente Malmagro *Manuel* *OC3, OC28, P21*
Vecchio *Graziella* *P44*
Venturini *Marcella* *OC21, OC26, P7, P9*
Verdejo *Begoña* *OC24, P33*
Vianelli *Giuseppina* *P41*
Villaescusa *Isabel* *OC2, P28*

Y

Yokel *Robert A.* *P17*
Yu *Fangting* *PL3*

Z

Zanonato *Pier Luigi* *P18, P19*
Zarza *Cristina* *P26*
Zastrow *Melissa* *PL3*
Zoroddu *Maria Antonietta* *OC32*

LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

ALBERTI, Giancarla

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università di Pavia
via Taramelli 12
27100 Pavia, ITALY
galberti@unipv.it

AMATO, Filippo

Department of Chemistry, Masaryk University, Kampus
Bohunice, Kamenice 5/A14
Room 330, A1 block, Vinarska 5
60300 Brno CZECH REPUBLIC
389626@mail.muni.cz

ARRANZ MASCARÓS, Paloma

Departamento de Química Inorgánica y Orgánica,
Universidad de Jaén
Campus Las Lagunillas
23071, Jaén, SPAIN
parranz@ujaen.es

BARONE, Giampaolo

Dipartimento di Chimica "S. Cannizzaro"
Università di Palermo
Viale delle Scienze Edificio 17
90128 Palermo, ITALY
gbarone@unipa.it

BERNAL PÉREZ, Eva

Departamento de Química Física,
Facultad de Química
Universidad de Sevilla
C/ Profesor García González S/N,
41012 Sevilla, SPAIN
evabernal@us.es

BIANCHI, Antonio

Dipartimento di Chimica "Ugo Schiff"
Università degli Studi di Firenze
Via della Lastruccia, 3
50019 Sesto Fiorentino, ITALY
antonio.bianchi@unifi.it

BIVER, Tarita

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale
Università di Pisa
Via Risorgimento, 35
56126 Pisa, ITALY
tarita@dcc.unipi.it

ALIBRANDI, Giuseppe

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
galibrandi@unime.it

ARENA, Giuseppe

Department of Chemical Sciences,
University of Catania
Viale Andrea Doria 6
95125 Catania, ITALY
garena@unict.it

AYDINOGLU, Sabriye

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale
Università di Pisa
Via Risorgimento, 35
56126 Pisa, ITALY
s.aydinoglu@ns.dcci.unipi.it

BECCIA, Maria Rosa

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale
Università di Pisa
Via Risorgimento, 35
56126 Pisa, ITALY
marosa@ns.dcci.unipi.it

BERTO, Silvia

Dipartimento di Chimica Analitica
Università di Torino
Via Pietro Giuria 5
10125 Torino, ITALY
silvia.berto@unito.it

BIESUZ, Raffaella

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università di Pavia
via Taramelli 12
27100 Pavia, ITALY
rbiesuz@unipv.it

BLASCO, Salvador

Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol)
Departamento de Química Inorgánica
Universidad de Valencia,
C\ Catedrático José Beltrán nº 2,
46980, Paterna, Valencia, SPAIN
salvador.blasco@uv.es

BRETTI, Clemente

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
cbretti@unime.it

CASALE, Agatino

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
acasale@unime.it

CREA, Francesco

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
fcreea@unime.it

CRISPONI, Guido

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Cittadella Universitaria
09042 Monserrato – Cagliari, ITALY
crisponi@unica.it

CUKROWSKI, Ignacy

Department of Chemistry
University of Pretoria
Lynnwood Road
0002 Pretoria, SOUTH AFRICA
ignacy.cukrowski@up.ac.za

DE ROBERTIS, Alessandro

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
aderobertis@unime.it

DEAN, Annalisa

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università di Padova
via Marzolo 1,
35131 Padova, ITALY
annalisa.dean@unipd.it

BUSTO, Natalia

Departamento de Química
Universidad de Burgos,
Pza. Misael Bañuelos s/n
09001 Burgos, SPAIN
nataliabyv@msn.com

CIGALA, Rosalia Maria

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
rmcigala@unime.it

CRESPO ALONSO, Miriam

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Cittadella Universitaria
09042 Monserrato – Cagliari, ITALY
mrm_crespo@hotmail.com

CUCINOTTA, Daniela

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
dcucinotta@unime.it

DANIELE, Pier Giuseppe

Dipartimento di Chimica Analitica
Università di Torino
Via Pietro Giuria 5
10125 Torino, ITALY
piergiuseppe.daniele@unito.it

DE STEFANO, Concetta

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
cdestefano@unime.it

DI BERNARDO, Plinio

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università di Padova
via Marzolo 1,
35131 Padova, ITALY
plinio.dibernardo@unipd.it

DOMINGUEZ-MARTIN, Alicia

Department of Inorganic Chemistry
Faculty of Pharmacy
University of Granada
Campus Cartuja
18071 Granada, SPAIN
adominguez@ugr.es

FALCONE, Gabriella

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
falconeg@unime.it

FERNÁNDEZ CUADRADO, Luis Ángel

Department of Analytical Chemistry,
University of The Basque Country,
Faculty of Science and Technology,
P.O. Box 644,
48080 Bilbao, SPAIN
luis-angel.fernandez@ehu.es

FOTI, Claudia

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
cfoti@unime.it

GANS, Peter

Protonic Software
2, Templegate Avenue
LS15 0HD Leeds, UNITED KINGDOM
peter.gans@hyperquad.co.uk

GARCÍA-ESPAÑA, Enrique

Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol)
Departamento de Química Inorgánica
Universidad de Valencia,
C\ Catedrático José Beltrán nº 2,
46980, Paterna, Valencia, SPAIN
enrique.garcia-es@uv.es

GIACALONE, Alba

Dipartimento di Chimica "S. Cannizzaro"
Università di Palermo
Viale delle Scienze Edificio 17
90128 Palermo, ITALY
agiacalone@unipa.it

EMMA, Giovanni

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università di Pavia
via Taramelli 12
27100 Pavia, ITALY
giovanni.emma@libero.it

FERENČÍKOVÁ, Zuzana

Department of Analytical Chemistry
Faculty of Chemical Technology
University of Pardubice
CZ-532 10 Pardubice, CZECH REPUBLIC
zuzka.ferencikova@seznam.cz

FIOL, Nuria

Chemical Engineering Department
Escola Politècnica Superior
Universitat de Girona
Avda. Lluís Santaló, s/n,
17071 Girona, SPAIN
nuria.fiol@udg.edu

FURIA, Emilia

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università della Calabria
Via Pietro Bucci, Cubo 12/C
87036 Arcavacata di Rende (CS), ITALY
e.furia@unical.it

GARCÍA, Begoña

Departamento de Química
Universidad de Burgos,
Pza. Misael Bañuelos s/n
09001 Burgos, SPAIN
begar@ubu.es

GHEZZI, Lisa

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale
Università di Pisa
Via Risorgimento, 35
56126 Pisa, ITALY
lisa@ns.dcci.unipi.it

GIANGUZZA, Antonio

Dipartimento di Chimica "S. Cannizzaro"
Università di Palermo
Viale delle Scienze Edificio 17
90128 Palermo, ITALY
giang@unipa.it

GIUFFRE', Ottavia

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
ogiuffre@unime.it

GODINO SALIDO, M^a Luz

Departamento de Química Inorgánica y Orgánica,
Universidad de Jaén
Campus Las Lagunillas
23071, Jaén, SPAIN
mlgodino@ujaen.es

GRUESO, Elia María

Departamento de Química Física,
Facultad de Química
Universidad de Sevilla
C/ Profesor García González S/N,
41012 Sevilla, SPAIN
elia@us.es

GUTIÉRREZ VALERO, Maria Dolores

Departamento de Química Inorgánica y Orgánica,
Universidad de Jaén
Campus Las Lagunillas
23071, Jaén, SPAIN
mdgutie@ujaen.es

LANDO, Gabriele

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
glando@unime.it

LLINARES BERENGUER, Jose Miguel

Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol)
Departamento de Química Inorgánica
Universidad de Valencia,
C\ Catedrático José Beltrán nº 2,
46980, Paterna, Valencia, SPAIN
jollibe@uv.es

MAEDER, Marcel

Department of Chemistry
University of Newcastle
NSW 2308 Newcastle, AUSTRALIA
marcel.maeder@newcastle.edu.au

GODFREY, Simon

Procter and Gamble
London Innovation Centre
TW20 9NW Egham, UNITED KINGDOM
godfrey.s@pg.com

GRASSO, Giuseppa Ida

Department of Chemical Sciences,
University of Catania
Viale Andrea Doria 6
95125 Catania, ITALY
gigrasso@unict.it

GUIISO, Maria Giovanna

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università di Pavia
via Taramelli 12
27100 Pavia, ITALY
maria.guiso@unipv.it

INCLÁN, Mario

Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol)
Departamento de Química Inorgánica
Universidad de Valencia,
C\ Catedrático José Beltrán nº 2,
46980, Paterna, Valencia, SPAIN
mario.inclan@uv.es

LEAL, José M.

Departamento de Química
Universidad de Burgos,
Pza. Misael Bañuelos s/n
09001 Burgos, SPAIN
jmleal@ubu.es

LO VECCHIO, Carmelo

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
clovecchio@unime.it

MAJLESI, Kavosh

Department of Chemistry
Science and Research Branch
Islamic Azad University
Pounack, Ashrafi Esfahani, Hesarak
1477893855 Tehran, IRAN
kavoshmajlesi@gmail.com

MANFREDI, Giuseppe

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
gmanfredi@unime.it

MARCHENA, Maria

Departamento de Química Física,
Facultad de Química
Universidad de Sevilla
C/ Profesor García González S/N,
41012 Sevilla, SPAIN
marijose@us.es

MAZZOTTI, Fabio

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università della Calabria
Via Pietro Bucci, Cubo 12/C
87036 Arcavacata di Rende (CS), ITALY
fmazzotti@unical.it

MELOUN, Milan

Department of Analytical Chemistry
Faculty of Chemical Technology
University of Pardubice
CZ-532 10 Pardubice, CZECH REPUBLIC
milan.meloun@upce.cz

MILLERO, Frank

Rosenstiel School of Marine and Atmospheric Science
University of Miami,
4600 Rickenbacker Causeway
33149-1031 Miami, USA
fmillero@rsmas.miami.edu

NIKOLAYENKO, Igor Vasyl

School of Chemistry (Pietermaritzburg)
University of KwaZulu-Natal
Private Bag X01,
3209 Scottsville, Pietermaritzburg, SOUTH AFRICA
nikolaenko@ukzn.ac.za

OLAZABAL DUEÑAS, Marian

Department of Analytical Chemistry,
University of The Basque Country,
Faculty of Science and Technology,
P.O. Box 644,
48080 Bilbao, SPAIN
marian.olazabal@ehu.es

MANSOORI, Delara

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Cittadella Universitaria
09042 Monserrato – Cagliari, ITALY
dely88@hotmail.it

MATERAZZI, Stefano

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università di Roma "La Sapienza"
p.le A.Moro 5
00185 Roma, ITALY
stefano.materazzi@uniroma1.it

MELCHIOR, Andrea

Dipartimento di Chimica Fisica e Ambiente
Università di Udine
Via Cottonificio 108
33100 Udine, ITALY
andrea.melchior@uniud.it

MILEA, Demetrio

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
dmilea@unime.it

NICLÓS GUTIÉRREZ, Juan

Department of Inorganic Chemistry
Faculty of Pharmacy
University of Granada
Campus Cartuja
18071 Granada, SPAIN
jniclos@ugr.es

NURCHI, Valeria Marina

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Cittadella Universitaria
09042 Monserrato – Cagliari, ITALY
nurchi@unica.it

PEANA, Massimiliano Francesco

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università di Sassari
Via Vienna 2
07041 Sassari, ITALY
peana@uniss.it

PECORARO, Vincent L.

Department of Chemistry
University of Michigan,
930 N. University Ave.,
MI 48109-1055 Ann Arbor, USA
vlpec@umich.edu

PERALTA, Elena

Dipartimento di Chimica Fisica e Ambiente
Università di Udine
Via Cottonificio 108
33100 Udine, ITALY
elena.peralta@uniud.it

PIAZZESE, Daniela

Dipartimento di Chimica "S. Cannizzaro"
Università di Palermo
Viale delle Scienze Edificio 17
90128 Palermo, ITALY
danielap@unipa.it

PUJOL ORIOLA, David

Chemical Engineering Department
Escola Politècnica Superior
Universitat de Girona
Avda. Lluís Santaló, s/n,
17071 Girona, SPAIN
davidpujol@udg.edu

REY-CASTRO, Carlos

Departament de Química
University of Lleida
ETSEA, Av. Rovira Roure 191
25198 Lleida, SPAIN
carlos.rey@quimica.udl.es

ROMANO, Vincenzo

Dipartimento di Chimica "S. Cannizzaro"
Università di Palermo
Viale delle Scienze Edificio 17
90128 Palermo, ITALY
viromano1938@libero.it

SAMMARTANO, Silvio

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
ssammartano@unime.it

PEÑAS SANJUÁN, Antonio

Departamento de Química Inorgánica y Orgánica,
Universidad de Jaén
Campus Las Lagunillas
23071, Jaén, SPAIN
apenas@ujaen.es

PETTIGNANO, Alberto

Dipartimento di Chimica "S. Cannizzaro"
Università di Palermo
Viale delle Scienze Edificio 17
90128 Palermo, ITALY
pettignano@unipa.it

PIVETTA, Tiziana

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Cittadella Universitaria
09042 Monserrato – Cagliari, ITALY
tpivetta@unica.it

REMELLI, Maurizio

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università di Ferrara,
Via L. Borsari 46,
44121, Ferrara, ITALY
rmm@unife.it

REZAIENEJAD, Saghar

Department of Chemistry
Science and Research Branch
Islamic Azad University
Pounack, Ashrafi Esfahani, Hesarak
1477893855 Tehran, IRAN
sagharrezaienejad@gmail.com

ROWLAND, Darren

School of Chemical and Mathematical Sciences
Murdoch University,
South St
6150 Murdoch, AUSTRALIA
d.rowland@murdoch.edu.au

SANCHEZ BURGOS, Francisco

Departamento de Química Física,
Facultad de Química,
Universidad de Sevilla
C/ Profesor García González S/N,
41012 Sevilla, SPAIN
gcjrv@us.es

SANTOS, Maria Amelia

Instituto Superior Técnico,
Centro de Química Estrutural
Univ. Tecn. Lisboa
IST, Av Rovisco Pais, 1
1049-001 Lisboa, PORTUGAL
masantos@ist.utl.pt

SGARLATA, Carmelo

Department of Chemical Sciences,
University of Catania
Viale Andrea Doria 6
95125 Catania, ITALY
sgarlata@unict.it

SIGEL, Helmut

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry,
University of Basel
Spitalstrasse 51,
CH-4056 Basel, SWITZERLAND
helmut.sigel@unibas.ch

TEGONI, Matteo

Dipartimento di Chimica Generale ed Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica, Chimica Fisica
Università di Parma
Parco Area delle Scienze 17A
43124 Parma, ITALY
matteo.tegoni@unipr.it

TOSO, Leonardo

Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche
Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Cittadella Universitaria
09042 Monserrato – Cagliari, ITALY
xeron08@hotmail.it

VALIENTE MALMAGRO, Manuel

Department of Chemistry.
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
Centre GTS. Campus de la UAB. Edifici CN
08193 Bellaterra, SPAIN
Manuel.Valiente@uab.es

VIANELLI, Giuseppina

Dipartimento di Chimica Inorganica,
Chimica Analitica e Chimica Fisica
Università di Messina
V.le F. Stagno d'Alcontres 31
98166 Messina, ITALY
gvianelli@unime.it

SECCO, Fernando

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale
Università di Pisa
Via Risorgimento, 35
56126 Pisa, ITALY
ferdi@dcci.unipi.it

SIGEL, Astrid

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry,
University of Basel
Spitalstrasse 51,
CH-4056 Basel, SWITZERLAND
astrid.sigel@unibas.ch

TAGARELLI, Antonio

Dipartimento di Chimica
Università della Calabria
Via Pietro Bucci, Cubo 12/C
87036 Arcavacata di Rende (CS), ITALY
a.tagarelli@unical.it

TOLAZZI, Marilena

Dipartimento di Chimica Fisica e Ambiente
Università di Udine
Via Cottonificio 108
33100 Udine, ITALY
marilena.tolazzi@uniud.it

TURRIANI, Elisa

Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa
Piazza dei Cavalieri 7
56126 Pisa, ITALY
elisa.turriani@sns.it

VENTURINI, Marcella

Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale
Università di Pisa
Via Risorgimento, 35
56126 Pisa, ITALY
marcella@dcci.unipi.it

Sponsored by:

P&G

HORIBA
Scientific

STR Servizio Turistico Regionale di Giardini Naxos